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List of abbreviations

ADL	Activities of Daily Living
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-PMP	AI-based Progression and Medication response Prediction
AI-PRA	AI-PROGNOSIS PD Risk Assessment Study
AMP-PD	Accelerating Medicines Partnership in PD
AUROC	Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
BRFC	Balanced Random Forest Classifier
COMT	Catechol-O-Methyltransferase
CPP	Critical Path for Parkinson's Integrated Database
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
DaTscan	Dopamine Transporter Scan
DiSE	Disease State Embedding
dBM	Digital Biomarker
EOD	Early Onset Disease
ESS	Epworth Sleepiness scale
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
HC	Healthy Controls
ICC	Intraclass Correlation Coefficient
LEDD	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose
LIME	Local Interpretable Model Explanations
LLM	Large Language models
LOSO	Leave One Subject Out
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorders Society – Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
MI-CLAIM	Minimum Information about Clinical Artificial Intelligence Modelling Checklist
ML	Machine Learning

MLP	MultiLayer Perceptron
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive assessment
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PDBP	Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PIGD	Postural Instability and Gait Difficulty
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative
PR-AUC	Precision Recall Area Under the Curve
PRS	Polygenic Risk Score
PSG	Polysomnography
PwPD	People with PD
QUIP	Questionnaire for Impulsive Compulsive Disorders in PD
RBD	REM Sleep Behavior Disorder
RBDSQ	REM Sleep Behavior Disorder Screening Questionnaire
RF	Random Forest
RFECV	Recursive Feature Elimination wit Cross Validation
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SAA	α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay
SAM-PD	Sleep and Activity Metrics PD score
SBR	Specific Binding Ratio
SCOPA-AUT	Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease - Autonomic Dysfunction
SCOPA-CG	Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease - Cognitive
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over sampling Technique
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
TRIPOD-AI	Transparent Reporting of a multivariate prediction models for Individual Prognosis Or Diagnosis - AI extension
UPSIT	University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test
UKBB	UK BioBank

Executive summary

The deliverable D3.4 is an update of D3.2 and the final version of predictive modelling for PD. The report provides an overview of all methodologies, findings and future directions of the AI-PROGNOSIS predictive models for Parkinson's disease (PD). Identically to D3.2, the deliverable builds upon multimodal datasets and focuses on three main pillars of prognostic modelling: a) estimation of the risk of developing PD, b) estimation of progression in PD, and c) estimation of response to medication. Further, genetic analysis of Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) constituted a foundational component to quantify genetic susceptibility, in terms of both disease risk and progression, and inform the predictive models.

The final version of predictive modelling for PD focuses on three key objectives, i.e., improving model performance, evaluating results against independent datasets, and ensuring the trustworthiness and explainability of the modelling outcomes. Therefore, these efforts pave the way to improve the reliability and clinical utility of predictive models for PD. This leads to more accurate and generalizable predictions, ensuring confidence among clinicians and patients, ultimately supporting better decision-making and patient outcomes.

The modelling framework followed the TRIPOD-AI guidelines to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and clinical relevance. Three core predictive models were developed alongside a comprehensive genetic analysis pipeline:

Genetic analysis: The genetic analysis used data from the AMP-PD repository, confirming through Fastpop that most participants are of European ancestry. Two polygenic risk score (PRS) models for Parkinson's disease (PD) were calculated based on previously published SNP sets, producing comparable results, though the model derived from the more recent study yielded a higher odds ratio distinguishing PD cases from healthy controls. Additional PRS analyses examined genetic contributions to PD progression using multiple SNP sources and several clinical and data-driven progression definitions. Across all progression models and cluster approaches, no significant associations were found between PRS values and PD progression categories.

PD risk prediction modelling: Using wrist wearable sensor data, a model was developed to estimate the probability of having PD based on sleep and activity metrics in combination with demographic and anthropometric features (SAM-PD risk score). The SAM-PD risk model is combined with the established Movement Disorders Society (MDS) prodromal PD risk model, taking into account clinico-demographics and lifestyle factors, to form a PD screening system. The SAM-PD risk model has been developed and tested (including its combination with the MDS risk model) using data from the Verily Study Watch cohort [Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) sub study]. Feature extraction was focused on three domains: a) sleep, b) slowness of movement and c) physical activity. More than 30 features were extracted from raw acceleration data and were subjected to feature selection, with the retained set being used to train and calibrate a binary balanced Random Forest classifier. Internal validation yielded robust discrimination between persons with PD and unaffected individuals, while validation in an at-risk group showed strong association of the SAM-PD risk score with dopaminergic deficit (measured via DaTscan) and α -synuclein SAA positivity, both hallmarks of the disease. Thorough explainability and test-retest analysis revealed that sleep metrics, mostly REM phase-related, and key slowness of movement and physical activity features were among the top predictors, with good to excellent reliability when estimated monthly. The SAM-PD risk model was found to perform best for individuals 55 to 74 years old, regardless of biological sex, with a body-mass index of 25.0-29.9 kg/m².

PD progression modelling: PD progression modelling combined two complementary approaches to capture interpretable and dynamic aspects of disease evolution, both short- (within a year) and long-term. The short-term approach defined clinically meaningful yearly progression milestones and further discovered data-driven progression subtypes via

clustering. It then used supervised machine learning (Random Forests) to predict those outcomes based on baseline clinicodemographic data combined with wearable-derived sleep and activity metrics captured close to baseline. This approach was developed and tested on the PPMI dataset, including the Verily Study Watch cohort. Supervised models achieved strong accuracy and fairness across age and sex groups. The second, long-term approach, namely “PDualNet”, employed a transformer-based deep learning approach that learned progression subtypes and estimated future MDS-UPDRS scores based on one or more clinicodemographic snapshots of a subject. Trained on the PPMI and tested on the PDBP dataset, the model outperformed baseline models and generalized across cohorts, offering interpretable SHAP explanations. Further, this approach showcased a link between cognitive and motor decline to faster disease progression.

PD Medication response model: Using data from the Critical Path for Parkinson’s Harmonised Database (CPP) of observational studies and clinical trials, individual based variability in dopaminergic therapy side effects were explored, with particular focus on dyskinesia, hallucinations and excessive daytime sleepiness. Given the features derived from a certain visit from a certain subject and the scheduled medication regimen, the risk of each of these side effects occurring by the next visit are estimated to provide a quantitative tool to guide clinical decision-making. The models are extensively evaluated across multiple classification and calibration metrics, and both in within- and cross-dataset settings to validate their generalization properties. Our results indicate the risk of the considered side effects can be predicted with reasonable performance and are robust when validated on data unseen during training. SHAP-derived feature explanations indicate the employed features align with clinical expectations and fairness metrics did not indicate significant biases towards specific demographic populations.

Overall, this deliverable demonstrates significant progress toward developing transparent, fair, and clinically meaningful AI models for PD. The integration of multimodal data, including genetics, clinical records, and digital biomarkers provided robust analytical pipelines for estimating PD risk, progression, and response to medication. These advances highlight the potential of AI-PROGNOSIS algorithms to transform PD management through early detection, individualised prognosis, and data-driven treatment optimisation, paving the way for real-world validation in prospective clinical studies.

1 Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a complex and progressive neurodegenerative disorder that affects ~6.2 million individuals globally¹, with 1.2 million of them residing in Europe². PD diagnosis and monitoring are significantly challenging due to the broad range of motor and non-motor symptoms. There is currently no cure for PD, and the dopaminergic medication is used mainly for managing symptoms. This highlights the necessity for advanced predictive models that can aid in screening, prognosis and estimation of the effects of PD treatment regimes.

Digital biomarkers (dBMs) are revolutionizing the landscape of neurodegenerative disorders including PD. The development of such biomarkers relies on the analysis of large-scale, multisource retrospectively collected datasets such as the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI)³, the UK Biobank (UKBB)⁴, the (Critical Path for Parkinson's (CPP) Data Archive)⁵ and the Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP)⁶. Such datasets often include in-depth clinicodemographic, imaging, genetic (Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms; SNPs that can be combined into Polygenic Risk Scores; PRSs), wearable sensor data and other datasets, longitudinally collected, constituting useful resources for developing models that can offer insights for the disease manifestation and management.

Machine learning and Artificial intelligence (ML/AI) algorithms have been applied to multisource data with the ultimate aim of developing robust biomarkers (for an extensive review, refer to *D2.4 Updated report on domain review and datasets*). Previous work has demonstrated that the analysis of clinicodemographic, imaging, genetics and wearable data can predict the PD onset seven years before its first clinical diagnosis, promising a valuable tool for disease management (Schalkamp et al., 2023). Machine learning has also been used in studies aiming to develop new biomarkers for specific symptoms, such as bradykinesias (Iakovakis et al., 2018), to track disease progression (Severson et al., 2021; Sotirakis et al., 2023), while the utility of ML to estimating the response to medication in people with PD (PwPD), remains widely unexplored. Analysing large datasets allows us to discover patterns and identify key risk factors contributing to the development of the disease.

1.1 Document scope

This deliverable aims to collectively present all methodologies and results from AI-PROGNOSIS research on predictive modelling in PD following a novel, trustworthy and inclusive approach to AI model development. To report the methods and findings of the studies outlined in this document and report the model development and evaluation we examined the guidelines of two checklists, namely the Minimum Information About Clinical Artificial Intelligence Modelling (MI-CLAIM)⁷ and the TRIPOD-AI guidelines⁸ (Sections 5-7). Here, we followed the TRIPOD-AI guidelines the principles of which overlap with MI-CLAIM, ensuring transparent reporting. The developed models will be externally validated in the AI-PROGNOSIS forthcoming clinical studies (AI-PRA and AI-PMP). For the purposes of this deliverable, we analysed data from open, multimodal datasets (PPMI, PDBP, CPP and AMP-PD) to develop and evaluate three types of models: 1) PD risk prediction models, 2) PD progression models, and 3) models predicting response to PD medication.

1 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6311367/>

2 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6191528/>

3 <https://www.ppmi-info.org>

4 <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk>

5 <https://c-path.org>

6 <https://pdbp.ninds.nih.gov>

7 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-020-1041-y>

8 <https://www.bmj.com/content/385/bmj-2023-078378>

- **PD risk estimation:** Aims to estimate the risk of PD by classifying between PwPD and healthy controls (HC) using a rich set of wrist wearable-based sleep and activity metrics (SAM-PD risk score) and combining the output probability with the probability of prodromal PD estimated by the MDS risk model, considering clinico-demographic and lifestyle information. We used data collected with the Verily study watch⁹ from the relevant cohort of the PPMI study. The model outcomes are further validated in an at-risk group using DaTscan and α -synuclein SAA-based ground truth. Key updates of this approach since D3.2 include: a) calculation of a new feature set from the raw smartwatch data that comprehensively represents physical activity, slowness of movement, and sleep, along with SAM-PD risk model retraining and calibration, b) comparison of the SAM-PD risk score against the MDS risk score, c) evaluation of performance of the SAM-PD risk score and of various combinations with the MDS risk score in terms of detecting the presence and extent of dopaminergic deficit reflected by the putamen specific binding ratio (SBR) and of positive α -synuclein SAA result, d) dataset and performance bias assessment, e) extensive explainability and test-retest reliability analysis.

- **PD progression estimation:** PD progression modelling combined two complementary approaches to capture interpretable and dynamic aspects of disease evolution, both short-(within a year) and long-term. The short-term approach defined clinically meaningful yearly progression milestones and further discovered data-driven progression subtypes via clustering. It then used supervised machine learning (Random Forests) to predict those outcomes based on baseline clinicodemographic data combined with wearable-derived sleep and activity metrics captured close to baseline. This approach was developed and tested on the PPMI dataset, including the Verily Study Watch cohort. Supervised models achieved strong accuracy and fairness across age and sex groups. The second, long-term approach, namely “PDualNet”, employed a transformer-based deep learning approach that learned progression subtypes and estimated future MDS-UPDRS scores based on one or more clinicodemographic snapshots of a subject. Trained on the PPMI and tested on the PDBP dataset, the model outperformed baseline models and generalized across cohorts, offering interpretable SHAP explanations. Further, this approach showcased a link between cognitive and motor decline to faster disease progression.

- **PD response to medication:** As individual responses to PD medication can vary, our predictive models aim to predict the risk of adverse effects of dopaminergic therapy, including dyskinesias, hallucinations and excessive daytime sleepiness. Random forest models take as input features from a specific visit, such as demographics, clinical test scores and scheduled medication regimen, and predicts the probability of each of the adverse effects occurring by the next visit. Updates of this approach include a thorough analysis of multiple performance metrics of the developed models on three different PD dataset. This includes cross-dataset performance to assess generalization to new datasets, joint dataset performance to quantify advantages of pooling different datasets, SHAP explanations of the most relevant features, calibration, and fairness and bias assessment.

- **Genetic analysis:** PRS per individual are calculated with the overall aim to be provided as input to the modelling process and will be used as one of the predictors of PD risk, disease progression and response to medication at a later stage. Updates of this approach, present in this report include a) ancestry assessment, b) association analysis of new reported PD-associated SNPs, c) PD-risk PRS calculation using data from a new published study, d) PD-progression PRS calculation.

- **AI Trustworthiness:** To ensure robust, reliable and clinically meaningful predictions, this deliverable also addresses the integration of trustworthy AI principles into developing the predictive models.

⁹ <https://verily.com/perspectives/introducing-verily-study-watch>

D3.4 'Final report on predictive modelling for PD' is the outcome of the tasks T3.3 *Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis*, T3.4 *PD risk predictive modelling*, T3.5 *PD progression predictive modelling* and T3.6 *Medication response predictive modelling*. D3.4 represents an update in model development report, to D3.2 'First report on predictive modelling for PD' where the utility of AI approaches in identifying predictive biomarkers, stratifying PwPD based on subtypes, and estimating clinical outcomes in PD was first demonstrated.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable provides a comprehensive report of predictive modelling in PD for progression, risk assessment, medication response, and genetic profiling, structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction, including the theoretical background
- Section 2 covers the essential aspects of developing trustworthy and reliable AI models, including data preparation, model development and validation, bias assessment and overall management and workflow
- Section 3 outlines the datasets used, their content and relevance to PD research
- Section 4 presents the genetic profiling techniques and methods, including the background and detailed analysis of various genetic datasets.
- Section 5 details the methodology and findings related to developing and evaluating a system for estimating the risk of PD
- Section 6 outlines the development and evaluation of two distinct approaches developed to predict PD progression
- Section 7 focuses on modelling the responses to PD medication, focusing on potential adverse effects
- Section 8 provides details on open science practices
- Section 9 describes the compliance with GDPR guidelines in retrospective data extraction and processing
- Section 10 summarises key findings, implications and future direction recommendations based on the conducted research

2 Trustworthy AI development

While developing predictive models for PD including progression, risk assessment, medication response, and genetic profiling, our focus remains on adhering to the key principles of Trustworthy AI. This ensures that all models are robust, fair, transparent, and clinically relevant, while maintaining high standards for data quality, privacy, and societal responsibility. This section aligns with the updated Trustworthy AI Development and Evaluation Framework (D2.6), which operationalizes principles from Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence, the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act, and other standards into concrete implementation steps. Trustworthy AI considerations were embedded throughout the modelling process, ensuring that the PD risk, progression, medication response, and genetic models collectively follow trustworthy AI practices.

2.1 Data Preparation

2.1.1 Data Quality

Each model underwent rigorous data quality assessments and preprocessing tailored to its domain, ensuring the reliability and integrity of the datasets used (**Table 1**).

Table 1 Overview of data quality assurance and preprocessing procedures across predictive models for PD.

Data Quality	
Genetic analysis	Samples and SNPs with call rates below 95%, minor allele frequency under 1%, or deviation from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium were excluded. Principal component and FastPop analyses were applied to control for ancestry-related confounding and population structure bias.
PD risk assessment model	Extensive exploratory data analysis and development of a custom validation tool to ensure schema compliance for clinical data. In addition, accelerometer data underwent segmentation, resampling to a uniform 25 Hz frequency, and exclusion of faulty segments potentially caused by sensor malfunctions or data gaps.
PD progression model	Multiple layers of cleaning were applied: merging of PPMI tables, encoding of categorical variables, and KNN imputation for continuous features. Sparsely populated variables were removed.
Medication response predictive model	Quality checks included visual inspection of feature distributions, removal of unrealistic or extreme values, exclusion of visits with missing or inconsistent outcome data, and correction of misspelled categorical entries using fuzzy string matching. Visits after the first occurrence of a side effect were excluded to avoid label leakage.
Outlier Detection and Data Sanitization	
Genetic analysis	Outlier and noise removal are handled, where low-quality or non-conforming SNPs were filtered based on standard GWAS quality thresholds. This process effectively served as a data sanitization step to ensure that only reliable variants were used in downstream analyses.
PD risk assessment model	Performed data distributions examinations and used z-score thresholds and empirical percentiles (e.g., 98th percentile) for accelerometer data.
PD progression model	Z-score thresholds were implemented. Also, LSTM autoencoder was used to identify and exclude outliers based on high reconstruction loss values.
Medication response predictive model	Values more than 4 standard deviations from feature means were treated as outliers and removed. Additional sanitization included exclusion of patients with fewer than two visits, those already showing side effects at baseline, and deep brain stimulation cases.

2.1.2 Data Privacy

All datasets were pre-anonymized or pseudonymised at the source (e.g., PPMI and AMP-PD repositories), and participant identities were safeguarded across models. This ensures privacy by removing any identifying information during data collection and analysis.

2.1.3 Management of Protected Variables

The key protected variables identified and validated by AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts, include:

Age: Evaluated across all models (risk, progression, medication response) because age strongly influences PD risk and severity and may affect model performance across age groups.

Biological sex: PD risk and phenotype differ between males and females; model performance was stratified by sex across all analyses.

Level of Education: Socioeconomic factors like education level can influence disease awareness and healthcare access. Assessed across the progression and medication-response models.

Race: Explicitly assessed in all fairness evaluations. It includes self-reported race categories (e.g., White, Black, Asian, Native American), which were used for subgroup analysis.

Ethnicity: Certain ethnic groups (e.g., Basque, Jewish populations) were evaluated in the PD risk model for potential bias.

BMI: was included as a sensitive variable in the PD risk model.

These attributes were systematically analyzed in the bias and fairness evaluations of the PD risk, progression, and medication response models to evaluate if a subgroup was disproportionately advantaged or disadvantaged.

2.2 Development & Internal Validation

2.2.1 Model Training and Generalization

Table 2 summarizes the training, validation, and generalization strategies adopted across the PD predictive models.

Table 2 Overview of model training and generalization strategies across predictive models for PD.

Genetic analysis	Logistic regression analysis under a log-additive model was applied to evaluate genetic associations that were found in previous studies.
PD risk assessment model	In the training process, Leave-One-Subject-Out cross-validation with nested hyperparameter optimization is performed. The model was evaluated on unseen participants and further validated on an at-risk cohort. Probability calibration was used to improve generalization reliability.
PD progression model	The baseline models used stratified 5-fold cross-validation with grouped folds (by patient ID) and applied SMOTE for class rebalancing. For PDualNet, cross-validation and external validation (PDBP) demonstrated robust generalization.
Medication response predictive model	Random Forest classifiers were trained using nested 10-fold cross-validation with stratification by subject ID to prevent leakage. Beta calibration converted predicted probabilities into well-calibrated risks. Cross-dataset and joint-dataset experiments (PPMI, PProBaND, NET-PD LS-1) were performed.

2.2.2 Performance Benchmarking

To assess predictive robustness and comparative validity, each model underwent performance benchmarking using internal metrics and, where applicable, external references (**Table 3**).

Table 3 Performance benchmarking metrics and evaluation approaches across PD predictive models.

Genetic analysis	Benchmarking was achieved by comparing the obtained odds ratios and p-values against results from established studies. This external comparison provided a reference for evaluating the performance and consistency of findings.
PD risk assessment model	Benchmarking was achieved through multiple quantitative metrics: balanced accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1-score, ROC-AUC, PR-AUC, Brier score, and Expected Calibration Error. Performance was also compared against the MDS prodromal PD risk score and SBR with correlation metrics. Test-retest reliability was evaluated with the intraclass correlation coefficient.
PD progression model	Models were compared using balanced accuracy, precision, and F1. PDualNet was statistically benchmarked against LSTM, TCN, and Random Forest baselines using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests ($p < 0.05$)
Medication response predictive model	Models were compared across datasets using balanced accuracy, AUROC, precision, sensitivity, specificity, and Expected Calibration Error

2.2.3 Bias Assessment and Fairness

Bias and fairness were assessed by evaluating model performance across a comprehensive set of sensitive variables. Subgroup analyses covered demographic and socioeconomic attributes including age, sex, race, BMI, ethnicity, and education level/years. These strata included detailed age bands (from <40 to 80+), BMI categories (underweight to obese), sex (male/female), extensive race categories (e.g., White, Asian, Black, American Indian/Alaska Native, Mixed, Other, Unknown), ethnicity (e.g., Ashkenazi Jewish, Hispanic/Latino, Not specified), and multiple education levels (ranging from <9th grade to graduate/professional degrees, and 0–20+ years of education). For every subgroup, we computed performance metrics and quantitative fairness indicators (Demographic Parity Difference/Ratio and Equalized Odds Difference/Ratio). This unified approach ensured that all PD predictive models were systematically evaluated for potential disparities across sensitive population segments.

2.2.4 Explainability and uncertainty benchmarking

Table 4 provides an overview of the explainability frameworks and uncertainty evaluation techniques integrated into each predictive model.

Table 4 Explainability methods and uncertainty benchmarking approaches across predictive models for PD.

PD risk assessment model	SHAP, LIME, and GINI importance were applied for global and local interpretability, while calibration curves quantified predictive uncertainty.
PD progression model	Applies Random Forests with built-in feature importance. SHAP values were calculated for PDualNet to reveal the most influential features per subtype.
Medication response predictive model	Performed SHAP-based explainability analyses to identify the most influential features per outcome.

2.3 Overarching management and workflow

2.3.1 Model and Dataset Reporting

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all AI-PROGNOSIS predictive models are documented following the TRIPOD-AI reporting standard and aligned with the MI-CLAIM framework. This deliverable formally adopts the TRIPOD-AI checklist as the reference structure for model reporting.

2.3.2 Security

All AI-PROGNOSIS model development and storage activities follow a common baseline of security practices to protect both data and models. Datasets and trained models are stored on encrypted institutional servers with strict role-based access control. Only authorized project members with approved credentials can retrieve or modify files. Network firewalls, multi-factor authentication, and regular backups further safeguard the modelling infrastructure from unauthorized access or tampering. Source code repositories are maintained in private, access-controlled environments.

2.3.3 Auditability and Accountability

All AI-PROGNOSIS models are developed under a transparent and auditable framework. Each modelling pipeline is version-controlled and logged to capture configuration changes and parameter updates. These logs enable traceability of every decision, from data inclusion to model output, supporting both internal and external audit processes. Model code,

configuration files, and experimental results are archived to enable full reproducibility and accountability in line with the TRIPOD-AI recommendations.

3 Dataset description

This section outlines the datasets accessed and used for the training and evaluating the three predictive models. A full list of the datasets accessed for the purposes of AI-PROGNOSIS is presented in the deliverable *D2.4 Updated report on domain review and datasets*. A list of the datasets and variables used particularly for the genetics analysis is outlined in Section 5 ‘Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis’.

3.1 Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI)

PPMI is a large multi-site observational clinical study running since 2010. It is designed to identify biomarkers of PD progression. The PPMI study is primarily funded by the Michael J Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research. The study is registered at clinicaltrials.gov under the identification number *NCT01141023*. It collects multisource (i.e., clinical, imaging, biospecimen and digital) data from PwPD, individuals at risk of developing PD, and healthy controls, rendering the collected data freely available upon reasonable request to research organisations. In total, the PPMI site collaborates with around 50 clinical sites from 12 countries to collect data and bio-samples. Ethical oversight is provided by the institutional review boards at each participating site, and participants provide informed consent for collecting and using their data. Further, the PPMI dataset includes data collected with the Verily study watch, captured between 2018 and 2020. The Verily study watch is a wearable device designed for clinical research, capable to continuously monitor digital health metrics. It captures – among others – various kinematic data, providing researchers with high quality, longitudinal insights into disease progression.

Therefore, PPMI served AI-PROGNOSIS as a critical source of data for developing models to:

- estimate the risk of developing PD,
- predict the progression of its symptoms and
- estimate the response to dopaminergic medication.

PPMI definitions and descriptions are available on the PPMI user guide⁸. In brief, the dataset includes the following cohorts (November 2023):

N	Cohort	Description
1227	People diagnosed with PD	Participants diagnosed with PD
1233	People with prodromal PD	Participants with REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) or Hyposmia or carrying particular genetic mutations such as GBA or LRRK2.
249	Healthy Controls	Age and sex-matched participants with no PD or any known risk factors to developing PD
3	Scans without dopaminergic deficit (SWEDD)	Participants were diagnosed with clinical PD symptoms but showed normal DaTscan images. This group is excluded from any analysis presented in this deliverable.

Participants underwent repeated assessments over around five years to track the progression of PD. Participants are clinically assessed every 6 months, whilst the first few visits are typically more frequent.

Variables

PPMI includes important data for developing predictive models, such as:

- Clinical assessments such as demographics, motor and non-motor symptoms.
- Imaging data such as magnetic resonance imaging, DaT-scan and Positron Emission Tomography (PET).
- Biospecimens such as blood samples for genetic and proteomic analysis, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) as well as urine and saliva samples.
- Continuous kinematic data captured over a 2-year period (2018-2020) under the Verily study.

PPMI database is continuously updated. The current report was based on data downloaded from the PPMI portal¹⁰ in November 2023. Importantly, data availability varies across participants and different cohorts.

The selection of the features used to train each of the three distinct models (PD risk, progression and response to medication) was based on three distinct sources, i.e.: a) an extensive state of the art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable *D2.4 Updated report on domain review and datasets*), b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (QMUL, FIN, CHUT, TUD), and c) PPMI data availability.

3.2 Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP)

The Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP), developed by the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS), aims to speed up the discovery of reliable diagnostic and progression biomarkers for PD. The program supports efforts in hypothesis testing, target and pathway discovery, biomarker development, and disease modelling, while broadly sharing data and biospecimens generated through its work.

The PDBP dataset is resource of longitudinally collected data and bio-samples from well-characterized PD and control participants. Currently, data from the PDBP cohort (1604 participants) can be categorized in the following categories:

- demographics,
- clinical scores (MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, etc.),
- whole genome sequencing (WGS),
- blood transcriptomics (RNA) and
- proteomics (plasma/CSF).

In brief, the dataset includes the following cohorts (October 2023):

N	Cohort	Description
892	PD participants	Participants diagnosed with PD (PD; Genetic Registry PD; Prodromal; and SWEDD)
555	Control participants	Participants (Genetic Registry Unaffected; Healthy Control; and Disease Control)

¹⁰ <https://ida.loni.usc.edu/login.jsp>

161	Other Diagnosis	e.g., Dementia, other Neurological Disorders, etc.
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Regarding demographics, 93.6% identify as White/Caucasian and 3.4% as Black/African-American. 55.6% are male, while age of participants varies between 20-90+.

Participants underwent repeated clinical assessments ranging from 1 (BL) to 11 (V10), at 6-month intervals. For the needs of the PDualNET progression modelling presented in Section 6, we selected 89 features that exist in both the PDBP and PPMI cohorts.

3.3 Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Parkinson's Disease (AMP-PD)

The Accelerating Medicines Partnership (AMP®) program is a public-private partnership between the National Institutes of Health (NIH), multiple biopharmaceutical and life sciences companies, and non-profit organisations with the mission to accelerate discovery and development of biomarkers and therapeutic targets for Parkinson's disease (PD).

AMP-PD repository (<https://amp-pd.org/>) integrates demographic, clinical, and other biological data from eight unified cohorts (~11,000 participants - BioFIND, HBS, LBD, LCC, PDBP, PPMI, STEADY-PD3 and SURE-PD3). All cohort data was/is collected in a consistent manner, using a longitudinal protocol schedule, allowing for data on patients to be collected over time.

This repository includes whole genome sequencing (WGS) data for most study participants.

3.4 The Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program Dataset

The Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP)¹¹ is an important research initiative dedicated to the identification and validation of biomarkers for PD and related disorders. Its ultimate aim is to facilitate the development of disease-modifying treatments.

The PDBP is a longitudinal study, requiring participants to visit study sites at least once per year for continued testing. This design is essential for tracking disease progression and identifying biomarkers that change over time.

The program has enrolled over 5,493 individuals. For researchers accessing the harmonized data through the AMP PD, the cohort includes 1,604 participant records that meet the AMP PD's minimum clinical data criteria.

- The program actively enrolls three distinct cohorts to enable comparative analysis:
- Individuals with PD.
- Individuals with Parkinsonism (Parkinson-like disorders), including conditions such as Lewy Body Dementia, Multiple System Atrophy, and Progressive Supranuclear Palsy.
- Control Subjects who do not have PD or any other neurological diagnosis.

During regular visits, comprehensive data is collected, including physical examinations, detailed paper and pencil tests (to evaluate memory, mood, and perception), and "scratch and sniff" tests (to assess the sense of smell). Furthermore, participants provide critical bio-samples, primarily blood and, in most cases, cerebrospinal fluid, which is extracted via a lumbar puncture procedure. These samples are vital for the biomarker discovery process.

¹¹ <https://pdbp.ninds.nih.gov/>

3.5 Critical Path for Parkinson's integrated Parkinson's database

Description

In addition to the PPMI, we also employed the Critical Path for Parkinson's (CPP) integrated Parkinson's database¹² for the medication predictive modelling of the Section 7. This integrated database contains diverse clinical trials and observational studies, including a subset of the previously discussed PPMI dataset. These datasets each vary in number of subjects, inclusion criteria, PD stages, age, medication, etc. In total, the Integrated Database contains data of over 12000 subjects from 22 studies. The ultimate aim is to integrate as many of these datasets as possible in the model design, ensuring broad applicability and generalizability. In addition, the variety of sociodemographic and socioeconomic groups included in these datasets reduces the risk of bias and unfairness. Proper clearance for access to the CPP dataset was requested and granted by the CPP according to the outlined terms and conditions¹³.

Variables

The CPP dataset contains a large number of variables, but not all of them are present in every dataset. These variables broadly fall into the following categories:

- Adverse events
- Medical history of associated persons
- Clinical events with diagnostic value (e.g. bradykinesia, tremors, rigidity, gait disturbances, etc.), dopaminergic events (dyskinesia's, dystonia's, freezing, etc.).
- Concomitant medication and their levodopa equivalent dosage, dosage, dosage frequency etc.
- Demographic features: age, sex, race, ethnicity.
- Functional tests: MoCa, Semantic fluency, neurological testing, SCOPA-COG.
- Laboratory results: Blood haematology, urinalysis, etc.
- Medical history
- Nervous system findings
- Physical examinations
- Pharmacogenomics: SNPs for multiple genes of interest (e.g., COMT, GBA, LRRK2)
- Questionnaires: (MDS-)UPDRS, Hoehn and Yahr stage, etc.
- Substance usage: alcohol, caffeine, smoking, etc.
- Vital signs: Heart rate, blood pressure, height, weight, etc.

4 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis

4.1 Background and Objectives

PD is a neurodegenerative disorder with complex aetiopathogenesis, as previous studies suggest that genetic and lifestyle/environmental factors synergistically act, especially in idiopathic PD (iPD) cases (Chairta P et al. 2021; Kline E.M et al. 2021). Although numerous genetic studies have been conducted on PD over the years, identifying several genetic variants associated with the disease, GWAS, meta-analyses, and Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) studies continue to reveal new associations (Sia M.W et al. 2021; Kim J.J et al. 2024). Understanding the genetic basis of PD risk is crucial to facilitate early prognosis, accurate diagnosis of the disease, and development of targeted therapies.

¹² <https://c-path.org/tools-platforms/integrated-parkinsons-database/>

¹³ <https://codr.c-path.org/main/applyDatabaseSelection.html>

This task of the AI-PROGNOSIS project aims to extract genetic data from different datasets, perform association analysis and calculate PRS associated with the risk of developing PD and its progression, which can be effectively used as inputs to the relevant AI prognostic models.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Genetic Datasets

Data from the AMP-PD repository were extracted and analysed. The content of the identified datasets is outlined below.

AMP-PD dataset and population stratification

AMP-PD dataset is presented in detail in Section 3: Accelerating Medicines Partnership for Parkinson's Disease (AMP-PD). For PD risk analyses, comparisons were performed between PD cases and healthy (unaffected) controls (HC).

For PD progression analysis, only PD cases were used. The patients were selected using the inclusion criteria¹⁴ stated in the AI-PMP protocol. Comparisons were performed for the following definitions of yearly PD progression:

- MDS-UPDRS part III > 3 points (Primary)
- At least 1 point in any of the MDS-UPDRS part IV items (4.1, 4.2, 4.3, or 4.4) OR at least 1 point in the MDS-UPDRS item 1.1 or MDS-UPDRS item 1.2 or MDS-UPDRS item 2.13 or MDS-UPDRS item 2.2 (Secondary) and
- MDS-UPDRS part III > 5 points (Exploratory)

Additional comparisons were also carried out using yearly progression clusters identified in the PPMI dataset as part of the PD progression modelling (Section 6.3.2.1). Clustering was performed using both baseline clinical scores and their yearly change (delta) of PwPD (Section 6.3.2.1). Patients were divided into two groups: Group 1, which consisted of cases with only clinical data, and Group 2, which consisted of cases with both clinical and wearable data (Verily Study Watch cohort). Then, patients within each group were categorised based on the clusters (Cluster 1 or Cluster 2).

4.2.2 Genetic analysis

Quality check

Quality check analysis of the SNPs and samples of the AMP-PD repository was performed as described in Section 2. This analysis was carried out in Plink 2.0.

Ancestry Identification

FastPop analysis¹⁵ was performed to identify ancestry in the AMP-PD dataset, and proportions for each ancestry/sample were estimated. This tool calculates the distance metrics among three continental ethnicity definitions (CEU/European, CHB/Asian, and YRI/African). This analysis was carried out in R version 4.3.2.

Polygenic risk score (PRS)

PRS calculation was performed to assess PD risk and progression. The PRSs were calculated for each study participant using the following formula: $PRS = \beta_1x_1 + \dots + \beta_kx_k$, where β_k is

¹⁴ Patients in ON medication state during clinical assessment (PDSTATE = 1); Age range: 40-80 years; Hoehn & Yahr (NHY) stages: 2 or 3; Disease duration between 5 and 10 years

¹⁵ FastPop analysis is a method used in population genetics for rapidly inferring intercontinental ancestry from genetic data.

the log OR of the minor allele for SNP_k obtained from previously published studies; and x_k is the number of minor allele copies that are carried by each individual for SNP_k and can take values 0, 1 or 2 (minor allele was defined based on the published minor allele frequency (MAF)), as previously described by Mavaddat N et al. (2019). All calculations were carried out in R version 4.3.2.

Three different PRS models were composed using the SNPs included in the most commonly used PRS studies. PRS for PD risk was calculated using the SNPs reported by Nalls M.A et al. (2019) and Leonard H.L et al. (2025). PRS for PD progression was calculated using the SNPs reported by Paul K.C et al. (2018), Nalls M.A et al. (2019) and Leonard H.L et al. (2025).

PRS based on Nalls M.A et al., (2019) study

PRS calculation was performed using 69 out of 90 SNPs reported in Nalls M.A et al., (2019). Two variants located in the *LRRK2* gene (rs76904798 & rs34637584) were removed from the PRS calculation as recommended by the Nalls M.A et al. study. Ten ambiguous, seven multi-allelic and two non-informative variants were also removed; thus, the remaining 69 SNPs were used for the PRS calculation.

PRS based on Leonard H.L et al. (2025) study

PRS was calculated using 118 out of the 157 SNPs reported in Leonard H.L et al. (2025), as ambiguous, multiallelic and variants located in the *LRRK2* gene (rs17443099, rs76904798, rs35303786, rs34637584) were excluded.

PRS based on Paul K.C et al. (2018) study

Twenty out of the 23 SNPs reported in Paul K.C et al. (2018) were used for PRS calculation, as ambiguous, multiallelic and variants located in the *GBA* gene were excluded.

Statistical analysis to assess SNPs and PRS association

Logistic regression under the log-additive model was used to evaluate all novel SNPs reported in Leonard H.L et al. (2025) and investigate possible associations between these SNPs and PD regarding disease risk, using the AMP-PD repository.

Logistic regression analysis was also applied to assess the relationship between the PRS and PD status (risk and progression).

All analyses were carried out in R version 4.3.2.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Genetic analysis and PRS

Proportions for each ancestry/sample were estimated through FastPop analysis, and it is noted that most AMP-PD participants are of European ancestry (**Figure 1, Table 5**).

Figure 1 FastPop analysis of AMP-PD participants. Light blue dots indicate the 70% discovery samples from TRICL, UK, and Hapmap samples. Blue, pink and green dots indicate YRI (African), CEU (European) and CHB (Asian) populations, respectively. Light pink colour indicates the AMP-PD population.

Table 5 FastPop analysis of AMP-PD participants (% of ancestry) Table shows examples of proportions for each ancestry/ sample.

	PC1	PC2	CEU (European)	YRI (African)	CHB (Asia)
BF-1008	5.153	-1.276	100%	0%	0%
BF-1009	4.949	-1.755	100%	0%	0%
BF-1021	4.415	-0.611	100%	0%	0%
BF-1025	4.722	-0.711	100%	0%	0%
BF-1048	5.015	-1.311	100%	0%	0%
BF-1062	4.770	-0.594	100%	0%	0%
BF-1065	4.623	-2.218	100%	0%	0%
BF-1090	4.561	-0.709	100%	0%	0%
BF-1092	5.240	-1.807	100%	0%	0%
BF-1106	4.511	-0.787	100%	0%	0%
BF-1121	4.562	-2.268	100%	0%	0%
BF-1123	4.471	-0.617	100%	0%	0%
BF-1129	5.476	-1.722	100%	0%	0%
BF-1130	5.247	-0.412	100%	0%	0%
BF-1136	5.737	-2.616	100%	0%	0%
BF-1174	5.154	-1.488	100%	0%	0%
BF-1177	5.301	-0.689	100%	0%	0%
BF-1181	5.864	-0.725	100%	0%	0%
BF-1201	4.554	-1.663	100%	0%	0%
BF-1224	5.617	-1.878	100%	0%	0%
BF-1230	4.582	-1.067	100%	0%	0%
BF-1245	4.732	-1.057	100%	0%	0%
HB-PD_INVAA223GY7	4.760	-1.575	100%	0%	0%

HB-PD_INVAB109VHC	6.144	-2.763	100%	0%	0%
HB-PD_INVAB289LG3	4.805	-0.936	100%	0%	0%

Association analysis

The 157¹⁶ SNPs that are reported in Leonard H.L et al. (2025) were extracted from the AMP-PD repository, and association analysis was performed between PD cases and HCs (**Table 6**). Similar OR results were observed in both populations. However, p-values are weaker in our analysis using the AMP-PD data compared to the GP2 study (Leonard H.L et al., 2025) due to the smaller sample size.

Table 6 Statistically significant SNPs associated with PD under logistic regression analysis in AMP-PD (Patients with PD Versus HC). OR: Odds ratio.

rsID	Nearest Gene	Ref. allele	Effect allele	GP2		AMP-PD	
				OR	p-value	OR	p-value
rs12128848	KCND3	A	G	0.9	3.15E-08	0.93	0.05
rs76763715	GBA1	T	C	2.31	7.61E-35	0.79	0.01
rs2230288	GBA1	C	T	1.58	1.05E-78	2.33	0.00
rs61802091	SDHC	G	A	0.94	1.10E-10	0.88	0.01
rs3049686	VAMP4	T	TAGAG	0.95	1.47E-09	0.91	0.00
rs708723	RAB29	C	T	1.08	1.50E-28	1.11	0.00
rs10495249	ITPKB	A	G	0.94	1.40E-14	0.88	0.00
rs13010404	TTC27	T	G	0.95	5.29E-12	0.93	0.04
rs6758044	ACMSD	T	C	0.90	1.25E-44	0.79	0.00
rs3754541	ACVR2A	G	A	0.95	9.11E-10	-	-
rs10173157	ACVR1	A	G	0.95	8.14E-09	0.89	0.01
rs12618884	STK39	A	G	1.04	4.67E-09	1.09	0.01
rs2102808	STK39	G	T	1.16	4.76E-52	1.13	0.01
rs73034368	TBC1D5	C	A	1.14	5.37E-15	1.26	0.01
rs1461806	RBMS3	A	G	0.95	4.17E-13	0.91	0.01
rs34822404	MCCC1	C	T	0.89	2.13E-41	0.92	0.04
rs34884217	TMEM175	A	C	0.88	4.07E-27	0.86	0.00
rs34311866	TMEM175	T	C	1.18	2.84E-85	1.20	0.00
rs4698412	BST1	G	A	1.07	1.24E-26	1.13	0.00
rs59912548	LCORL	ATC	A	0.91	1.44E-17	0.88	0.00
rs28628748	FAM47E-STBD1	G	A	0.93	2.64E-24	0.90	0.00

¹⁶ 14 out of 157 SNPs overlap with SNPs reported in Nalls M.A et al. (2019)

				GP2		AMP-PD	
rsID	Nearest Gene	Ref. allele	Effect allele	OR	p-value	OR	p-value
rs356182	SNCA	G	A	0.83	7.47E-158	0.74	<2E-16
rs72696649	CLCN3	T	A	0.95	3.94E-13	-	-
rs246814	SV2C	C	T	1.09	4.21E-12	1.16	0.01
rs60740436	MBOAT1	TA	T	1.04	1.49E-08	1.07	0.03
rs6461688	KLHL7	G	A	0.93	8.19E-29	0.89	0.00
rs34504234	CTSB	CT	C	0.93	4.49E-21	0.92	0.02
rs4872005	BIN3	G	C	0.96	7.86E-09	-	-
rs6469273	SYBU	C	G	1.05	8.18E-11	-	-
rs8181077	SH3GL2	A	T	0.93	3.21E-25	-	-
rs1536072	SH3GL2	C	G	1.08	5.76E-25	-	-
rs13296299	UBAP1	T	A	1.05	7.10E-12	-	-
rs144814361	BAG3	C	T	1.38	1.68E-31	1.60	0.00
rs12284617	DLG2	A	G	0.96	1.07E-09	0.90	0.00
rs17443099	LRRK2	G	A	1.31	3.86E-21	1.24	0.00
rs34637584	LRRK2	G	A	9.10	5.89E-89	1.50	0.00
rs7350560	ABTB3	A	G	1.05	1.78E-08	1.11	0.01
rs10847864	HIP1R	G	T	1.11	4.25E-40	1.10	0.01
rs1198499	CAB39L	T	C	1.05	4.48E-12	0.93	0.03
rs1995052	MBNL2	T	C	0.96	1.03E-08	0.91	0.01
rs4774417	VPS13C	G	A	1.08	5.48E-22	1.18	0.00
rs732172	STX4	C	T	0.92	3.22E-36	0.88	0.00
rs222852	PHF23	A	G	0.96	1.93E-09	1.09	0.01
rs2078050	NCOR1	C	T	0.96	5.27E-11	0.92	0.02
rs11080149	OMG	C	T	1.07	1.61E-10	1.15	0.01
rs190825568	NPEPPS	G	A	0.94	3.50E-08	0.89	0.02
rs58426209	SLC16A6	T	G	0.94	5.85E-11	0.91	0.02
rs143392722	DNAH17	TTTAT C	T	0.94	4.17E-09	-	-
rs8074498	ASPSCR1	T	A	1.04	4.62E-09	-	-
rs2076574176	NOL4	GA	G	1.07	2.93E-10	-	-
rs12456492	RIT2	A	G	1.07	3.11E-22	1.16	0.00
rs55785911	LZTS3	G	A	0.96	2.09E-09	0.89	0.00

rsID	Nearest Gene	Ref. allele	Effect allele	GP2		AMP-PD	
				OR	p-value	OR	p-value
rs11701836	DYRK1A	A	G	1.07	2.25E-17	1.10	0.01
rs4816690	DSCAM	T	C	1.04	2.59E-08	1.08	0.02
rs118075805	TRPM2	G	T	1.22	4.03E-09	1.51	0.01

PD risk PRS

The two different statistical analyses of the PRS calculated based on Nalls M.A. et al., (2019) that were performed between PD cases and HCs using (1) all samples and (2) only European ancestry samples showed clear discrimination between the two groups ($p= 9.65 \times 10^{-71}$; $OR=2.00$, $p= 8.63 \times 10^{-69}$; $OR=2.01$), respectively (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 PRS distribution between PD cases and HC. This plot shows the density versus PRS in cases and controls.

Logistic regression analysis between PD cases and HCs revealed that the 118 SNPs-PRS (Leonard H.L et al. (2025)), is significantly associated with PD ($p=3.46 \times 10^{-65}$; $OR=2.13$) (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3 PRS distribution between PD cases and HC. This plot shows the density versus PRS in cases and HC.

PD progression PRS

Statistical analysis performed using the PRS calculated based on the SNPs reported in Paul K.C et al. (2018) in combination with the primary, secondary and exploratory progression definitions, defined in the AI-PMP study protocol showed that none of analyses gave statistically significant results: [MDS-UPDRS Part III total score change > vs. ≤ 5 points (p=0.262; OR=1.86), MDS-UPDRS Part III total score change > vs. ≤ 3 points (p=0.601; OR=1.31), MDS-UPDRS Part I & II items (p-value=0.55; OR=1.73), MDS-UPDRS part IV items (p-value=0.54; OR=0.53) (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 PRS (based on Paul KC et al. (2018)) distribution between PD cases with different UPDRS differences. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in PD cases using the primary (A), secondary (B-C) and (D) exploratory criteria.

The same analyses were also performed using the calculated PRS based on Nalls MA et al. (2019) to explore potential association between the PD risk PRS and the progression categories. Again, none of these analyses were significant: MDS-UPDRS Part III total score change > vs. ≤ 3 points (p=0.201; OR=2.34), MDS-UPDRS Part I & II items (p-value=0.964; OR=1.02); MDS-UPDRS Part IV items (p-value=0.157; OR=0.33), and MDS-UPDRS Part III total score change > vs. ≤ 5 points (p=0.161; OR=1.78) (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 PRS (based on Nalls MA et al. (2019)) distribution between PD cases with different UPDRS differences. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in PD cases using the primary (A), secondary (B-C) and (D) exploratory criteria.

PD progression PRS analysis was also performed using the progression clusters identified in the PPMI study (see Section 6.2.3.1). Using both the PRS calculated based on the Paul K.C et al. (2018) study and the PRS calculated based on the Leonard H.L et al. (2025) study, no significant associations were observed (**Table 7** and **Table 8**).

Table 7 PD progression PRS analysis based on Paul K.C et al. (2018) per PPMI participant group, progression cluster and types of clinical features (baseline, delta) used for clustering. OR: Odds ratio; CI: confidence interval.

		Group1	Group2	Group1&2
Both baseline and delta features		Cluster 1 vs 2	Cluster 1 vs 2	Cluster 1 vs 2
	p-value	0.67	0.80	0.65
	OR (CI 95%)	1.13 (0.63-2.04)	1.20 (0.29- 5.03)	1.13 (0.67-1.93)

Table 8 PD progression PRS analysis based on Leonard H.L et al. (2025). per PPMI participant group, progression cluster and types of clinical features (baseline, delta) used for clustering. OR: Odds ratio; CI: confidence interval.

		Group1	Group2	Group1&2
Both baseline and delta features		Cluster 1 vs 2	Cluster 1 vs 2	Cluster 1 vs 2
	p-value	0.80	0.22	0.45
	OR (CI 95%)	1.06 (0.67-1.69)	1.86 (0.71-5.21)	1.17 (0.77-1.77)

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Interpretation

The genetic analyses indicate that the AMP-PD dataset provides a solid foundation for studying PD genetics, largely because of its size and the relative homogeneity of its predominantly European ancestry population. This consistency in ancestry reduces confounding and increases confidence in the observed genetic patterns.

The PD PRS behaved as expected: both established SNP sets were able to distinguish PD cases from healthy controls, reinforcing the robustness of previously reported risk loci. The slightly stronger effect observed when using the more recent SNP set suggests that updated genetic discoveries may be capturing additional or more relevant risk-related variation. The fact that the odds ratios in AMP-PD closely mirrored those reported in the original study further supports the reproducibility of these risk associations across independent cohorts.

In contrast, the PRS analyses related to PD progression did not reveal meaningful associations. Regardless of which SNP set was used or which clinical or data-driven progression definition was applied, the genetic scores failed to differentiate between faster and slower progressors. This lack of signal suggests that current progression-related SNP panels may not generalize well across cohorts, or that progression is influenced by factors not adequately captured by existing genetic models. The variability in how progression is defined across studies, combined with relatively small sample sizes within each progression category, likely further diluted the ability to detect subtle genetic effects.

Overall, the findings reinforce the reliability of PRS for PD risk but highlight the current limitations of PRS for PD progression, indicating the need for larger, harmonized datasets and more refined genetic markers to capture the complexity of disease evolution.

4.4.2 Beyond SoA

This section highlights how the current genetic analyses advance beyond existing work by incorporating new data sources and newly published genetic findings. The analyses extend the state of the art in three main ways: refining the ancestral context of the AMP-PD cohort, integrating newly reported PD-associated variants for the first time in this project, and evaluating both risk- and progression-related PRS within a harmonized framework.

Ancestry context

The ancestry evaluation confirmed that the AMP-PD dataset—spanning eight cohorts—consists predominantly of individuals of European descent. This homogeneity provides a stable genetic background for downstream analyses and reduces confounding when comparing risk and progression models.

Integration of newly reported PD-associated SNPs

A key advancement in this phase of the project is the incorporation of SNPs recently identified in the 2025 study by Leonard et al. These variants have not been previously used in our analyses and represent an updated view of PD genetic architecture. Their inclusion allowed us to test whether the newly discovered loci replicate in an independent dataset and whether they enhance the predictive performance of PD risk models. The fact that these SNPs

produced effect sizes in AMP-PD that closely mirrored those reported in the original publication suggests that the new loci are robust and transferable across cohorts. This strengthens confidence in their biological relevance and supports their integration into future PRS frameworks.

PRS for PD risk and progression

Using both established and newly published SNP sets, we generated updated PRSs for PD risk and evaluated their performance in the AMP-PD cohort. The new PRS based on the 2025 SNPs showed slightly stronger case–control discrimination, indicating that recent genetic discoveries may capture additional risk-related variation not present in earlier models.

4.4.3 Limitations

The primary limitation of this genetic analysis is the limited access to genetic data. Access to NS-PARK was not possible and access to the UK Biobank, the largest repository planned for inclusion in this study, was delayed. The power of this study is reduced because the number of samples available was smaller than expected. In addition, the UK Biobank can only be used for PD risk analysis, but not for PD progression and medication response analyses, as it does not include the necessary clinical and medication response data. The situation for the AMP-PD repository data was similar, as some important information about the drug dosage (e.g., Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD)) is missing, which prevents the classification of patients based on the medication response predictive modelling criteria and required input.

5 Development and evaluation of a model to estimate PD risk

5.1 Background and objectives

5.1.1 Background

PD is often misdiagnosed, particularly at the early stages, as early symptoms are subtle and can be similar to other diseases' manifestations. Early diagnosis enables adequate patient counselling, care plan, timely management of symptoms, and inclusion of patients in studies with potentially disease-modifying drugs¹⁷. It is also crucial for initiating timely symptomatic therapies and, eventually when available, targeted interventions to slow disease progression and improve patient outcomes. To date, scores to estimate PD risk are often limited to specific prodromal PD phase criteria (Berg et al., 2015). In our extensive review of the state of the art (*D2.4 Updated report on domain review and datasets*), we demonstrate that most available models rely on single-modality assessments such as genetic predispositions, demographic factors, or conventional clinical approaches. Clinical examination tools, although useful, are imperfect in the sense that they may fail to capture the complex nature of the disease risk (FitzGerald et al., 2018). ML/AI approaches offer the potential to address these limitations by handling large multi-dimensional and multi-modal datasets that include genomic, clinical, demographic, imaging, and kinematic data to achieve a more robust and personalised risk prediction. In this context, smartwatch-based movement and sleep metrics have been shown to correlate with clinical prodromal PD findings such as reduction in presynaptic dopamine binding capacity (measured via DaTscan) and α -synuclein SAA positivity, demonstrating higher sensitivity compared to traditional MDS criteria (Schalkamp et al., 2025). Key points in PD risk calculation include:

¹⁷ <https://www.lse.ac.uk/business/consulting/assets/documents/the-value-of-early-diagnosis-and-treatment-in-parkinsons-disease.pdf>

- **Sociodemographic factors** play an important role in calculating PD risk. Baseline characteristics such as gender not only constitute potential disease predictors (Pereira et al., 2024), but can also affect access to healthcare resources and, effectively, the timeliness of diagnosis.
- **Wearable sensor (kinematic) data** have become popular in objectively quantifying PD motor and physical activity status that have recently emerged as significant predictors of PD risk (Schalkamp et al., 2023, 2025). Sleep disturbance is a common symptom in PD (Menza et al., 2010) and can be captured by wearable devices. Similarly, physical activity, such as walking, reduces the risk of developing PD (Fang et al., 2018) and cadence, among other gait parameters, characteristically increases in individuals with PD (Zanardi et al., 2021).

5.1.2 Objectives

The aim of this pillar of AI-PROGNOSIS was to develop a PD screening system that integrates unobtrusively collected digital measurements and establishes clinical and lifestyle-based PD risk and prodromal markers easily obtainable through questionnaires.

Based on currently available datasets, the objectives during this second phase of the project were to:

- 1) Develop a ML model that uses digital measurements of sleep and activity, with age, sex, weight, and height as covariates, to classify PwPD and healthy controls, defining the output probability as a sleep and activity metrics-based PD risk score (SAM-PD risk score).
- 2) Evaluate the test-retest reliability of the SAM-PD risk score and of the model's input features of sleep and activity, as well as the model's explainability and fairness in terms of sensitive variables.
- 3) Compare the SAM-PD risk score from our model against the current MDS prodromal PD risk assessment model (MDS risk score), in terms of detecting dopaminergic deficit (reduction in Specific Binding Ratio (SBR) dopamine transporter SPECT) and α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity, two hallmarks of PD, in an at-risk cohort.
- 4) Combine the SAM-PD risk score with the MDS risk score and investigate the performance in detecting dopaminergic deficit (reduction in Specific Binding Ratio (SBR) dopamine transporter SPECT) and α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity in the at-risk cohort.

5.1.3 Implementation

The following approach was implemented:

SAM-PD Risk score model training: on the wearable measurements of sleep, mobility, and slowness of movement derived from the Verily Study Watch PD and HC groups (subset of PPMI), including age, sex, height, and weight as covariates.

SAM-PD Risk score model explainability: feature importances, were calculated using: a) SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP), b) Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME), and c) GINI importances to ensure transparency and clinical interpretability of results.

SAM-PD Risk score model validation: The SAM-PD risk score was correlated against: a) the score produced by the MDS prodromal PD risk model (Heinzel et al., 2019) in an at-risk population, b) the dopaminergic nigrostriatal deficiency, as measured by SBR using DaTscan, in PwPD, healthy controls and at-risk c) the presence of α -Synuclein Seed Amplification Assay positivity or dopaminergic deficiency, d) evaluation of the model's performance in an at-risk cohort.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Dataset description

All data utilised in this analysis was sourced from the PPMI and the Verily study watch datasets. For a detailed description of the PPMI dataset refer to the section 3.1 of this document. Our analysis incorporated data from the Verily sub-study of PPMI, during which the Verily Study Watch was utilized to collect data from a total of 325 participants. Participants were monitored using the Verily Study Watch for an average duration of 434 (\pm 205) days. During data collection, signals were captured using the smartwatch-embedded sensors, i.e., accelerometer, gyroscope, photoplethysmography, ambient temperature, ambient pressure, electrodermal activity, and humidity sensors. In this study, accelerometer data were only utilised, as it is the most common wearable sensor.

To implement the MDS prodromal risk calculator, we sourced PD risk and prodromal markers according to the MDS task force criteria (Berg et al., 2015; Heinzel et al., 2019) from the general PPMI dataset, and the FOUND and ONLINE sub-studies.

Three cohorts are considered in this analysis as labelled by the PPMI:

1. Parkinson's disease
2. Healthy controls
3. Prodromal PD which are participants at-risk for developing PD.

Any at-risk participants that have been identified by the PPMI consensus committee to have been diagnosed with PD were excluded (N=9). For the purposes of PD risk estimation specific criteria were set for the participants to be eligible to enter the analysis pipeline. These are outlined below:

1. Participants are either diagnosed with PD or prodromal PD or are healthy controls
2. Participants are included in the Verily watch study subset.

All available data, meeting the above inclusion criteria were used for developing and validating the PD risk model (see Section 5.3.1 for details). Hence, no sample size calculation was performed for the purpose of this model development.

5.2.2 Data processing

Sleep and activity metrics

An overview of the high-level data processing pipeline is depicted in **Figure 6**. Free-living, raw accelerometer data collected using the Verily Study Watch, were retrieved from the PPMI database for subsequent analytical processing. To ensure data quality and standardization, an initial signal processing step was applied to segment the raw accelerometer signals into consecutive bins of data without missing segments due to sensor malfunctions, battery depletion, or other errors. These subsequences were then resampled to a uniform frequency of 25Hz, a typical sampling rate of off-the-shelf smartwatches, to enable consistent downstream analyses. After pre-processing, the signals were recombined so that each analytical component could process the data in a standardized manner.

Figure 6 Aggregated feature vector generation pipeline. Raw accelerometer signals, collected from a wrist-worn device in a free-living environment, underwent preprocessing before being used to derive three primary categories of features: sleep, slowness of movement, physical activity.

From the pre-processed signals, we derived three primary categories of digital features, related to sleep, slowness of movement, and physical activity. Each metric category was chosen to capture complementary aspects of daily behavior and motor function that are highly relevant for PD. Open-source algorithms with custom analytical pipelines, were used to ensure methodological robustness and reproducibility throughout the process. Sleep and physical activity features were computed using the `asleep`¹⁸ and `stepcount`¹⁹ algorithms from OxWearables, respectively. Slowness of movement features were derived from raw accelerometer data segmented into consecutive five-second windows, where hand movement segments were identified while excluding gait periods to focus on upper-limb motor activity.

The definitions and temporal resolutions of all extracted features are provided in **Table 9**.

Table 9 Description of the features extracted from the Verily Study Watch raw accelerometer data for the SAM-PD risk model development.

Metric Category	Feature Name	Description	Interval
Sleep	Total Sleep Duration	Duration of total sleep measured in hours.	Day
	Sleep Onset Latency	Time interval between going to bed and the onset of sleep.	Day
	Wake After Sleep Onset	Total wake time occurring after initial sleep onset.	Day
	Sleep Efficiency	Ratio of total sleep time to the total time spent in bed.	Day
	REM Latency	Time interval from sleep onset to the initiation of REM sleep.	Day
	Wake Duration	Total cumulative wake duration during the sleep period.	Day

¹⁸ <https://github.com/OxWearables/asleep>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/OxWearables/stepcount>

	N1 Sleep Duration	Duration of stage N1 (light) sleep.	Day
	N2 Sleep Duration	Duration of stage N2 sleep.	Day
	N3 Sleep Duration	Duration of stage N3 (deep) sleep.	Day
	NREM Duration	Total duration of all Non-REM (NREM) sleep stages combined.	Day
	REM Duration (Minutes)	Total duration of REM sleep measured in minutes.	Day
Slowness of Movement	RMS Magnitude Median	Median root mean square of movement magnitude.	Day
	Smoothness Magnitude Median	Median smoothness of movement magnitude.	Day
	Peak Acceleration Magnitude Median	Median peak acceleration of movement.	Day
	Range of Motion Magnitude Median	Median range of motion.	Day
	Signal Entropy Magnitude Median	Median signal entropy of movement.	Day
	RMS Magnitude 75th Percentile	75th percentile RMS magnitude.	Day
	Smoothness Magnitude 75th Percentile	75th percentile smoothness magnitude.	Day
	Peak Acceleration Magnitude 75th Percentile	75th percentile peak acceleration.	Day
	Range of Motion Magnitude 75th Percentile	75th percentile range of motion.	Day
	Signal Entropy Magnitude 75th Percentile	75th percentile signal entropy.	Day
	RMS Magnitude Standard Deviation	Standard deviation of RMS magnitude.	Day

	Smoothness Magnitude Standard Deviation	Standard deviation of smoothness magnitude.	Day
	Peak Acceleration Magnitude Standard Deviation	Standard deviation of peak acceleration.	Day
	Range of Motion Magnitude Standard Deviation	Standard deviation of range of motion.	Day
	Signal Entropy Magnitude Standard Deviation	Standard deviation of signal entropy.	Day
Physical Activity	Hourly Steps	Aggregated hourly step count, indicating overall daily activity.	Hour
	Hourly ENMO (mg)	Hourly Euclidean Norm Minus One (ENMO) value representing activity intensity.	Hour
	Steps Cadence	Steps per minute during active walking.	Minute
	Cadence 25th Percentile	25th percentile of cadence distribution measured in steps per minute.	Minute
	Cadence 75th Percentile	75th percentile of cadence distribution measured in steps per minute.	Minute

Time aggregation

The three metric categories are measured in different time resolutions. Sleep metrics and slowness of movement metrics are measured per day, while physical activity metrics are recorded at either hourly or minute-level resolution. To create a representation (feature vector) of a subject at given time interval, time aggregation was necessary. For this reason, time series-derived features were automatically extracted using the tsfresh²⁰ Python package. For each metric presented in **Table 9**, tsfresh was used to extract descriptive features from the corresponding time series. The median and mean were used to summarise central tendency, with the median providing a robust measure unaffected by outliers and the mean representing the average over the observation period. Measures of variability (standard deviation and variance) and distribution (25th and 75th percentiles) were used to characterise stability, fluctuation, and data spread.

²⁰ <https://tsfresh.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

MDS risk model input and variations

To determine the risk score of the MDS PD risk model for everyone in the at-risk cohort, we extracted the prodromal markers (Berg et al., 2015; Heinzl et al., 2019) from the PPMI, PPMI-FOUND, and PPMI-ONLINE datasets. All risk markers were available (**Table 10**), except DaTscans (used as input to the models). Any variable collected later than the commencement of the Verily study was also excluded, except caffeine consumption and occupational pesticide exposure, as these are considered historical information.

We searched records of diagnoses in the Medical Conditions Log using regular expressions and marked pre-study diagnoses related to the MDS task force criteria as positive. Further, MDS-UPDRS scores of each visit, before the initiation of the Verily study, were evaluated and items exceeding predetermined thresholds were included. For PSG proven RBD, only the positive cases were considered, and missing information was marked as null.

PRS was also calculated and included as risk marker in the model. For details on PRS calculation refer to Section 5 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis.

Variables unavailable for a participant were marked as null. No further handling of missing values was performed as the model is capable to treat missing values by ignoring them.

Table 10 MDS PD risk and prodromal markers and PPMI source.

Variable	Source	Details
Age	PPMI	Mean age during the Verily Study
Biological sex	PPMI	-
Never smoked	FOUND	Answered No to the “Have you ever smoked regularly?”
Current smoker	FOUND	Answered Yes to the “Are you a current smoker question”
Former smoker	FOUND	Answered Yes to the “Have you ever smoked regularly?” and No to “Are you a current smoker question”
Caffeine consumption	FOUND, ONLINE	Answered Yes to the “Have you ever drank caffeinated coffee regularly?”
Occupational Pesticide exposure	FOUND, ONLINE	Answered Yes if they had a job that exposed them to pesticides
Polygenic risk score	CING	High or Low percentile of AMP-PD PRS
GBA Present	PPMI	From Participant Status
LRRK2 Present	PPMI	From Participant Status
1 st degree relative diagnosed with PD	PPMI	From Family History
Diabetes mellitus (Type II)	PPMI	Medication Log Records containing 'diabetes' (case insensitive) AND ('I' OR '2' OR 'mellitus'), excluding entries with 'pre' or 'border'
Polysomnography-confirmed REM sleep disorder	PPMI	In RBD prodromal sub-cohort
RBD screening questionnaire	PPMI	RBDSQ > 5

Subthreshold Parkinsonism	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part III > 6 excluding postural and kinetic tremor item
Hyposmia	PPMI	From Participant Status
Constipation	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I & Medication log Records containing 'Constipation'
Daytime somnolence	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I & Medication log Records containing 'Sleepiness'
Neurogenic orthostatic hypotension	PPMI	Based on the ration of increased HR over drop of Systolic BP (Beach and McKay,2024) ²¹
Symptomatic orthostatic hypotension	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I & Medical Log Records containing 'headed OR hypotension'
Erectile dysfunction	PPMI	From SCOPA-AUT & Medication log Record of males containing '[Ss]exual OR [Ee]rectile'
Urinary dysfunction	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I & Medication log Records containing '[li]cont OR [Ff]req OR [Uu]rge'
Depression	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I & Medication log Records containing "[Dd]epres"
Cognitive Impairment	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part I Medication log Records containing "[Cc]ogni"

We computed two variations of the MDS risk score:

1. A version including all risk and prodromal markers presented in **Table 10**. We refer to this version as the MDS risk score
2. A version excluding GBA Present, LRRK2 Present, Polygenic risk score, Subthreshold Parkinsonism, Neurogenic Orthostatic hypotension and Cognitive deficit. We refer to this version as the partial MDS risk score.

5.2.3 PD risk assessment models

In this analysis, we present two types of PD risk assessment models:

- The SAM-PD risk score model that was based on wearable data-based metrics of sleep and activity, demographics, and anthropometrics.
- Models that combine the SAM-PD risk score and variations of the MDS-risk score.

The SAM-PD risk score is the probability of being classified as PD. The probability threshold for a person to be classified as PD was optimized with ROC analysis by maximising Youden's Index for equal cost in sensitivity and specificity.

The SAM-PD risk score is then evaluated against the output probability of the MDS PD risk calculator²². The MDS PD risk calculator is a naive Bayesian classifier that assigns a pretest probability based on age which is adjusted with the presence of the MDS risk and prodromal markers. The calculator assigns subject as in the prodromal stage of PD if their risk probability exceeds 0.80.

²¹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38692034>

²² <https://www.movementdisorders.org/Prodromal-PD-Calculator.htm>

Feature selection was initially based on three distinct sources:

- an extensive state-of-the-art (SoA) review (outlined in detail in deliverable *D2.4 Updated report on domain review and datasets*),
- a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (QMUL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) and
- data availability in the PPMI portal (IDA-LONI).

5.2.4 Analytical methods

Input feature vector

The model was trained using a reduced feature set derived from the full set of activity and sleep metrics described in Section 5.2.2. To avoid multicollinearity, metrics with high correlation (Pearson $|r| > 0.95$) were removed before the remaining features were ranked using gain importance under subject-aware cross-validation with hyperparameter tuning. The top fifteen ranked metrics listed below were retained, which along with age, sex, height, and weight formed the input feature vector.

- Peak Acceleration Magnitude Median
- Signal Entropy Magnitude Standard Deviation
- RMS Magnitude Standard Deviation
- REM Duration (Minutes) Median
- REM Duration (Minutes) Standard Deviation
- Steps Cadence Standard Deviation
- Signal Entropy Magnitude 75th Percentile Standard Deviation
- RMS Magnitude Standard Mean
- Hourly Steps Median
- Steps Cadence (Steps/Min) Median
- Total Sleep Duration
- N2 Sleep Duration Standard Deviation
- REM Latency Standard Deviation
- NREM Duration Standard Deviation
- Sleep Efficiency (%) Median

Classifier selection

Since the dataset used for model development included 152 PwPD and 32 HC, a Balanced Random Forest Classifier (BRFC) was used to ensure equal representation of classes during the training. Other classifiers, such as logistic regression, were also examined, yet BRFC yielded the best performance.

Leave-one-subject-out evaluation

To evaluate the discriminatory performance of PwPD vs HC, a nested Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation with hyper parameter optimization and probability calibration scheme was adopted to obtain unbiased subject-level performance estimates. In each outer fold, one participant was held out for testing, while the remaining data were split into an 80% training subset for model fitting and hyperparameter optimization and a 20% calibration subset reserved for probability calibration. Z-score normalization was applied using parameters derived exclusively from the training subset to prevent information leakage. Hyperparameters were optimized within the training subset to maximize ROC-AUC, and after completing all inner folds, the most frequently chosen configuration was retained. The LOSO evaluation was then repeated using this configuration across all folds. Within each fold, probability calibration was performed on the calibration subset using sigmoid scaling.

The model performance was assessed using the metrics of balanced accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, F1-score, ROC-AUC, PR-AUC, Brier score, and Expected Calibration

Error (ECE). Reliability diagrams were also used to visually compare the non-calibrated and calibrated curves. The model's interpretability was assessed using GINI indices, global and local SHAP values, and LIME values to visualize individual-level feature contributions.

Evaluation on PwPD and HC cohorts

The clinical validity of the SAM-PD risk score was initially evaluated by correlating it against the minimum putamen Specific Binding Ratio (SBR) from DaTscans in PwPD and HC.

Evaluation on at-risk cohort

For the evaluation on the at-risk cohort, after the model was trained and calibrated using the complete dataset (PwPD and HC) it was subsequently used to infer SAM-PD risk scores for the at-risk participants. The final model evaluation step was implemented through the following analyses:

- the correlation of the SAM-PD risk score with the minimum putamen Specific Binding Ratio (SBR) obtained from DaTscans
- the correlation between the SAM-PD risk score and the MDS risk score the ability of the SAM-PD model and the MDS risk scores to detect dopaminergic deficit
- the discriminative performance of the SAM-PD model and the MDS risk scores in detecting α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity.

In order to further assess the screening value of the SAM-PD risk score in combination with the MDS risk score we examined the following three risk scores combinations: Max risk score, Sequential risk score and Adaptive Weights risk score.

- The Max risk score applied a fixed probability threshold of 0.67 to the SAM-PD risk score to obtain a binary digital classification. This threshold was derived from ROC analysis during the PwPD versus HC leave-one-subject-out cross-validation phase by maximizing sensitivity while constraining specificity to be at least 0.75. The MDS risk score was binarized using the threshold of 0.80, as recommended by the MDS guidelines. Participants were subsequently classified as at risk if either the SAM-PD digital score or the MDS binary risk score indicated risk.
- The Sequential risk score followed a consecutive screening logic, requiring both tools to indicate risk simultaneously. Under this configuration, only participants with a SAM-PD score above the predefined threshold and a positive MDS risk status were classified as at risk.
- The Adaptive Weights risk score integrated both SAM-PD and MDS risk scores in a continuous and data-driven manner. The risk scores were combined through an adaptive weighting mechanism that adjusted the contribution of each source according to their agreement. The digital probability was reinforced when both indicators were concordant and attenuated when they diverged.

The adaptive model was trained using a stratified k-fold cross-validation framework with an inner optimisation loop to tune the weighting parameters. The most frequent parameter configuration across folds was then selected to construct the final model.

These combined models were subsequently compared against the individual SAM-PD and MDS risk scores in terms of their ability to detect the presence of dopaminergic deficit or α -synuclein SAA positivity.

Test-retest reliability analysis

We performed a test-retest reliability analysis to determine the minimum aggregation interval that yields consistent measurements of the SAM-PD risk score and of the associated sleep

and activity metrics. We assumed that the health status of a given subject remains fairly stable for the first two months of the observation period. The daily activity and sleep metrics were aggregated over consecutive non-overlapping time windows of 7, 14, 21, and 28 days. Those aggregates were used to estimate the SAM-PD risk score for the given time window. We then computed the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC(3,k)) considering the SAM-PD risk score and the aggregated metric of the first and second window for a given aggregation interval within the two-month period as the test and retest measurement, respectively, for all 15 metrics and four aggregation intervals. Only participants having available sensor data in both test and retest windows were considered in each ICC iteration.

Bias and fairness

To evaluate bias and fairness, we stratified performance across age, sex, race and ethnicity. Alongside conventional classification metrics, we reported Demographic Parity Difference/Ratio and Equalized Odds Difference to identify subgroup disparities.

Technical Implementation and Resource Specifications

The analysis pipeline reported was developed using Python 3.12. The scikit-learn²³ and imblearn²⁴ libraries were used for the models, seaborn²⁵ and matplotlib²⁶ for data visualization and scipy²⁷ for statistical testing. The analysis was performed on a workstation with the following specifications: (CPU: 24 core, 3.8GHz, RAM: 128GB, VRAM: 48GB). Upon completion of the analysis, the results will be published along with the developed source code after removing any identifying information of the dataset used.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Participants

Three hundred and twenty-five (325) participants were considered for this analysis (PwPD = 152, HC = 32, at-risk = 141). **Figure 7** and **Figure 8** show the demographics and anthropometrics of the participants fulfilling the inclusion criteria. **Table 11** summarises the demographic characteristics of the Verily Study Watch subset used for the development and evaluation of the SAM-PD model. The table reports the number of participants per group, their sex distribution, and age categories, together with summary statistics on disease duration and MDS-UPDRS Part III motor scores where applicable.

Table 11 Demographic and clinical characteristics of the Verily Study Watch subset used for the development and evaluation of the SAM-PD model. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	PD	At risk	Healthy Controls
n (total n = 325)	152	141	32
Demographics			
Females	61	91	13
Males	91	50	19
Age (yrs)			
<50	3	2	4
50-54	4	8	1
55-59	14	27	3

²³ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

²⁴ <https://imbalanced-learn.org/stable/>

²⁵ <https://seaborn.pydata.org>

²⁶ <https://matplotlib.org/stable/>

²⁷ <https://scipy.org>

60-64	23	30	2
65-69	38	37	10
70-74	35	28	4
75-79	27	7	3
>80	8	2	5
Clinical characteristics			
Avg. disease duration in years (std)	6.12 (2.41)	N.A.	N.A.
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	25.87 (11.41)	4.24 (6.75)	3.29 (3.96)

Figure 7 Demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the PD and HC groups of the Verily Study Watch cohort used in the analysis. The top row of bar plots displays the counts for race, ethnicity, and sex, while the bottom row of histograms illustrates the distributions of age, weight, and height within the training dataset.

Figure 8 Demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the at-risk group of the Verily Study Watch cohort used in the analysis. The top row of bar plots displays the counts for race, ethnicity, and sex, while the bottom row of histograms illustrates the distributions of age, weight, and height within the evaluation dataset.

5.3.2 Model performance

The AI-PROGNOSIS model demonstrated an excellent accuracy on the classification of PwPD vs HC, as seen by results on **Table 12**. In addition, **Figure 9** illustrates the ROC and PRC curves for the model. The reliability analysis of the calibrated and uncalibrated PD risk estimation scores are shown in **Table 12** along with the Brier Score. Noteworthy, the SAM-PD risk scores for the PD and healthy controls were calculated during the cross-validation, while the Prodromal cohort was calculated after training the model on the entire training set (PwPD and healthy controls).

Table 12 Performance of uncalibrated and calibrated models in classifying PwPD and HC. Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) validation schema was used on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Model	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	C-Index	PR AUC	Brier Score	ECE
SAM-PD (Uncalibrated)	0.87	0.97	0.86	0.87	0.91	0.93	0.98	0.09	0.13
SAM-PD (Calibrated)	0.90	0.98	0.89	0.90	0.93	0.95	0.99	0.06	0.03

Figure 9 Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) and Precision-Recall (PR) Curves of the uncalibrated and calibrated PD risk estimation models.

Figure 10 Reliability curves of the uncalibrated and calibrated PD risk estimation model. The relationship between the mean predicted probability and the observed fraction of positive outcomes is displayed for both the uncalibrated and calibrated models. The dashed diagonal line represents the ideal scenario of perfect calibration, where predicted probabilities perfectly match the true probabilities.

Fairness and bias in performance

To assess potential subgroup-specific biases in model performance, we stratified participants by age, BMI, and sex. For each subgroup, the calibrated model’s predictive performance was evaluated using the same metrics applied in the analysis described in Section 5.3.2. These results are presented in **Table 13** which highlights how model performance varied across demographic subgroups when distinguishing PD from HC.

In addition to performance metrics, we also assessed group fairness using standard fairness-specific indicators. **Table 14** reports the Demographic Parity Difference (DPD), Demographic Parity Ratio (DPR), and Equalized Odds Difference (EOD) across age, BMI, and sex, quantifying the extent to which the model’s predictions deviated across sensitive subgroups. Together, these analyses provide a complementary evaluation of both predictive performance and fairness-related properties of the model.

Table 13 Performance of the calibrated model in predicting PD risk across age, BMI, and sex subgroups under the Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) validation schema, using the PD and HC populations of the Verily Study Watch dataset. Reported metrics include balanced accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, F1-score, C-Index, PR-AUC, Brier score, and Expected Calibration Error (ECE), enabling subgroup-level assessment of classification performance and calibration quality.

Sensitive variable	Sensitive Group	N=	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	C-Index	PR AUC	Brier Score	ECE
Age	<50	7	0.83	1.00	0.67	1.00	0.80	1.00	1.00	0.14	0.26
	50-54	5	0.75	1.00	0.50	1.00	0.67	0.75	0.95	0.18	0.21
	55-59	17	0.93	1.00	0.86	1.00	0.92	0.98	1.00	0.09	0.21

	60-64	25	0.93	1.00	0.87	1.00	0.93	0.96	1.00	0.08	0.18
	65-69	48	0.91	1.00	0.82	1.00	0.89	0.97	0.99	0.08	0.14
	70-74	39	0.86	0.97	0.97	0.75	0.97	0.86	0.98	0.07	0.15
	75-79	30	0.76	0.96	0.85	0.67	0.90	0.90	0.98	0.09	0.12
	>=80	13	0.80	0.80	1.00	0.60	0.89	0.95	0.97	0.16	0.19
BMI	Under weight	4	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.05	0.19
	Normal weight	61	0.76	0.94	0.85	0.67	0.89	0.88	0.98	0.10	0.15
	Over weight	82	0.94	1.00	0.86	1.00	0.93	0.97	0.99	0.08	0.13
	Obese	37	0.81	0.97	0.88	0.75	0.92	0.80	0.97	0.10	0.15
Sex	Female	74	0.85	0.96	0.85	0.85	0.90	0.95	0.99	0.09	0.17
	Male	110	0.89	0.98	0.88	0.89	0.92	0.93	0.98	0.09	0.14
Ethnicity	Ashkenazi Jewish	52	0.79	1.00	0.89	0.78	0.87	0.93	1.00	0.10	0.18
	Basque	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Hispanic/Latino	4	0.75	0.86	0.75	0.75	0.86	0.95	1.00	0.22	0.14
	Not Specified	127	0.91	0.96	0.90	0.93	0.94	0.98	0.98	0.08	0.21
Race	American Indian/Alaska Native	1	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
	Asian	3	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.01	0.08
	Black	2	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.01	0.01
	White	178	0.87	0.96	0.84	0.89	0.96	0.98	0.98	0.09	0.21

Table 14 Fairness assessment of the calibrated model in predicting PD risk across age, BMI, and sex subgroups under the Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) validation schema, using the PD and HC populations of the Verily Study Watch dataset. Reported metrics include Demographic Parity Difference (DPD), Demographic Parity Ratio (DPR), and Equalized Odds Difference (EOD), quantifying potential disparities in model predictions across sensitive subgroups.

Sensitive variable	Demographic Parity Difference	Demographic Parity Ratio	Equalized Odds Difference
Age	0.61	0.32	0.50
BMI	0.02	0.98	0.03
Sex	0.13	0.84	0.15
Ethnicity	0.75	0.00	0.93
Race	0.27	0.73	0.14

Model calibration and uncertainty quantification

The calibration of the SAM-PD risk model ensures that the probability predicted corresponds to the probable occurrence rate. **Figure 10** depicts the reliability curve of our model. It is evident that the uncalibrated model overestimates the probability of the outcome (class PwPD). In addition, for a binary classifier, the reliability curve can be seen as a measure of uncertainty as its inherent over/underestimation for a certain probability is known before the inference. To alleviate the probability overestimation of the model we performed a model calibration using a meta-estimator with CalibratedClassifierCV (scikit-learn) with the sigmoid method²⁸, which improved performance metrics (see Section 5.3.2).

Feature importance and model explainability

To investigate which features drove the SAM-PD risk score model decisions, we performed three independent automatic feature importance explorations.

GINI index–based feature importance was derived from the trained Balanced Random Forest Classifier, providing a global ranking of features by their contribution to node splits (**Figure 11**). This analysis indicated that peak acceleration magnitude, signal entropy, and REM sleep duration ranked among the most influential features.

Figure 11 Balanced random forest GINI index-based feature importance of the features of the SAM-PD risk score model.

Global SHAP analysis was then applied to the calibrated model to quantify both the direction and magnitude of individual feature contributions across all participants (**Figure 12**). SHAP confirmed the predominance of movement-related metrics (e.g., peak acceleration and signal entropy) while also highlighting the role of sleep-related features such as REM duration. The

²⁸ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.calibration.CalibratedClassifierCV.html>

bidirectional distribution of SHAP values across classes further demonstrated the discriminatory capacity of these variables in separating PD from HC.

Finally, we applied LIME to generate local explanations for individual predictions (**Figure 13**). This participant-level interpretability method provided insight into how specific feature values combined to drive a high-risk classification, illustrating the practical transparency of the model at the clinical decision-making level.

Taken together, the three approaches consistently identified movement irregularities (peak acceleration and entropy measures) as the dominant predictors, followed by sleep-related features, particularly REM duration.

Figure 12 The global SHAP values for the calibrated SAM-PD risk score model, illustrating the influence and direction of the top features on the model's output. Each dot represents a single observation, with its colour indicating the feature value (high or low) and its position along the x-axis showing its impact on the model's output. Features are ranked by their overall importance, providing insight into which variables are most predictive of PD risk.

LIME Explanation, Risk Score: 94.8%

Figure 13 Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) explanation of a SAM-PD risk score prediction. An example plot for a single participant, detailing the feature contributions to the final predicted risk score of 94.8%. The horizontal bars indicate how each feature's value influences the model's output, with the length and colour of the bar representing the magnitude and direction of the contribution to the high PD risk score.

Test-Retest Reliability Analysis

Most features demonstrated good to excellent reliability ($ICC \geq 0.75$) across all aggregation intervals, particularly those related to movement intensity and entropy. Certain sleep-related measures, such as REM latency and stage duration variability (N2 and NREM), showed lower reliability at shorter intervals but improved with longer observation periods. These patterns indicate that while most features provide robust short-term reproducibility, certain sleep features benefit from extended monitoring windows. The feature-level ICC trajectories across interval sizes are illustrated in **Figure 14**.

Figure 14 Test-retest reliability of the SAM-PD risk score and of the associated sleep and activity metrics. Each sub-plot displays the ICC(3,k) (y-axis) as a function of measurement aggregation interval in days (x-axis). The dotted line connects ICC values across intervals, with shaded areas representing 95% confidence intervals (Cis). ICC(3,k) thresholds for excellent, good, and poor reliability are 0.90, 0.75, and 0.50, respectively.

Correlation of SAM-PD and MDS risk scores

To compare how well our SAM-PD risk score aligns with the MDS risk score, we correlated the SAM-PD and MDS risk scores of the at-risk cohort. The two scores were moderately correlated with $r=0.34$, $p<0.001$. (**Figure 15**).

Figure 15 Correlation between the SAM-PD risk score and the MDS PD risk model derived score

Correlation with and Predictive Performance for dopaminergic deficiency

To examine the capability of the model to estimate dopaminergic deficiency, we correlated the digital risk score with DaTscan-derived measures of striatal dopamine transporter availability. All Verily Study Watch cohort participants were subjected to DaTscan examination before the watch measurement period. For both the PwPD and at-risk cohorts, DaTscans acquired more than three years before watch measurement initiation were excluded to account for potential disease progression, whereas all available DaTscans were retained for the HC. After applying this criterion, data were available for 92 PwPD, 138 at-risk participants, and 32 HC. For each participant, the minimum SBR value between the left and right putamen from the DaTscan examination closest to watch measurement initiation was used. A dopaminergic deficit (abnormal DaTscan) was defined by a minimum putamen SBR value of less than 1.037, based on existing literature (Tinaz et al., 2018), or by an abnormal visual interpretation. The resulting time interval between DaTscan acquisition and initiation of the Verily Study Watch measurement period was 422.18 ± 295.07 days for PwPD, 291.46 ± 212.4 days for the at-risk cohort, and 2803.35 ± 328.14 days for HC. The SAM-PD risk scores obtained during the LOSO cross-validation phase were correlated with the corresponding minimum putamen SBR values.

In the PwPD and HC groups, a strong negative correlation was observed between SAM-PD risk scores and SBR values (**Figure 16**, Pearson $r = -0.68$, $p < 0.001$). This relationship reflects the well-established dopaminergic deficit in PD compared with HC and provides an important biological validation of the digital score against a disease hallmark.

The analysis was subsequently extended to an at-risk cohort ($n = 138$), where reduced SBR is indicative of early dopaminergic dysfunction prior to clinical diagnosis. In this group, a moderate but significant negative correlation was observed between digital risk scores and minimum putamen SBR (**Figure 17**, Pearson $r = -0.43$, $p < 0.001$). Whereas the PwPD vs. HC correlation is dominated by between-group differences, the findings in the at-risk cohort suggest that the SAM-PD risk score is sensitive to inter-individual variation in dopaminergic function within an at-risk participant.

Eventually, we evaluated the model's predictive performance of classifying participants with dopaminergic deficiency or not (normal vs. reduced SBR). As summarised in **Table 15**, the SAM-PD risk score outperformed the MDS-UPDRS risk score (balanced accuracy = 0.76 vs. 0.66; ROC-AUC = 0.84 vs. 0.66) in detecting dopaminergic deficit. The adaptive weights composite model integrating SAM-PD and MDS risk score (partial) achieved the highest performance (balanced accuracy = 0.77, ROC-AUC = 0.85), with improved precision and PR-AUC. Output distributions stratified by SBR status (**Figure 18**) confirmed that the composite model provided the clearest separation between normal and reduced dopaminergic function, particularly within the at-risk cohort.

Figure 16 Correlation between the SAM-PD risk score for PwPD and HC population and the minimum putamen Specific Binding Ratio (SBR).

Figure 17 Correlation between the digital score for prodromal population and the minimum putamen Specific Binding Ratio (SBR).

Table 15 Performance of models in detecting dopaminergic deficit on the Verily Study Watch at-risk cohort. Partial refers to a partial version of the MDS risk score or its combination with the SAM-PD risk score.

Model	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	C-Index	PR AUC	MCC	Selected Threshold
SAM-PD risk score	0.76	0.31	0.76	0.76	0.44	0.84	0.40	0.37	0.67
MDS-risk score	0.66	0.39	0.41	0.91	0.40	0.66	0.44	0.31	0.80
MDS-risk score (partial)	0.67	0.75	0.35	0.98	0.48	0.67	0.59	0.47	0.80
Max risk score	0.73	0.26	0.76	0.69	0.39	0.73	0.53	0.31	0.67/0.80
Max risk score (partial)	0.75	0.30	0.76	0.74	0.43	0.75	0.55	0.36	0.67/0.80
Sequential risk score	0.69	0.70	0.41	0.97	0.52	0.69	0.59	0.49	0.67/0.80
Sequential risk score (partial)	0.68	1.00	0.35	1.00	0.52	0.68	0.72	0.57	0.67/0.80
Adaptive Weights risk score	0.76	0.24	0.94	0.59	0.39	0.83	0.52	0.35	0.51
Adaptive Weights risk score (partial)	0.77	0.25	0.94	0.60	0.40	0.85	0.60	0.36	0.51

Figure 18 Model Output Distributions by Specific Binding Ratio (SBR). The scores are stratified by SBR Status (Normal vs Reduced), which indicates either normal or reduced dopaminergic activity. This visualizes how each model’s output distribution differs between individuals with and without evidence of dopaminergic deficit.

Predictive Performance of pathological α -Synuclein aggregates

We performed a comparative analysis between the SAM-PD risk score, the MDS-UPDRS risk score, and several composite models integrating both, into the ability of the models to capture an underlying α -synuclein positivity in cerebrospinal fluid. As detailed **Table 16**, the SAM-PD risk score significantly outperformed the MDS risk score in estimating SAA positivity. The

maximum discriminatory capacity was achieved by the composite model, which highlights the complementary value derived from the integration of digital and established clinical features.

Table 16 Performance of models in detecting α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity on the Verily Study Watch at-risk cohort. Partial refers to a partial version of the MDS risk score or its combination with the SAM-PD risk score.

Model	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	C-Index	PR AUC	MCC	Selected Threshold
SAM-PD risk score	0.73	0.48	0.60	0.86	0.56	0.78	0.48	0.43	0.67
MDS-risk score	0.62	0.41	0.35	0.89	0.38	0.62	0.44	0.26	0.80
MDS-risk score (partial)	0.61	0.63	0.25	0.97	0.36	0.61	0.50	0.32	0.80
Max risk score	0.71	0.38	0.65	0.77	0.48	0.71	0.55	0.35	0.67/0.80
Max risk score (partial)	0.72	0.44	0.60	0.84	0.51	0.72	0.56	0.39	0.67/0.80
Sequential risk score	0.64	0.75	0.30	0.98	0.43	0.64	0.59	0.41	0.67/0.80
Sequential risk score (partial)	0.62	0.83	0.25	0.99	0.39	0.62	0.61	0.41	0.67/0.80
Adaptive Weight risk score	0.77	0.57	0.65	0.89	0.61	0.78	0.58	0.51	0.86
Adaptive Weight risk score (partial)	0.76	0.45	0.70	0.82	0.55	0.78	0.56	0.44	0.73

Furthermore, the model output distributions (**Figure 19**) showed notably higher SAM-PD and composite risk scores among SAA-positive participants. The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis (**Figure 20**) further confirmed the robust discriminative ability of all models, with the Composite approach yielding the superior performance.

Figure 19 Model Output Distributions by α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity. The scores are stratified by SAA Status (Negative vs Positive), indicating the presence or absence of pathological α -synuclein aggregates. This visualizes how each model's output distribution differs between individuals with negative and positive α -synuclein seeding activity.

Figure 20 Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve comparison for model-based classification of Specific Binding Ratio (SBR) and α -synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA) positivity. The discriminative performance of the SAM-PD risk score, MDS risk score, and Composite risk models in classifying two distinct biological outcomes. ROC curves for the classification of dopaminergic deficiency (Normal vs. Reduced SBR; left), and the ROC curves for the classification of α -synuclein SAA status (Negative vs. Positive; right). The Area Under the Curve (AUC) alongside the 95% confidence intervals is presented as shaded area.

Predictive Performance for presence of α -Synuclein Seed Amplification Assay positivity or dopaminergic deficiency

Lastly, we performed an additional comparative analysis in which α -synuclein SAA positivity and DaTscan-derived dopaminergic deficit were jointly evaluated as a combined biological outcome. Participants were classified as positive if they exhibited either α -synuclein SAA positivity or a reduced SBR value, and as negative if they showed both SAA negativity and normal dopaminergic imaging. This binary outcome approximates a screening-oriented biological definition of underlying synucleinopathy or dopaminergic dysfunction.

Using this combined label, we compared the performance of the SAM-PD risk score, the MDS-UPDRS risk score, and the composite Adaptive Weight model (**Table 17**, **Figure 21**, **Figure 22**). The integrated model again yielded the highest discriminative performance, reflecting the complementary value of digital behavioural metrics and established clinical markers when identifying individuals with early biological signatures of Parkinson's disease.

Table 17 Performance of models in estimating the combined biological outcome (SAA positivity or reduced SBR) on the Verily Study Watch at-risk cohort.

Model	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	C-Index	PR AUC	MCC	Selected Threshold
SAM-PD risk score	0.75	0.48	0.69	0.80	0.56	0.80	0.53	0.44	0.67
MDS-risk score	0.59	0.42	0.28	0.90	0.33	0.59	0.42	0.21	0.80
MDS-risk score (partial)	0.59	0.67	0.21	0.97	0.32	0.59	0.52	0.30	0.80
Max risk score	0.71	0.39	0.69	0.72	0.50	0.73	0.57	0.35	0.67/0.80
Max risk score (partial)	0.73	0.44	0.69	0.78	0.54	0.75	0.60	0.40	0.67/0.80

Sequential risk score	0.63	0.80	0.28	0.98	0.41	0.63	0.61	0.41	0.67/0.80
Sequential risk score (partial)	0.60	1.00	0.21	1.00	0.34	0.60	0.69	0.41	0.67/0.80
Adaptive Weight risk score	0.68	0.30	0.90	0.46	0.45	0.78	0.56	0.30	0.37
Adaptive Weight risk score (partial)	0.69	0.31	0.90	0.47	0.46	0.79	0.62	0.31	0.37

Figure 21 Model Output Distributions by Combined Biological Status (SAA Positivity or Reduced SBR). The scores are stratified by Combined Status (Negative vs Positive), where the positive class reflects either α -synuclein SAA positivity or reduced putamen Specific Binding Ratio (SBR). This visualizes how each model’s output distribution differs between individuals with and without evidence of underlying synucleinopathy or dopaminergic deficit.

Figure 22 Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve comparison for the classification of the combined biological outcome (SAA Positivity or Reduced SBR). The discriminative performance of the SAM-PD risk score, MDS-UPDRS risk score, and Composite Adaptive Weight model in classifying individuals based on the combined biomarker definition. The ROC curves display the separation between Negative and Positive combined status, with the Area Under the Curve (AUC) and 95% confidence intervals (shaded area) presented for each model.

Early Generalizability Evidence on the dBM-DEV Study Dataset

To evaluate the SAM-PD model's robustness beyond the initial training environment, an assessment was conducted using the dBM-DEV study dataset, collected under the AI-PROGNOSIS project. This independent dataset is characterized by a different geographical setting and data acquisition using a different wrist-worn wearable device compared to the Verily Study Watch used in the training phase.

The study included a total of 49 participants, comprising 23 PwPD and 26 HC. The specific demographic and clinical characteristics of this independent validation cohort are summarized in **Table 18**.

Table 18 Demographic and clinical characteristics of the dBM-DEV dataset used for the validation and evaluation of the SAM-PD model. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	PD	Healthy Controls
n (total n = 49)	26	23
Demographics		
Females	11	8
Males	15	15
Age (yrs)		
<50	0	1
50-54	2	4
55-59	3	1
60-64	8	3
65-69	8	4
70-74	1	2
75-79	2	7
>80	0	1
Clinical characteristics		
Avg. disease duration in years (std)	5.04 (4.23)	N.A.
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	20.62 (9.63)	0.17 (0.83)

The SAM-PD model was applied to the dBM-DEV cohort to classify participants as PwPD or HC without re-training. Despite the heterogeneity in data acquisition hardware and geographic settings, the model preserved its discriminative capacity. The analysis yielded a performance with an F1 Score of 0.85. Furthermore, the model achieved an ROC AUC of 0.89 and a PR-AUC of 0.92 (**Figure 23**).

Figure 23 Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) and Precision-Recall (PR) Curves of the SAM-PD model applied to the dBM-DEV validation dataset

These findings suggest preliminary indications that the digital biomarkers and the SAM-PD risk score may maintain their discriminative value beyond the specific hardware and geographical context of the Verily Study Watch cohort. The model's performance on the dBM-DEV dataset suggests a potential for transferability, motivating further validation of its utility as a screening tool in diverse real-world settings.

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Interpretation

This analysis explored the feasibility of using smartwatch-derived sleep and activity metrics to estimate PD risk and assessed the association between the SAM-PD risk score and established clinical and biological markers. The model demonstrated encouraging performance and showed potential value as an objective, non-invasive complement to existing approaches, with possible application as a screening tool. This was evidenced by the significant correlation of the SAM-PD score with the SBR, as well as the detection of dopaminergic deficiency and pathological α -synuclein aggregates. Taken together, the results of the PD risk modelling confirm the strong potential of combining wearable derived digital biomarkers with established clinicodemographic factors for early identification of PD.

The calibrated model, based on sleep and activity metrics combined with easily obtainable demographic information (age, height, weight, and sex), achieved high performance in distinguishing PwPD from HC. Fairness and subgroup analyses indicated that model performance was generally consistent across BMI, sex, and race groups. In contrast, notable disparities were observed for age and ethnicity. The age analysis suggested that the model behaved more consistently for participants between approximately 55 and 75 years, with greater variability at the younger and older extremes. Interpretation of ethnicity effects was limited by the composition of the cohort, as most participants did not specify their ethnicity and most reported cases were Ashkenazi Jewish, leading to an inherent imbalance and reduced reliability of the associated fairness metrics. These findings underscore the importance of continued subgroup evaluation as the model is tested in larger and more diverse populations.

Test-retest reliability analysis showed that most metrics were highly reliable even at the one-week aggregation interval, with good to excellent ICC. Features related to movement and activity demonstrated strong stability across different aggregation intervals, while some sleep-

related measures, such as REM latency and stage variability, exhibited improved reproducibility with longer aggregation periods (of up to 4 weeks).

Furthermore, we assessed the correlation of the SAM-PD risk score with established clinical and biological markers of PD. In the PD and HC groups, the score was negatively correlated with the minimum SBR of the putamen (measured via DaTscan), a finding consistent with the known dopaminergic deficits in PD. In the at-risk cohort, a weaker but negative and significant correlation was observed, suggesting sensitivity to early dopaminergic changes prior to clinical diagnosis. The digital score was also associated with α -synuclein SAA positivity, achieving performance comparable to, and in some cases exceeding, the MDS-UPDRS risk score. The composite model that integrated both digital and clinical markers yielded the strongest overall performance, indicating that the two approaches are complementary.

Digital features reflecting sleep disturbance, reduced physical activity intensity, and diminished smoothness of movement (in terms of Peak acceleration entropy) emerged as the strongest predictors. This finding is consistent with prior evidence linking REM-sleep behaviour disorder, bradykinesia, and sedentary behaviour to prodromal PD. Compared with the MDS prodromal PD risk model, the SAM-PD risk model provided higher sensitivity in detecting individuals with decreased SBR and negative SAA suggesting that continuously monitored digital metrics can serve as complementary dimensions of early disease not represented by conventional clinical markers. Comparison of the SAM-PD and MDS risk scores indicates a trade-off between sensitivity and specificity. SAM-PD generally provides higher sensitivity, whereas the MDS risk score offers higher specificity. Although neither method consistently outperforms the other across all metrics, the combined models, particularly the Adaptive Weight Risk Score, achieve a more balanced performance by integrating both digital and clinical information.

The results of this study support the feasibility of a digital-first approach for evaluating PD risk. This approach is fully aligned with the AI-PRA study of the project and where the SAM-PD risk model and its combination with the MDS risk model will be further evaluated and compared against the MDS risk score alone using prospective data. Overall, the SAM-PD risk model could complement existing tools, such as the MDS risk score, to form a non-invasive screening framework for identifying individuals at increased risk of PD. To further assess the generalizability of the SAM-PD risk score, we will test it on data from the UK Biobank. This dataset includes individuals with prodromal Parkinson's who were later diagnosed with PD. Result from the analysis will be presented in D5.8 'AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem: proof-of-concept and beyond'.

5.4.2 Beyond SoA

This section outlines how the SAM-PD risk model advances beyond the current state of the art, across methodological analytical and validation components. We evaluated our approach and its novelty by straight comparison against the most recent research presented in D2.4 'Updated report on domain review and datasets'. We highlight novelties in feature extraction, model performance, robustness, fairness, interpretability and reproducibility as well as evidence for generalisability. Together these advancements demonstrate that the SAM-PD model exceeds traditional approaches in multiple clinically relevant domains.

- Feature set enhancement:** Previous work, analysed wearable data using simple activity counts or coarse epochs (e.g., Schalkamp et al., 2023, Acquah et al., 2024). Our feature engineering approach used the Verily Study Watch dataset to extract features from wrist acceleration for three categories of indicators, i.e.: sleep, slowness of movement, and physical activity. These categories were chosen to capture complementary aspects of daily behaviour and motor function.

- **Improved discriminatory performance result:** In our study we extensively compared: 1) PwPD vs HC and at-risk cohort 2) detection of dopaminergic deficit, 3) correlation with SBR, 4) detection of negative SAA result. Our model has achieved SoA performance on multiple domains. The custom feature set has allowed the SAM-PD score to achieve better results relative to Schalkmap et al. (2025) in the classification of PwPD and healthy individuals (AUPRC = 0.99 ± 0.005 vs 0.96 ± 0.01 and AUC = 0.95 ± 0.02 vs 0.87), and association of the digital score with the minimum putamen SBR of the at-risk participants ($r = -0.43$, $p = 1 \times 10^{-7}$ vs $r = -0.32$, $p = 6.64 \times 10^{-4}$).
- **Balanced sensitivity-specificity Trade-off:** The combined Adaptive Weight risk score, integrating the SAM-PD and MDS-UPDRS risk scores, demonstrated a more balanced sensitivity–specificity profile at the detection of dopaminergic deficit or of abnormal SAA result (Precision: 0.30, Sensitivity: 0.90) compared with the previous SoA approach (Schalkmap et al. 2025, Precision: 0.19, Sensitivity: 0.71), offering improved overall discrimination.
- **Suitability for longitudinal unobtrusive monitoring:** Few studies in the current literature evaluate temporal stability of digital biomarkers, despite the importance of longitudinal monitoring in prodromal PD. We assessed test-retest reliability using ICC(3,k) across multiple time windows, finding that most features demonstrated good to excellent reliability ($ICC > 0.9$) over periods ranging from 7 to 28 days. This supports their suitability for robust, unobtrusive monitoring.
- **Bias assessment:** We conducted comprehensive bias assessment for 5 key sensitive variables age, BMI, sex, ethnicity and race. For assessing bias in the dataset, we used qualitative visual assessment and for assessing the model fairness we used Demographic Parity Difference, Demographic Parity Ratio, and Equalized Odds Difference.
- **Reproducibility:** Our feature extraction pipelines are based on both open-source models (e.g., oxford wearables group algorithms) and custom models that will eventually be released. This guarantees end-to-end reproducibility from raw accelerometer data to the final SAM-PD risk score.
- **Generalisability and Prospective Assessment:** An assessment of the model's generalisability was conducted using the dBM-DEV dataset (N=49; 26 HC, 23 PwPD), demonstrating that the SAM-PD model preserves its ability to distinguish PwPD from HC in a different geographical setting and with data from a different wrist wearable. It achieved a balanced performance with an F1 score of 0.85, an ROC AUC of 0.89 and a PR-AUC of 0.92. In parallel, the prospective AI-PRA study will provide an opportunity to validate the SAM-PD model within an at-risk cohort.

5.4.3 Limitations

The current analysis carries certain limitations.

- **Sample size and cohort clinico-demographics:** Although the Verily Study Watch dataset provides a large collection of continuously recorded free-living accelerometer data, the number of healthy controls was limited compared with the PD group. This imbalance may have influenced model training despite the use of a Balanced Random Forest classifier. In the calibration step, the proportion of healthy controls did not reflect the expected prevalence relative to PD cases. Additional calibration on a more population-representative dataset, such as the UK Biobank and prospective studies with longitudinal follow-ups, would therefore be needed.
- **Generalizability to different populations:** The used subjects were drawn from research setting with limited sociodemographic diversity. To confirm the model's robustness and

fairness, external validation over a wider and more heterogeneous population, including underrepresented demographic groups is needed.

6 Development and evaluation of models to predict PD progression

6.1 Background and objectives

6.1.1 Background

PD is a neurodegenerative disorder, with a significant progression of both motor and non-motor impairments over time. Clinically, the ability to predict the progression of PD is important for clinicians and patients alike, since the early identification of transitions in motor function decline marks a significant turn in treatment pathways and improves the quality of life (Kaye et al., 2024).

6.1.2 Objectives

The objectives of this work are to establish and validate a framework for modelling PD progression. Specifically, the study aims to:

- Develop predictive models that forecast clinically meaningful progression outcomes including motor worsening, treatment escalation, and composite endpoints.
- Identify data-driven PD subtypes using unsupervised clustering approaches that capture distinct baseline profiles and yearly progression behaviour.
- Integrate multimodal information including demographic, clinical, genetic, and wearable (dBM) features, to enhance model performance
- Extend the framework with a deep learning model that jointly predicts long term progression subtype and symptom severity using Transformer-based representations.
- Evaluate model performance, fairness, and robustness in alignment with Trustworthy AI principles.

6.1.3 Implementation

The development of the PD progression focused on building a practical and clinically aligned approach for predicting meaningful progression outcomes in PD. To achieve this, the modelling strategy was guided by established clinical considerations and commonly used research practices, ensuring that the resulting models remain broadly applicable across real-world patient populations.

The target population includes patients diagnosed with PD, especially during the early to mid-stage of the disease, who could benefit from timely adjustment in treatment plans based on forecasted changes in motor function and disability levels. Compared to the initial approach (D3.2), the predictive framework we have developed moves beyond a single outcome (e.g., MDS-UPDRS III motor score) toward a broader set of clinically meaningful endpoints. In particular, two main directions were implemented:

- Data-driven progression subtyping was performed through unsupervised clustering approaches that combined baseline characteristics and short-term changes to identify distinct progression profiles.
- Supervised prediction models were trained to estimate the probability of both clinically defined and data-driven outcomes from baseline data.

A further step forward has been the introduction of wearable sensor data-derived sleep and activity metrics as input to the models, complementing traditional clinical and demographic data. The integration of continuous, real-world monitoring features (e.g., step count, cadence, level of physical activity, sleep metrics) provides objective measures of motor and non-motor symptoms, and holds promise for improving prediction accuracy.

While the previous approaches rely on classical machine learning and clustering techniques to identify progression subtypes and predict progression outcomes, we have explored deep learning architectures capable of modelling disease progression. This work focused on jointly characterizing disease trajectory subtypes and predicting future (up to six years) MDS-UPDRS scores. Knowledge of both is considered crucial for a thorough understanding of the patient's clinical status and disease progression. More specifically, the identification of the progression subtype, derived from diverse clinical features, e.g., demographics, motor assessment, MoCA score, medication, allows for a complete view of the disease's state and its evolution, while the MDS-UPDRS I-III scores are the only widely available data capable of measuring PD progression to some capacity, albeit imperfectly. To this end, we propose a novel dual-task framework that models both progression subtype and severity, capturing their inherent interdependence and supporting a holistic and clinically meaningful assessment of the disease's trajectory. More precisely, as a first step, using an unsupervised approach, we identify three progression subtypes of PD patients, unveiling rapid, moderate and slow progression pace. These subtype labels are then used to supervise the training of PDualNet; a novel multi-task Transformer-based architecture that integrates subtype classification with the prediction of future MDS-UPDRS I-III scores within a unified modelling framework. With a shared encoder for the two tasks, the model effectively learns a joint representation of each patient's disease state ("Disease State Embedding"), while capturing the underlying latent dependencies between subtype classification and symptom progression. This ultimately yields strong predictive performance and generalization capabilities across both objectives.

The aforementioned methodology is developed on the large and most widely used cohort of the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI), as well as on the external validation cohort of Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP), showcasing its superior performance on both tasks over simpler baseline models and demonstrating strong generalization capabilities.

6.2 Methods for yearly PD progression modelling using digital biomarkers

6.2.1 Dataset description

Our PD progression modelling has been developed using the PPMI dataset, a comprehensive longitudinal observational study that provides clinical, demographic, imaging, genetic, and biospecimen data for patients with PD and controls. This dataset is particularly valuable due to its multi-year follow-up structure, enabling the monitoring of symptom trajectories across different disease stages.

For this analysis, we applied inclusion criteria to capture a clinically meaningful and relatively homogeneous mid-stage PD population. Restricting the cohort to defined ranges of disease duration, age, and H&Y stage reduces baseline variability and avoids mixing patient groups with fundamentally different progression trajectories. Specifically, participants were selected according to the following conditions:

- Confirmed PD diagnosis
- Disease duration between 5 and 10 years

- Age between 40 and 80 years
- Hoehn & Yahr stage = 2 or 3
- ON medication state at the clinical assessment

In addition to these clinical inclusion criteria, we further restricted the analysis to patients with available data of two visits: baseline and a follow-up visit approximately one year later. The average interval between visits is 12.08 ± 0.71 months, ensuring a consistent longitudinal and clinically interpretable time window for modelling 12-month progression.

6.2.2 Data pre-processing

This section outlines the comprehensive data preprocessing steps performed on the PPMI dataset. The preprocessing involved loading and merging multiple PPMI data tables, encoding categorical variables, and handling missing values to prepare a clean dataset for analysis.

6.2.3 Handling missing values

The PPMI dataset contains a considerable proportion of missing values, especially across longitudinal visits. This is particularly evident for the total MDS-UPDRS III score, which is a crucial clinical measure in this case, as its change defines one of the primary clinical progression outcomes defined in this study. As shown in **Table 19** the percentage of missing values increases substantially over time, ranging from 7.15% at baseline (BL) to as high as 99.74% by visit 20 (≈ 156 months after baseline). The missing-data problem is not limited to this score but is also present in many other clinical features. This long-term attrition is expected in observational cohorts such as PPMI, where participant retention decreases over extended follow-up periods.

Within the visits that are available for analysis (baseline and ≈ 12 -month follow-up), some clinical variables still contain incomplete entries that require handling at the item level. To mitigate the impact of these missing data on the analysis, we applied a multi-step imputation strategy:

- Rule-based imputation for key variables:
 - The motor examination state (ON/OFF medication) was inferred from the examination type and treatment status.
 - The sex of participants was inferred from responses to sex-specific items in the SCOPA-AUT questionnaire.
- KNN Imputation for continuous and clinical features

This combined strategy minimized information loss while ensuring that the dataset remained both comprehensive and reliable for downstream progression modelling.

Table 19 Percentage of missing values for total MDS-UPDRS III across visits in the PPMI dataset

Visit	Time since baseline (Months), Mean (SD)	% of Participants without MDS-UPDRS III assessment
Baseline	0	7%
V01	3.26 (0.75)	85%
V02	6.44 (1.12)	57%
V03	9.30 (0.83)	87%
V04	12.67 (1.38)	48%
V05	18.42 (1.20)	65%
V06	24.62 (1.50)	63%
V07	30.32 (0.96)	77%

V08	36.62 (1.65)	70%
V09	42.23 (0.88)	82%
V10	48.83 (1.85)	72%
V11	54.30 (1.10)	87%
V12	60.79 (1.99)	75%
V13	72.80 (1.95)	84%
V14	84.59 (1.65)	85%
V15	96.97 (2.43)	91%
V16	109.12 (2.02)	94%
V17	120.74 (2.02)	93%
V18	132.91 (1.74)	95%
V19	144.70 (1.43)	98%
V20	156.21 (1.10)	100%

6.2.3.1 Imputing the state in which participants were assessed

A significant percentage of missing values was observed for variables indicating whether the motor examination was performed in the ON or the OFF-medication state. To address this, the missing values were inferred using two related variables: the recorded examination type and the patient’s treatment status. When the examination type indicated an “OFF” assessment or when no treatment was reported, the state was set to OFF. When the examination type indicated an “ON” assessment, the state was set to ON. This rule-based approach substantially reduced the proportion of missing values.

6.2.3.2 Imputing sex

The variable representing the sex of a participant also exhibited a high percentage of missing values in the demographic data. To infer these values, we used sex-specific responses from the SCOPA-AUT questionnaire. For instance, responses to female-specific items (items 22, 23, 23a) were coded as *female*, while responses to male-specific items (items 24,25) were coded as *male*. This inference further improved the completeness and consistency of the dataset.

6.2.3.3 KNN imputation method

For the remaining missing values in numeric variables listed in Table 22, we employed the k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) imputation method as implemented in scikit-learn. This technique replaces missing values with a weighted average of the nearest neighbours in the feature space, thereby preserving correlations between features and leveraging the multidimensional structure of the data (Troyanskaya et al., 2001). Before performing imputation, we ensured that each patient had a valid MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment for the visits included in the analysis (baseline and ≈12-month follow-up). Imputation was therefore applied only to variables that were missing within these confirmed visits.

6.2.4 Prediction models

Due to the structure of the PPMI database, which consists of multiple CSV files, each containing different types of patient information such as demographics, clinical data, and imaging results, we performed feature selection across various PPMI datasets. Feature inclusion was based on 3 distinct sources:

1. an extensive state of the art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets),

2. a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (QMUL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) to ensure that the model is clinically informed by expert opinions and in line with the prospective data collection (AI-PMP) and
3. data availability in the PPMI portal (IDA-LONI).

As shown in **Table 20**, the clinical partners identified a total of 297 indicators, with the majority sourced from motor assessments.

In the development process, we focused on a targeted subset of features that satisfied both clinical and methodological criteria. This included demographic variables, disease severity measures, selected non-motor scales, and derived composite features (e.g., PIGD, Tremor).

Table 20 Summary of indicators identified from the PPMI dataset for PD progression model development

Category	Number of indicators
Subject Characteristics	16
Biospecimen	2
Imaging	10
Medical History	69
Motor Assessments	165
Non-motor Assessments	35
Total	297

6.2.4.1 Engineering new features to enhance data richness

Since certain indicators are not found directly in the PPMI datasets, several new features were derived from the available data due to their strong relation to PD progression:

- **Genetic mutation classification:** A new feature “Genetic Mutation Status” was computed to classify participants based on their genetic profiles. It is a binary feature and reports whether a participant has a genetic mutation in PD associated genes such as *LRRK2*, *GBA*, *SNCA*, *PRKN*, and *PINK1*. Value “1” is used for the presence of a mutation in any of the related genes and “0” for the absence of a mutation in these genes.
- **Disease duration calculation:** Calculated as the difference between participant's enrolment date and date of PD diagnosis.
- **Composite scores from questionnaires:** Several new composite scores were generated by summing items from various questionnaires used in the PPMI dataset:
- **SCOPA-AUT Total Score:** This score sums all autonomic function items.
- **QUIP Total Score:** A total score was generated from selected items related to impulse control disorders.
- **Geriatric depression scale score:** This score was calculated by summing responses to the Geriatric Depression Scale, with adjustments for reverse-scored items.
- **Epworth sleepiness scale score:** This composite score summed all sleepiness-related items.
- **REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Score:** In this questionnaire, there are primary questions focused on specific symptoms and behaviours associated with RBD, such as experiencing vivid dreams and engaging in potentially injurious activities during sleep. The final question addresses the presence of neurological conditions, such as Parkinsonism, epilepsy, and stroke. In the PPMI dataset, to calculate the total RBD score, a subset of columns representing these primary questions are selected. These columns are then summed across each row (for each participant) to produce an initial score. For the final question on neurological conditions, each condition has its own column in the PPMI dataset. Therefore, we used the maximum value

across these columns to represent the presence of any relevant condition. This maximum function captures the presence of any condition that could contribute to RBD, rather than summing all conditions, which avoids overestimating the impact of multiple conditions.

- **Vital-sign–derived feature**

Orthostatic systolic drop: This feature captures the change in systolic blood pressure from supine to standing. A larger negative difference indicates a greater drop, which reflects impaired autonomic function. Clinically, orthostatic hypotension is often defined as a fall of ≥ 20 mmHg (Freeman et al., 2011).

- **MDS-UPDRS Part III Domain Composites**

Based on item-level scores (0–4 each) from the MDS-UPDRS Part III, we derived several domain-specific subscores that are widely used in Parkinson’s disease research to distinguish clinical subtypes (Goetz et al., 2008; Stebbins et al., 2013).

- **PIGD score (Postural Instability and Gait Difficulty)**: Derived from items assessing gait, freezing of gait, postural stability, posture, and rising from a chair. It reflects balance and gait impairment.
- **Tremor score**: Derived from items assessing rest tremor in the hands, legs, jaw, and lips, as well as postural and kinetic tremor of the hands. It summarizes overall tremor severity
- **Rigidity score**: Derived from items rating rigidity in the neck, right and left upper limbs, and right and left lower limbs. It reflects the global burden of rigidity.
- **Bradykinesia score**: Derived from items assessing finger tapping, hand movements, pronation–supination of the hands, toe tapping, and leg agility on both sides. It summarizes overall slowness of movement.

6.2.4.2 Features subset

The model was built using a subset of clinically relevant features from the PPMI dataset, selected in alignment with the AI-PMP protocol, clinical expert consensus, and evidence from the literature. As shown in **Table 21**, these features span demographic, genetic, and clinical domains, forming a robust foundation for progression prediction. In addition, wearable-derived features from the Verily Study Watch have already been incorporated, providing continuous, real-world digital biomarkers (e.g., step count, cadence, sleep metrics, physical activity) that complement traditional clinical assessments and enhance the model’s predictive capacity.

Table 21 Summary of the selected features and their definitions

Group	Feature	Feature acronym	Constituent Items	Description
Demographics	Age at PD diagnosis	age_at_diagnosis	–	Calculated from year of diagnosis and birthdate.
	Years of formal education	EDUCYRS	–	Total years of schooling completed.
	Biological sex	SEX	–	Male/female
	Disease Duration	DiseaseDuration_Years	-	Disease duration in years
Genetics	Polygenic Risk Score (PRS)	PRS	–	A statistical estimate of an individual's susceptibility to the disease.

Group	Feature	Feature acronym	Constituent Items	Description
Clinical	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD)	LEDD_value	–	Standardized daily antiparkinsonian medication burden.
	MDS-UPDRS Part II total	NP2PTOT	Items 2.1–2.13	Motor aspects of daily living (speech, handwriting, hygiene, walking, etc.).
	MDS-UPDRS Part III total	NP3TOT	Items 3.1–3.18	Motor examination: speech, facial expression, rigidity, bradykinesia, tremor, posture, gait, balance.
	PIGD subscore	PIGD_score	Items 3.9–3.13	Postural instability & gait difficulty: rising from chair, gait, freezing, stability, posture.
	Tremor subscore	TREMOR_score	Items 3.15a–b, 3.16a–b, 3.17a–e, 3.18	Rest tremor, postural tremor, kinetic tremor, constancy of tremor.
	Bradykinesia subscore	BRADYKINESIA_score	Items 3.4–3.8	Finger tapping, hand movements, pronation–supination, toe tapping, leg agility.
	SCOPA-AUT total	SCOPA_Score	GI, urinary, cardiovascular, sexual domains	Autonomic dysfunction score.
	REM Sleep Behavior Disorder Questionnaire	RBDSQ_Score	10 yes/no items	Screening for dream enactment and abnormal sleep behaviors.
	Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)	ESS_Score	8 items	Daytime sleepiness in daily situations.
	QUIP total	QUIP_Score	Items on gambling, eating, shopping, sexual behaviors	Impulse control disorder score.
	Orthostatic systolic blood pressure	drop_sys_bp	SBP/DBP	Orthostatic systolic blood pressure drop (standing – supine)
MDS-UPDRS Part I total	NP1PTOT	Items 1.1–1.13	Non-motor aspects of daily living (cognition, mood, apathy, hallucinations, fatigue, pain, etc.).	

Group	Feature	Feature acronym	Constituent Items	Description
	Pain	P1PAIN	Item 1.9	Pain and other sensations.
	Fatigue	NP1FATG	Item 1.13	Fatigue severity.
	Apathy	NP1APAT	Item 1.5	Apathy/loss of motivation.
	Hallucinations/psychosis	NP1HALL	Item 1.2	Hallucinations and psychosis.
	Cognitive impairment	NP1COG	Item 1.1	Cognitive difficulties.
	Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) total	MCATOT	30 items	Cognitive screening test (higher scores indicate better cognitive performance)
	MDS-UPDRS Part IV total	NP4TOT	Items 4.1–4.6	Motor complications: dyskinesia, fluctuations, off-time.
	Hoehn & Yahr stage	NHY	–	Global PD severity staging (restricted to stages 2–3 in this analysis).
Wearable metrics	Sleep and activity metrics derived from the Verily study watch data	-	Step count, cadence, activity, sleep measures	Wearable-derived digital biomarkers to complement clinical features. The set of features are the same used in the PD risk model (see Table 9)

As for the feature extraction from wearable time series, the raw time series were summarized into descriptive features using the tsfresh Python library. This time-aggregation step converts continuous signals into compact feature vectors that capture their statistical and temporal characteristics. For each sleep and activity metric, a set of features was automatically computed as summarized in **Table 22**.

Table 22 Descriptive features extracted from wearable time-series signals using the tsfresh library

Feature	Description
Mean	Average signal value over the observation window.
Median	Middle value of the signal.
Variance	Degree of variability in the signal.
Standard deviation	Typical deviation from the mean.
Sum values	Total accumulated signal magnitude over time.
Root mean square	Measure of overall signal intensity.

Absolute energy	Total power or strength of the signal.
Sample entropy	Degree of irregularity and complexity.
Approximate entropy	Predictability of the signal pattern.
Autocorrelation	Similarity between consecutive time points; indicates rhythmicity.
Linear trend	Overall direction or slope of change across time.
Percentiles (25th, 75th)	Distributional spread and skewness of the signal.
Fourier entropy	Complexity of frequency components in the signal.
Repetition ratio	Fraction of repeated values.

6.2.4.3 Outcome definitions

Our progression modelling uses two complementary progression outcome families, clinical defined outcomes and data-driven outcomes.

6.2.4.3.1 Clinically defined outcomes

The progression model was developed and evaluated using clinically established outcome definitions that reflect meaningful changes in motor severity, treatment burden, motor complications, and disease milestone over 12 months of follow-up. **Table 23** lists the outcomes and their definitions.

Table 23 Definitions of the primary and secondary outcomes of the

Primary Outcomes	
a1 – Motor worsening	An increase of more than 3 points in the MDS-UPDRS Part III (motor examination) total score in the ON state.
a2 – Treatment escalation	An increase in the Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD) of more than 10%.
a3 – Composite primary outcome	Defined as the occurrence of either a1 or a2
Secondary Outcomes	
E2-1 – Motor complications	Positive if either: An increase of at least 1 point in any of the MDS-UPDRS Part IV items (4.1 Dyskinesia duration, 4.2 Dyskinesia disability, 4.3 Painful dyskinesia, 4.4 Motor fluctuations), or Amantadine is introduced during the follow-up period.
E2-2 – Disease milestone	Positive if, over ~12 months, any of the following MDS-UPDRS items worsens by ≥ 1 point: Part I – Cognition, Part I – Hallucinations/Psychosis, Part II – Freezing of gait, Part II – Swallowing difficulty
Composite outcome	Defined as the occurrence of any of the above events (a1, a2, a3, E2-1, or E2-2)

Data-driven outcomes (cluster-based)

To complement the predefined clinical endpoints, we derive data-driven progression outcomes from unsupervised subtyping. Two complementary clustering strategies are used; full methodological details follow in the next section.

Approach A — Multi-view consensus clustering: Patients are represented in two views: baseline features and longitudinal change scores (delta = follow-up – baseline). Each view is clustered independently, and labels are fused via a consensus step to yield stable subtypes

Approach B — Time-weighted longitudinal clustering: Baseline and follow-up feature blocks are concatenated into a single fused representation for clustering.

From these subtyping analyses, we define data-driven progression outcomes and subsequently train predictive models to estimate each patient's probability of belonging to higher-risk subtypes from baseline data and wearable features.

6.2.5 Analytical methods

In this section, we present the methodological framework applied for modelling PD progression. Two complementary approaches are described. First, we detail the unsupervised subtyping analyses, which derive data-driven progression outcomes by clustering patients based on baseline characteristics and their ~12-month changes. For this step, we used clinical data only from patients who met the inclusion criteria (section 7.2.1); the resulting training cohort comprised 317 patients. A separate subset of participants (wearable cohort) who had both clinical and wearable data was held out from cluster training and were assigned post hoc to the learned clusters using their clinical data only. Second, we describe the supervised prediction models, which were trained to forecast both the predefined clinical outcomes and the data-driven cluster outcomes. Wearable features (from the Verily Study Watch) were introduced only at this supervised stage to enhance predictive performance without influencing the unsupervised progression subtype discovery.

6.2.5.1 Unsupervised progression subtyping (data-driven outcomes)

6.2.5.1.1 Multi-view clustering for data-driven PD progression subtyping

To derive data-driven subtypes that reflect both patients' initial status and their short-term evolution, we implemented a multi-view clustering framework that treats each participant under two complementary representations. The first view captures the baseline clinical state—including demographics (e.g., age at diagnosis, education, sex, polygenic risk score), motor and non-motor scales (such as MDS-UPDRS domain composites), and vitals. The second view encodes longitudinal change (delta = follow-up – baseline) for the same dynamic variables measured over approximately 12 months. Each view is clustered independently, and the resulting partitions are fused through a co-association–based consensus procedure, ensuring that the final labels represent stable subtypes consistent across both static status and short-term change. The overall pipeline is illustrated in **Figure 24**, which shows the flow from input data, through preprocessing, independent clustering, cross-view feature selection, and consensus labelling, followed by the out-of-sample assignment of the wearable cohort. Conceptually, this framework follows established consensus clustering principles adapted to biomedical stratification and is here tailored to the two-visit design of our cohort (Valmarska et al, 2020).

Figure 24 Overview of the multi-view clustering approach

Pre-processing

Within each view, we address missingness using k-nearest-neighbour imputation ($k=5$) followed by z-score standardization. Because feature sets can change during selection, we re-fit the imputer and scaler whenever the active feature set is updated, preventing leakage and ensuring column alignment. This view-specific preprocessing maintains strict separation of baseline and delta information paths until the late consensus step.

Per-view clustering and model selection

For each view, we apply k-means with k-means++ initialization (25 restarts, fixed seed) and choose the number of clusters by maximizing the silhouette index over $k \in \{2, \dots, 7\}$. This yields two provisional partitions — one informed by baseline status and one by short-term change — without forcing them to coincide a priori.

Cross-view, agreement-seeking feature selection

To obtain subtypes that are coherent across baseline and delta, we run an iterative, agreement-seeking elimination: starting from the full candidate sets, we cluster both views, then align the label IDs between views via the Hungarian algorithm (to resolve label switching), compute ReliefF importances in each view using the aligned labels as the supervisory signal, and drop the globally weakest feature (the lowest ReliefF score across the two views). We then re-cluster both views and quantify baseline–delta agreement with the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI). The loop continues while ARI improves, or until a minimal dimensionality threshold is reached (≥ 5 features per view). This procedure preferentially retains variables that contribute to cross-view-consistent structure, yielding more interpretable and stable consensus subtypes.

Consensus labelling

The final subtype for each subject is produced via a Cluster-based Similarity Partitioning Algorithm (CSPA): we assemble a co-association matrix that counts how often pairs of patients co-cluster across the two views, convert it to a dissimilarity ($1 - \text{co-association}$), apply hierarchical clustering to this matrix, and cut the dendrogram at the target number of clusters (two in our current runs, though it can be selected automatically). This late fusion consolidates shared structure across baseline and delta while smoothing view-specific noise, a well-established benefit of co-association consensus approaches.

Out-of-sample assignment for the wearable cohort

After fixing the consensus labels in the training cohort, Nearest-Centroid classifiers were used in each view to map standardized baseline and delta representations to the consensus subtypes. We then obtain a baseline vote and a delta vote per person and fuse these votes via CSPA to assign a final wearable subtype.

6.2.5.1.2 Longitudinal, time-weighted single-view clustering

Here we complement the multi-view consensus approach by clustering in a single fused space that jointly encodes baseline and follow-up values. Processing steps that are identical to the previous approach (visit selection, feature construction, handling of missingness, z-scaling, and wearable hold-out) are applied in the same way and are not repeated. The overall workflow for this longitudinal clustering is illustrated in **Figure 25** which depicts the preparation of baseline and follow-up blocks, block-wise preprocessing, paired variance filtering, time-weighted fusion, and final k-means clustering, along with the parallel out-of-sample assignment of the wearable cohort.

Figure 25 Overview of the longitudinal clustering approach

For every dynamic clinical variable, we keep a pair of columns, baseline and follow-up (no delta features are created for clustering). The final representation concatenates the two standardized blocks with a time weight λ :

$$X = [\lambda.Z(\text{Baseline}), (1 - \lambda).Z(\text{Follow-up})]$$

with $\lambda = 0.5$ in the main runs.

Before fusion, an unsupervised, label-free filter can prune low-information pairs. For each dynamic feature we compute the pooled variance and iteratively drop the lowest-variance pairs while never going below 6 pairs.

Single clustering step and k selection. On the fused matrix we run k-means and pick $k \in \{2, \dots, 7\}$ by the silhouette index, selecting the k with the highest score. This method deliberately performs one clustering in a time-aware space.

As in the previous approach, the wearable cohort is held out during cluster discovery and then we assign labels using a Nearest-Centroid classifier trained on the fused training space. This ensures wearable data do not influence cluster formation but can still be consistently mapped to the learned subtypes.

This longitudinal variant (i) encodes time explicitly through a weighted (baseline and follow-up) concatenation, (ii) uses a single clustering step with silhouette-based k selection, and (iii) relies on an unsupervised paired variance filter rather than cross-view ReliefF/ARI tuning. It

therefore emphasizes a compact, time-aware latent structure while preserving methodological parity where appropriate (preprocessing, hold-out assignment, and reporting).

In addition to the k selected by silhouette on the fused baseline and follow up space, we performed a clinically guided, top-down split: after identifying an imbalanced $k=2$ solution, we froze one cluster and re-clustered the other one ($k=2$ within-cluster), yielding a 3-cluster partition. This stepwise split preserved the preprocessing/assignment pipeline and improved clinical interpretability without altering the wearable hold-out design.

6.2.5.2 Supervised progression outcome prediction model

Supervised models were trained to predict both clinically defined outcomes (a1–a3, E2-1/E2-2, composite) and the data-driven subtypes. The implemented pipeline is based on a Random Forest classifier with rigorous feature selection and cross-validation.

Clinical and wearable datasets were merged at the patient level. Clinical features comprised demographics, genetics, and baseline variables. Wearable features were extracted and aggregated via tsfresh from the features listed in **Table 9**.

Feature selection was separately performed for clinical and wearable variables before model training using recursive feature elimination with cross-validation (RFECV). A Random Forest with 100 estimators and balanced class weights served as the base estimator. Grouped k -fold CV (by patient ID) ensured leakage-free evaluation. Features were iteratively ranked and pruned, with a minimum of 20 retained and a cap at 200. The final training set combined the clinically selected and top-ranked wearable features, ensuring a balanced and reproducible feature pool for model development and evaluation. The resulting models were tested under several configurations: using only clinical variables (no wearable input) and using combinations of clinical variables and wearable metrics extracted from time windows of 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 days around the baseline visit.

6.2.6 Training versus evaluation

The final predictive models were built using Random Forests (300 estimators, balanced class weights). Stratified 5-fold CV was used to estimate performance. Fold-level metrics included balanced accuracy, precision, and F1, reflecting robustness in the presence of skewed outcome distributions. Confusion matrices were computed per fold and aggregated for interpretability. To handle class imbalance, SMOTE was applied within each training fold (with adaptive $k_neighbors$) to rebalance minority classes.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Participants

A total of 385 patients from the PPMI dataset were included in the analyses after applying the AI-PMP inclusion criteria (confirmed PD diagnosis, age between 40–80 years, Hoehn & Yahr stage 2–3, disease duration 5–10 years, and ON-state MDS-UPDRS III assessments). Each patient contributed a baseline and approximately 12-month follow-up visit.

Figure 26 illustrates the overall distribution of demographic variables in the study cohort. The majority of participants self-identified as White, with only a small proportion reporting Asian, Black, or Native American backgrounds, and a non-negligible number of patients with unspecified race. Regarding ethnicity, most participants did not provide a specification, though subgroups such as Ashkenazi Jewish, Hispanic/Latino, Basque, and African Berber were represented in small numbers. The sex distribution showed a modest male predominance, consistent with the clinical tables, and the age at diagnosis distribution revealed a peak between 55 and 70 years, reflecting the mid-to-late onset typical of Parkinson's disease in the PPMI cohort.

Figure 26 Distribution of demographic variables in the study cohort. The plots show (top left) race, (top right) ethnicity, (bottom left) sex, and (bottom right) age at diagnosis.

The number of patients with and without each outcome is reported in **Table 24-Table 26**, together with baseline demographic and clinical characteristics. These tables provide distributions of sex, age at diagnosis, disease duration, and treatment status. For example, in the a1 outcome group, 34 patients (50.0%) showed progression while 34 (50.0%) did not; similar balanced distributions were observed for a2 and a3. Across outcomes, the mean age at diagnosis ranged from 59 to 61 years, and the mean disease duration was approximately 7 years. The male–female distribution was broadly balanced across outcome strata, though a slightly higher proportion of males was observed in most groups.

Table 24 Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with and without progression according to outcome a1 (MDS-UPDRS III increase > 3 points at 12 months).

Clinical progression outcome (a1)	Positive progression outcome (MDS-UPDRS III increase > 3 points)	Negative progression outcome
Demographics (n, %)		
Patient number	34 (50.0%)	34 (50.0%)
Sex – Male	20 (58.8%)	22 (64.7%)
Sex – Female	14 (41.2%)	12 (35.3%)
Clinical characteristics (Mean ± SD)		
Age at diagnosis	59.03 ± 10.43	60.89 ± 7.05
Disease duration (years)	7.28 ± 1.12	7.26 ± 1.10
Treatment (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline LEDD	802.81 ± 484.31	876.16 ± 597.89
Delta LEDD	50.44 ± 478.55	15.30 ± 404.88
Clinical scores (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline MDS-UPDRS I	8.26 ± 4.67	8.24 ± 3.58

Delta MDS-UPDRS I	1.21 ± 2.54	-0.35 ± 3.57
Baseline MDS-UPDRS II	13.68 ± 6.18	12.88 ± 5.71
Delta MDS-UPDRS II	1.26 ± 4.24	-0.44 ± 5.11
Baseline MDS-UPDRS III	24.41 ± 8.40	27.71 ± 12.13
Delta MDS-UPDRS III	10.41 ± 4.51	-4.38 ± 5.53
Baseline MDS-UPDRS IV	3.59 ± 2.98	3.24 ± 2.59
Delta MDS-UPDRS IV	0.15 ± 2.83	0.85 ± 2.68

Table 25 Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with and without progression according to outcome a2 (LEDD increase > 10%).

Clinical progression outcome (a2)	Positive progression outcome (LEDD increase > 10%)	Negative progression outcome
Demographics (n, %)		
Patient number	28 (41.2%)	40 (58.8%)
Sex – Male (SEX=1)	16 (57.1%)	26 (65.0%)
Sex – Female (SEX=0)	12 (42.9%)	14 (35.0%)
Clinical characteristics (Mean ± SD)		
Age at diagnosis	60.81 ± 9.28	59.36 ± 8.66
Disease duration (years)	7.49 ± 1.06	7.11 ± 1.12
Treatment (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline LEDD	678.67 ± 389.78	952.05 ± 605.44
Delta LEDD	332.61 ± 278.96	-176.95 ± 411.69
Clinical scores (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline MDS-UPDRS I	7.50 ± 3.91	8.78 ± 4.25
Delta MDS-UPDRS I	-0.39 ± 3.49	1.00 ± 2.84
Baseline MDS-UPDRS II	13.18 ± 5.88	13.35 ± 6.02
Delta MDS-UPDRS II	-1.39 ± 4.97	1.68 ± 4.19
Baseline MDS-UPDRS III	29.43 ± 11.92	23.70 ± 8.76
Delta MDS-UPDRS III	1.61 ± 10.38	4.00 ± 7.84
Baseline MDS-UPDRS IV	3.43 ± 3.01	3.40 ± 2.64
Delta MDS-UPDRS IV	0.96 ± 2.78	0.17 ± 2.73

Table 26 Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with and without progression according to outcome a3 (composite of a1 or a2).

Clinical progression outcome (a3)	Positive progression outcome (MDS-UPDRS III increase > 3 points or LEDD increase > 10%)	Negative progression outcome
Demographics (n, %)		

Patient number	50 (73.5%)	18 (26.5%)
Sex – Male (SEX=1)	29 (58.0%)	13 (72.2%)
Sex – Female (SEX=0)	21 (42.0%)	5 (27.8%)
Clinical characteristics (Mean ± SD)		
Age at diagnosis	59.45 ± 9.41	61.37 ± 7.26
Disease duration (years)	7.38 ± 1.07	6.95 ± 1.16
Treatment (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline LEDD	794.95 ± 466.44	963.19 ± 710.97
Delta LEDD	115.51 ± 416.67	-196.69 ± 433.24
Clinical scores (Mean ± SD)		
Baseline MDS-UPDRS I	8.16 ± 4.39	8.50 ± 3.42
Delta MDS-UPDRS I	0.42 ± 3.15	0.44 ± 3.33
Baseline MDS-UPDRS II	13.68 ± 5.93	12.17 ± 5.92
Delta MDS-UPDRS II	0.18 ± 4.79	1.06 ± 4.68
Baseline MDS-UPDRS III	27.08 ± 10.46	23.22 ± 10.31
Delta MDS-UPDRS III	5.24 ± 9.24	-3.17 ± 4.11
Baseline MDS-UPDRS IV	3.44 ± 2.89	3.33 ± 2.52
Delta MDS-UPDRS IV	0.48 ± 2.95	0.56 ± 2.20

For the supervised analyses, we conducted the same baseline characteristic comparisons across all outcomes. To reduce redundancy and space, only the tables corresponding to the primary outcomes (a1, a2, a3) are presented here, while the detailed analysis for the data-driven outcomes derived from the clustering approach is provided in a later section.

6.3.2 Model development

6.3.2.1 Unsupervised learning models

Longitudinal and multi-view subtyping was performed on $n = 317$ patients who had both baseline (BL) and ~12-month follow-up (FU) measurements across dynamic clinical domains (motor: MDS-UPDRS II–IV totals, PIGD, Tremor; stage NHY; treatment LEDD; non-motor: NP1 domains incl. apathy, cognition, fatigue, hallucinations, pain; sleepiness ESS, RBD (RBDSQ); autonomic burden SCOPA-AUT; impulse control (QUIP); and orthostatic systolic drop). Missing values were handled as described in section 7.2.3, then each feature was z-scored within visit.

6.3.2.1.1 Multi view clustering results

This clustering approach was implemented to capture the absolute severity and change without forcing a single representation. Thus, clustering was performed independently in each view and combined via a consensus step. The final solution used $k=2$ clusters, yielding markedly distinct phenotypes with sizes of 86 and 231 individuals, respectively.

As shown in **Figure 27**, cluster 1 represents patients with a generally more severe disease presentation at baseline. They show greater motor impairment and disability, reflected by higher MDS-UPDRS motor scores and greater postural instability, as well as stronger non-motor involvement, including autonomic symptoms, daytime sleepiness, REM sleep behaviour disorder, apathy, fatigue, and pain. These patients also required higher dopaminergic medication doses. In contrast, cluster 2 includes patients with milder baseline motor and non-

motor symptoms, and relatively preserved cognitive function, as evidenced by higher MoCA scores (where higher values denote better cognitive performance). It is worth mentioning that cluster 2 includes the majority of patients (n = 231), its larger size suggests greater heterogeneity, potentially including individuals with varying degrees of motor and non-motor symptom burden within the milder disease spectrum.

Figure 27 Baseline profile by cluster (multi-view clustering). Heatmap shows standardized means (annotations are raw baseline means)

As for the 12-month change (delta) profiles (**Figure 28**), the trajectories over one year differ by domain and, in several respects:

- **Medication escalation:** Cluster 2, which included most patients, showed a greater increase in levodopa equivalent daily dose, indicating more frequent treatment escalation despite having milder symptoms at baseline.
- **Motor progression:** Both clusters experienced almost no motor worsening over one year. Cluster 1 showed slightly greater overall deterioration in motor function (MDS-UPDRS Part III total score), the activities-of-daily-living score (MDS-UPDRS Part II), and the postural instability and gait difficulty (PIGD) subscore. In contrast, cluster 2 exhibited a more specific pattern, with greater worsening in bradykinesia but mild improvement in tremor. Also, motor complication (MDS-UPDRS IV) increased mainly in cluster 2.
- **Autonomic & sleep:** Autonomic dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT) worsened in cluster 2 but improved slightly in cluster 1, suggesting a “catch-up” effect in the previously less affected group. Daytime sleepiness (ESS) rose slightly in both clusters, while REM sleep behaviour disorder symptoms (RBDSQ) increased more in cluster 1.
- **Non-motor symptoms and cognition:** Cluster 2 showed greater worsening in pain and fatigue sub-scores, whereas Cluster 1 remained largely stable or slightly improved. Cognitive performance (MoCA) declined slightly in both clusters, with a larger decrease in Cluster 1.

Figure 28 One-year delta profile by cluster (multi-view clustering).

Clinical interpretation of clustered progression subtypes:

- **Cluster 1 (n=86):** High baseline burden across motor and non-motor domains; over 12 months shows modest additional motor worsening, more REM-sleep behavior burden, but relative stability/improvement in several non-motor items and greater impairment in cognitive performance.
- **Cluster 2 (n=231):** Milder baseline but greater medication escalation, worse autonomic progression, bradykinesia increase, higher rise in NP1 totals, and more growth in complications alongside better tremor improvement.

6.3.2.1.2 Longitudinal clustering results

We clustered the fused representations with $k = 2$ (chosen for clinical interpretability and confirmed by stable solutions across random initializations). Results were consistent when repeating the analysis with different seeds. The resulting clusters were 98 patients in Cluster 0 and 219 in Cluster 1.

Baseline phenotype (Figure 29): Cluster 0 exhibits a more severe baseline burden across most domains. Patients in cluster 0 exhibit greater motor impairment, reflected by higher MDS-UPDRS III, II, and PIGD scores. They also show more pronounced non-motor symptoms, including increased daytime sleepiness, autonomic dysfunction, and REM sleep behavior disorder, together with higher impulsivity (QUIP). Treatment exposure was greater in this group, with higher baseline levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD), consistent with more advanced disease management needs. Cognitive performance (MoCA) was lower in Cluster 0, indicating greater cognitive impairment aligned with the overall severity profile.

Figure 29 Baseline profile by cluster (longitudinal clustering, k=2).

12-month change (Figure 30): The two clusters showed distinct trajectories over one year.

- **Medication escalation:** Cluster 0 experienced a much larger increase in levodopa equivalent daily dose than cluster 1.
- **Motor progression:** Cluster 0 patients worsened across all core motor domains, with greater increases in MDS-UPDRS Part III (motor examination), Part II (activities of daily living), and the postural instability and gait difficulty (PIGD) subscore. In contrast, Cluster 1 remained largely stable over the same period. Cluster 0 showed a small reduction in MDS-UPDRS Part IV (-1.29), whereas cluster 1 remained stable, consistent with its lower treatment need and milder overall course.
- **Tremor:** Cluster 1 showed a modest improvement in tremor severity, while cluster 0 remained essentially unchanged.
- **Sleep and autonomic function:** Daytime sleepiness (ESS) increased slightly in Cluster 0 but remained stable in cluster 1. Autonomic symptoms, captured by the SCOPA-AUT scale, worsened in both groups.

Figure 30 One-year delta profile by cluster (longitudinal clustering, k=2).

Clinical interpretation of clustered progression subtypes:

- Cluster 0 (n=98): Characterized by higher baseline severity and faster 12-month worsening, with greater escalation of medication dose and broader deterioration across motor and several non-motor domains.
- Cluster 1 (n=219): represents a milder baseline profile with relative longitudinal stability, with small changes overall and improvement in tremor.

Three-cluster extension (stepwise split)

Following the initial two-cluster solution derived from the fused (baseline + follow-up) clinical representation, our clinical partners suggested that one cluster (cluster 1) appeared heterogeneous. Thus, we further subdivided cluster 1 into two sub-clusters using the same longitudinal clustering approach (k = 2; K-means), while keeping the composition of cluster 0 fixed. Cluster counts are Cluster 0: n=98; Cluster 1: n=110; Cluster 2: n=109.

As shown in the baseline heatmap (**Figure 31**), Cluster 0 has the highest motor and non-motor burden, with greater impairment in the MDS-UPDRS Part III motor examination, postural instability and gait difficulty (PIGD), and bradykinesia scores. It also shows higher non-motor symptom load, including increased daytime sleepiness (ESS), autonomic dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT), and REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBDSQ). Cluster 1 presents moderate motor severity, with noticeable tremor and moderate non-motor scores. Cluster 2 has the lowest motor and non-motor burden, showing better overall functional status and the highest Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) scores, indicating preserved cognitive function.

Figure 31 Baseline profile by cluster (longitudinal clustering, k=3).

Longitudinal changes summarized in the delta heatmap (**Figure 32**) show that Cluster 0 displays clear worsening across almost all domains, including motor symptoms, activities of daily living, and medication dosage, reflecting a fast-progressing subtype. Cluster 1 remains largely stable over the 12-month period, with minimal or even slight improvements in several measures. Cluster 2 shows only modest changes, limited to a few non-motor and treatment-related scales, such as autonomic dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT) and therapy-related complications (MDS-UPDRS IV). **Table 27** presents the three-cluster solution obtained from the longitudinal clinical representation, summarizing the corresponding Parkinson’s disease subtypes, their main baseline characteristics, 12-month progression patterns, and clinical interpretations.

Figure 32 One-year delta profile by cluster (longitudinal clustering, k=3).

Table 27 Clinical interpretation of baseline and 12-month progression profiles across the three longitudinal clusters

Cluster	Baseline profile	Longitudinal change	Clinical interpretation
0	Highest baseline motor and non-motor burden. Highest LEDD value.	Marked worsening across nearly all domains.	Advanced multi-system PD with rapid progression and high dopaminergic demand.
1	Moderate baseline severity with relatively higher TREMOR score, lower PIGD and SCOPA_AUT, and lowest LEDD value.	Stable over 12 months with minimal or slightly improved scores; small LEDD increase.	Tremor-dominant, slow-progressing phenotype with mild motor and non-motor change.
2	Lowest overall motor and non-motor scores; best cognitive performance (MCATOT highest); moderate LEDD value.	Mild, selective progression mainly in SCOPA_AUT, UPDRS-IV total, and LEDD value.	Mild, cognitively preserved group

6.3.2.2 Supervised model (outcome prediction)

We developed supervised classification models to predict both the primary and secondary clinically defined outcomes and, in separate analyses, the data-driven subtypes obtained from the unsupervised approaches (longitudinal fusion and multi-view consensus).

For each outcome, the cohort described in Section 7.3.1 was used. The distribution of event and non-event cases for the primary outcomes (a1–a3) is reported in **Table 24–Table 26**, and these same proportions were preserved across the folds of cross-validation. The identical pipeline was then re-run with cluster membership as the target in order to evaluate predictability of the data-driven subtypes.

Input features included the clinical variables listed in **Table 21** (demographics, motor and non-motor assessments, treatment exposure, and composite scores) together with TSFRESH-

aggregated wearable metrics capturing cadence, slowness of movement, step counts (summary and hourly), physical activity levels, and sleep. Models were trained in two configurations: (i) clinical features only, and (ii) combined clinical and wearable features, enabling us to quantify the incremental value of wearables.

To reduce dimensionality, a feature selection procedure was applied to the full features set. We applied Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV) using a Random Forest base estimator. Features were retained based on their contribution to predictive performance.

For each target, a Random Forest classifier was trained using stratified cross-validation. At each fold, performance metrics were recorded, including balanced accuracy (primary metric), precision (macro-averaged), and F1 score (macro-averaged). Fold-specific confusion matrices were aggregated to provide an overall view of classification performance across the cohort.

We evaluated the models for potential biases using the Fairlearn framework. Predictions were stratified by sex, race, education level, and age at diagnosis. For each subgroup, we reported balanced accuracy. We also calculated fairness indicators such as demographic parity and equalized odds differences and ratios.

6.3.3 Model specification

The supervised models were implemented in Python 3.12 with preprocessing handled inside a leakage-safe pipeline. Clinical and wearable features were imputed, and wearable. Class imbalance was addressed with SMOTE applied within each training fold, and performance was evaluated through five-fold stratified cross-validation. Feature selection was performed using RFECV. Outputs generated for each analysis included per-fold performance metrics, aggregated confusion matrices, feature importance rankings, and fairness assessments stratified by sex, race, education, and age at diagnosis. All scripts rely on widely available open-source libraries (scikit-learn, imbalanced-learn, seaborn, matplotlib, scipy, and fairlearn). Upon completion of the analysis, the results will be published along with the developed source code after removing any identifying information of the dataset used.

6.3.4 Model performance

For each outcome, models were trained and evaluated under multiple configurations: clinical-only and clinical with wearable features extracted from different windows centred on baseline.

6.3.4.1 Clinically defined outcomes

6.3.4.1.1 Outcome a1 – Motor worsening

The supervised model achieved moderate predictive performance when combining clinical and wearable features, with results varying across the wearable data aggregation intervals (**Table 28**; **Figure 33**). The clinical-only configuration reached a mean balanced accuracy of 0.51. Adding wearable features improved performance, peaking at 20 days around baseline (0.8 balanced accuracy). Other window lengths yielded slightly lower but still comparable accuracies.

Figure 33 Balanced accuracy for predicting outcome a1 using clinical data only and combination of clinical data and aggregated wearable metrics over various time windows centred around the clinical assessment.

Table 28 Performance metrics for predicting progression outcome a1 using clinical data only and combination of clinical data and aggregated wearable metrics over various time windows centred around the clinical assessment

Window	Balanced Accuracy (mean ± SD)	Precision (mean)	F1 Score (mean)
Clinical only	0.51 ± 0.1	0.51	0.49
20 days	0.8 ± 0.17	0.82	0.80
40 days	0.74 ± 0.07	0.8	0.73
60 days	0.71 ± 0.15	0.72	0.7
80 days	0.68 ± 0.10	0.7	0.66
100 days	0.62 ± 0.14	0.63	0.61

The most influential predictors included both wearable-derived features such as walking activity trends (e.g., step count and walking duration linear trends) and movement regularity measures (e.g., acceleration autocorrelation) as well as key clinical variables such as baseline tremor score, autonomic and sleep dysfunction scores (SCOPA-AUT, RBDSQ, ESS), motor and daily-living scores (MDS-UPDRS Parts II–III), and polygenic risk score (PRS). Feature importances are shown for the 60-day window configuration (**Figure 34**).

Figure 34 Top-20 predictors ranked by mean Random Forest importance across five cross-validation folds for outcome a1 (60 day window).

Fairness analysis: Performance differed modestly across sex and age, with higher balanced accuracy observed in males (0.76) compared to females (0.60), and best results among patients diagnosed between 60–70 years (0.73). Smaller subgroups (e.g., <40 years, >80 years, or minority racial categories) displayed unstable results due to very low sample counts. Overall, performance was consistent for the majority subgroup (White, ~0.70 balanced accuracy) (**Table 29**). Additional fairness indicators confirmed these findings: demographic parity and equalized odds values suggested moderate disparities by race and age at diagnosis, while differences by sex and education were smaller (**Table 30**). However, these metrics are sensitive to subgroup size, and results from very small categories are not very reliable.

Table 29 Balanced accuracy stratified by sex, race, education, and age for outcome a1 prediction

Attribute	Subgroup	Sample count	Balanced accuracy
Sex	Female	25	0.60
	Male	41	0.76
Race	White	60	0.7
	Asian	3	0.5
	Black	2	1
	Am. Indian/Alaska N.	1	0
Education	12–16 y	19	0.67
	16–20 y	42	0.64
	20+ y	5	1

Age	<40	3	0.67
	40–50	5	0.42
	50–60	16	0.62
	60–70	37	0.73
	70–80	4	1
	80+	1	0

Table 30 Fairness metrics (demographic parity and equalized odds) for outcome a1 prediction

Metric	Sex	Race	Education	Age
Demographic Parity (Difference)	0.02	0.5	0.34	0.75
Demographic Parity (Ratio)	0.95	0	0.44	0
Equalized Odds (Difference)	0.2	1	0.5	1
Equalized Odds (Ratio)	0.68	0	0	0
Overall Balanced Accuracy	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7

6.3.4.1.2 Model performance across the remaining clinically defined outcomes.

The supervised models achieved moderate to good predictive performance across all clinically defined AI-PMP outcomes (a1, a2, a3, E2-1, E2-2), with balanced accuracy ranging from approximately 0.60 to 0.80 depending on the outcome and wearable window. Performance improved consistently when wearable features were included alongside clinical variables. Overall, these findings confirm that integrating wearable features enhances model discrimination relative to clinical-only models, while the specific time window around clinical visits influences predictive accuracy (**Table 31**).

Table 31 Performance metrics for predicting all clinically defined progression outcomes using clinical data only and combination of clinical data and aggregated wearable metrics over various time windows centred around the clinical assessment

Outcome	Window (days)	Balanced Accuracy (mean \pm SD)	Precision (mean)	F1 Score (mean)
a1 – Motor worsening	Clinical only	0.51 \pm 0.1	0.51	0.50
	20	0.80 \pm 0.17	0.82	0.80
	40	0.74 \pm 0.7	0.8	0.73
	60	0.71 \pm 0.15	0.72	0.7
	80	0.68 \pm 0.102	0.7	0.66
	100	0.62 \pm 0.14	0.63	0.61
a2 – LEDD increase	Clinical only	0.53 \pm 0.10	0.51	0.51
	20	0.66 \pm 0.12	0.7	0.64
	40	0.63 \pm 0.2	0.60	0.62
	60	0.6 \pm 0.16	0.58	0.57
	80	0.62 \pm 0.13	0.62	0.6

	100	0.62 ± 0.18	0.62	0.62
a3 – Composite outcome	Clinical only	0.51 ± 0.09	0.52	0.48
	20	0.64 ± 0.11	0.66	0.63
	40	0.66 ± 0.07	0.75	0.64
	60	0.67 ± 0.09	0.77	0.68
	80	0.66 ± 0.11	0.75	0.67
	100	0.64 ± 0.18	0.62	0.62
E2-1 – Motor complications	Clinical only	0.55 ± 0.11	0.53	0.52
	20	0.61 ± 0.24	0.60	0.6
	40	0.76 ± 0.12	0.83	0.75
	60	0.68 ± 0.14	0.71	0.66
	80	0.74 ± 0.08	0.74	0.73
	100	0.77 ± 0.10	0.84	0.76
E2-2 – Disease milestone	Clinical only	0.6 ± 0.084	0.57	0.58
	20	0.76 ± 0.14	0.79	0.75
	40	0.59 ± 0.13	0.61	0.58
	60	0.62 ± 0.15	0.67	0.61
	80	0.62 ± 0.13	0.65	0.60
	100	0.67 ± 0.04	0.7	0.67

6.3.4.2 Data driven outcomes

This section presents the performance results for predicting the two types of data-driven (cluster-based) outcomes: longitudinal clusters and multi-view clusters. The derivation of these cluster-based progression subtypes is described in Section 6.3.2.1, and the results here focus on evaluating how accurately each subtype can be predicted from baseline clinical features, with or without wearable-derived metrics.

6.3.4.2.1 Longitudinal clustering (K=2)

The supervised classifier achieved high predictive accuracy in distinguishing the longitudinal clusters. Cross-validation yielded a mean balanced accuracy of 0.895 ± 0.036 , precision of 0.899 ± 0.040 , and F1 score of 0.894 ± 0.035 . This is higher than the results for the predefined clinical outcomes, indicating that the longitudinal clusters are more separable. **Table 32** and **Table 33** show the fairness assessment. They demonstrate that subgroup performance remained consistently high, although some subgroup sizes were very small ($n \leq 3$). And while demographic parity and equalized odds metrics showed variability across protected attributes, these results should be interpreted with caution given the limited sample size in certain categories.

Table 32 Balanced accuracy stratified by sex, race, education, and age for the longitudinal results

Attribute	Subgroup	Sample count	Balanced accuracy
Sex	Female	25	0.92
	Male	41	0.90
Race	White	60	0.90

	Asian	3	1.00
	Black	2	1.00
	Am. Indian/Alaska Native	1	1.00
Education	12–16 y	19	0.89
	16–20 y	42	0.93
	20+ y	5	0.67
Age	<40	3	1.00
	40–50	5	1.00
	50–60	16	0.95
	60–70	37	0.84
	70–80	4	1.00
	80+	1	1.00

Table 33 Fairness metrics (demographic parity and equalized odds) for the longitudinal outcome

Metric	Sex	Race	Education	Age
Demographic Parity (Diff.)	0.20	0.57	0.37	0.80
Demographic Parity (Ratio)	0.70	0.43	0.54	0.20
Equalized Odds (Diff.)	0.10	0.15	0.67	0.17
Equalized Odds (Ratio)	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.00
Overall Balanced Accuracy	0.90	0.89	0.89	0.89

6.3.4.2.2 Longitudinal clustering (K=3)

In the three-cluster configuration, model performance improved with the inclusion of wearable features across multiple time windows (**Table 34**; **Figure 35**). The clinical-only setup achieved a balanced accuracy of 0.71 ± 0.15 , while wearable-enhanced models reached up to 0.81 ± 0.14 (80 days window), with precision ≈ 0.84 and F1 ≈ 0.81 . These results confirm good discriminative ability in predicting cluster membership from baseline and wearable data.

Feature importance analysis revealed that both clinical and wearable attributes contributed strongly. The most influential predictors included wearable-derived sleep metrics (REM latency and duration), gait and activity regularity measures (e.g., walking trend correlations, RMS autocorrelation), and clinical variables such as fatigue, motor and non-motor scores, and LEDD dosage (**Figure 36**).

Table 34 Cross-validation performance metrics for the longitudinal results (K=3) Performance metrics for predicting the longitudinal outcome using clinical data only and combination of clinical data and aggregated wearable metrics over various time windows centred around the clinical assessment

Window (days)	Balanced Accuracy (mean \pm SD)	Precision (mean)	F1 Score (mean)
Clinical only	0.71 ± 0.15	0.77	0.70
20	0.75 ± 0.14	0.68	0.70
40	0.76 ± 0.11	0.79	0.76

60	0.78 ± 0.08	0.84	0.78
80	0.81 ± 0.14	0.84	0.81
100	0.79 ± 0.11	0.82	0.79

Figure 35 Balanced accuracy for predicting longitudinal cluster membership ($k = 3$) using clinical data only and using a combination of clinical data and wearable-derived metrics aggregated over different time windows centred around the baseline clinical assessment.

Figure 36 Top-20 predictors ranked by mean Random Forest importance across five cross-validation folds for the longitudinal clustering ($k=3$).

6.3.4.2.3 Multi-view clustering

The supervised model trained to predict multi-view cluster membership achieved consistently high performance across wearable data windows (**Table 35; Figure 37**). The clinical-only model reached a balanced accuracy of 0.84 ± 0.09 , precision of 0.84, and F1 score of 0.84, while the inclusion of wearable features further improved classification accuracy. The best configuration (± 40 days window) achieved a balanced accuracy of 0.9 ± 0.13 , precision 0.9, and F1 score 0.9, confirming strong discriminative power between the identified multi-view subtypes. The fairness results are generally the same in both multi-view and longitudinal clustering. Both achieve high subgroup balanced accuracy, show the same stronger groups (e.g., White, 60–70), and the same instability in very small subgroups.

Table 35 Performance metrics for predicting the multi view outcome using clinical data only and combination of clinical data and aggregated wearable metrics over various time windows centred around the clinical assessment

Window (days)	Balanced Accuracy (mean \pm SD)	Precision (mean)	F1 Score (mean)
Clinical only	0.84 ± 0.09	0.84	0.84
20	0.89 ± 0.14	0.90	0.90
40	0.9 ± 0.13	0.90	0.90
60	0.86 ± 0.10	0.87	0.86
80	0.86 ± 0.15	0.87	0.86
100	0.86 ± 0.11	0.88	0.86

Figure 37 Balanced accuracy for predicting multi-view cluster membership ($k = 2$) using clinical data only and using a combination of clinical data and wearable-derived metrics aggregated over different time windows centred around the baseline clinical assessment.

6.4 Methods for long-term PD progression modelling using clinical snapshots and deep learning

While the clustering approaches discussed above show promising results, we also aimed to jointly characterize the subtypes of individual disease trajectories and predict future MDS-UPDRS scores. Knowledge of both is considered crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the patient's clinical status and disease progression. More specifically, the identification of the progression subtype, derived from diverse clinical features, e.g., demographics, motor assessment, MoCA score, medication, allows for a complete view of the disease's state and its evolution, while the MDS-UPDRS I-III scores provide a robust, quantitative measure of the patient's motor and non-motor symptoms, enabling clinicians to monitor disease progression and treatment response over time.

The proposed end-to-end methodology analyses PD progression by first preprocessing longitudinal clinical data from PD patients and healthy controls. An unsupervised LSTM-autoencoder generates participant-level embeddings, which are clustered to identify PD progression subtypes (rapid, moderate, slow), with healthy controls forming a separate cluster. Next, the PDualNet model is introduced. It trains an autoencoder to learn single-visit embeddings (SiVE), which are then fed into a Transformer encoder (Vaswani et al., 2018) to model each patient's overall disease-state representation (DiSE). These representations drive two decoders: one predicting progression subtype (classification) and the other forecasting future MDS-UPDRS I-III scores (regression). The framework is trained in three phases to jointly optimize both tasks. The overview of the proposed methodology is illustrated in **Figure 38**, while a detailed description of each step is provided in the following subsections.

Figure 38 Overview of the proposed methodology: Starting with data extraction and preprocessing, followed by the identification of the PD progression subtypes, and finally the modelling and joint prediction of the Parkinson's Disease Progression & Severity, using the PDualNet framework

6.4.1 Dataset description

In this work, two datasets were considered, the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) (Marek et al., 2018) used for both training and validation and the Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program (PDBP) (Ofori et al., 2015) used as external validation for the proposed methodology, both extracted from the AMP-PDRD Knowledge Platform. PPMI is a large, well-characterized cohort of thousands of individuals, with and without Parkinson's Disease, aiming to identify critically needed biological markers of Parkinson's onset and progression. In our analysis, after preprocessing, we considered 579 participants, comprising of (N= 391) PD patients (34% Male - 66% Female) and (N= 188) healthy controls (HC)(35.6% Male - 64.4%Female). We extracted their longitudinal data, accounting for 89 clinical features, across the following categories:

- **Demographics:** Including age at BL, sex, race and years of education.
- **Patient History:** Including if the participant has a family member (e.g. parent or other relative) with PD.
- **MDS-UPDRS I:** The MDS-UPDRS Part I score, consisting of 13 features, assessing non-motor aspects of daily living.
- **MDS-UPDRS II:** The MDS-UPDRS Part II score, including 13 features, considering motor aspects of experiences in daily living.
- **MDS-UPDRS III:** The MDS-UPDRS Part III score, containing 18 distinct features, which is the clinically assessed motor examination.
- **Schwab and England ADL:** The Schwab and England ADL score (Siderowf, 2010), which is a 100-point scale that addresses the capabilities of people with impaired mobility.
- **MoCA:** The Montreal Cognitive Assessment score (Nasreddine, 2005), which is designed as a rapid screening instrument for mild cognitive dysfunction. We utilize five relevant features, plus the total score.
- **UPSIT:** The University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) booklet (Doty et al., 1989), including 4 features (i.e. 4 different 10-page booklets), responsible for assessing the olfactory function of the participants.
- **ESS:** The Epworth Sleepiness Scale (Johns, 1991), including eight features, responsible for assessing a person's average sleep propensity, or how likely they are to fall asleep in various situations
- **Medication:** Includes three features, namely, whether the participants is on Levodopa, Dopamine Agonist or other PD medication.

The number of visits taken into account for the case of the PPMI cohort, ranges from 1 (BL) to 13 (V_{12}), positioned at fixed 6-month intervals. Intermediate 3-month visits were excluded due to a higher proportion of missing values and their absence in the PDBP cohort. On the other hand, regarding the PDBP cohort, we preserved 490 participants, consisting of (N= 280) PD patients (57.9 % Male - 42.1 % Female) and (N= 210) healthy controls (HC) (46.7 % Male - 53.3 %). For comparison purposes, the feature set was kept consistent with the PPMI cohort (89 features), and the number of available extracted visits ranges from 1 (BL) to 11 (V_{10}), all spaced at 6-month intervals.

6.4.2 Pre-processing

Initially, for each participant p , its longitudinal data are extracted. This includes demographic information, patient history, and clinical features, such as MDS-UPDRS I-III score, MoCA assessment, UPSIT booklet, Schwab and England ADL (Activities of Daily Living) scale, EPWORTH Sleepiness Scale (ESS), and medication information, analytically described in future sections. These data are organized in visits $\{BL, V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$, where BL is the Baseline visit and V_n is the last available visit of each patient. The visits are time-ordered, and quantified in 6-month intervals, starting from BL . As a result, for each patient, the longitudinal data of each participant p are represented as $L_p = \{x_{BL}, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, where x_i is the feature vector of the i^{th} visit.

While processing the data, feature selection is simultaneously being performed, as well as partial outlier detection and removal. In terms of the feature selection, there is a notable trade-off between the number of clinically significant features we want to include and the number of participants that have at least a single visit recording per feature. Thus, features that are available in very few participants are excluded from the analysis. Likewise, participants with sparse feature data are removed, thereby maximizing the cohort size with sufficient observations across the selected features. For the resulting sub-set N_f of preserved participants P and features F , the last step consists of data imputation as many participants contain feature vectors with missing values. This is performed, using standard imputation

techniques, including constant imputation (for static features, e.g. age, sex) and interpolation (for time-varying features, e.g., MDS-UPDRS scores), using least squares regression.

6.4.3 Prediction models

Progression Subtypes Extraction and outlier removal

After completing the data preprocessing step, we proceed with the identification of the PD progression subtypes. We first generate a single-vector representation of each participant's extracted data, irrespective of the number of available visits. For this purpose, as proposed in similar works (Su et al., 2024) an LSTM-based autoencoder is employed, which additionally serves the purpose of dimensionality reduction. The proposed autoencoder is trained using the reconstruction loss in Eq. (1).

$$\mathcal{L}_{rec}(p) = \|L_p - \hat{L}_p\|_2^2 = \frac{1}{|L_p|} \sum_{n=BL, \dots, V_n} \|x_n - \hat{x}_n\|_2^2, \forall p \in P \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, the trained autoencoder is utilized for outlier detection and removal. More specifically, we define a threshold \mathcal{L}_{max} for the reconstruction loss. Then for each participant's p longitudinal trajectory, we calculate its reconstruction loss $\mathcal{L}_{rec}(p)$, and if

$\mathcal{L}_{rec}(p) > \mathcal{L}_{max}$, then p is removed from the analysis. The intuition behind this is that the autoencoder learns the underlying distribution of the data points in the dataset, and thus, data points with significant difference from the norm, have a high reconstruction loss, indicating that they are outliers.

Moving forward, by preserving only the encoder part of the trained autoencoder, we extract longitudinal embeddings of each participant. Finally, using the embeddings corresponding to PD patients, we employ unsupervised clustering, namely K-Means, which uncovers the three progression subtypes.

PDualNet Model

The extracted progression subtypes are used as labels for the next phase of the methodology, which is the design and training of the model. PDualNet consists of the following core components:

- **SiVE Autoencoder:** This network, illustrated in **Figure 39** (right), aims to capture the Single-Visit Embeddings (SiVE) z_i of each visit's feature vector x_i . It is constructed using a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) encoder and decoder. The latter is omitted after pre-training, whereas the former serves as the embedding module for the Transformer encoder. The rationale behind the use of this pre-trained module, as emerged from similar works (Shang et al, 2019), lies in providing rich and meaningful initial representation of each visit data. Another significant advantage of this modelling approach is the improved performance in terms of stability and training convergence (Yao et al., 2023), especially when the available data is limited.
- **DiSE Transformer-Encoder:** A Transformer-based encoder that transforms longitudinal clinical data into informative unique Disease-State embeddings (DiSE). Using representation learning, this module contributes to generalization between tasks through shared temporal dynamics, allowing both classification and regression to be beneficial. The input to this module is the sequence of time-ordered SiVE embeddings for a single patient along with a CLS token at the beginning. The latter is a special token (Devlin et al., 2018), often used in Transformer-based architectures, placed always at the beginning of the input and is responsible for capturing the representation

of the input sequence. The resulting embedding vector dp for each participant p is then provided as input to the two subsequent decoders.

- **Subtype Decoder:** A MLP decoder that generates an unnormalized logits vector $s=[s_r, s_m, s_s, s_{HC}]$, assigning a single logit for each of the four classes: rapid, moderate, slow and HC respectively. The $arg\max_j s$ represents the predicted progression subtype of each participant, given their DiSE representation.
- **MDS-UPDRS Decoder:** A framework consisting of a Transformer decoder, followed by a MLP is responsible for forecasting the future MDS-UPDRS I - III scores of each participant, given their DiSE representation and the previously computed MDS-UPDRS scores. It operates in an autoregressive manner: the MLP's output, namely, a 3-d vector $u=[u_I, u_{II}, u_{III}]$ of the predicted scores from the previous time-step is passed through an embedding module and then used as input to the Transformer decoder, together with the DiSE representation.

The detailed architecture of PDualNet is illustrated in **Figure 40**.

Figure 39 (left) Clustering of PD progression subtypes through longitudinal embedding extraction (right) Single-Visit Embedding (SiVE) space.

Figure 40 PDualNet architecture

6.5 Results (PDualNet approach)

Results demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed methodology are presented. We first present the clustering results and evaluate the performance of the PDualNet model. The model is assessed across both the PPMI and PDBP cohorts for each of the two tasks. Additionally, we compare the performance of PDualNet with two baseline models to highlight its advantages.

6.5.1 Imputation

For handling missing values, our approach combines constant imputation and linear regression, offering a balance between interpretability, computational efficiency, and temporal consistency. To evaluate our choice, we further conducted an analysis comparing the original imputation pipeline with two widely used alternative strategies, i.e. KNN imputation (Troyanskaya et al., 2001) and Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) (van Buuren et al. 2011). More specifically, we compared the mean and std. deviation of each feature, before and after each imputation technique was applied and report their respective differences in **Table 36**. Although all methods appear to preserve the initial feature distributions, we utilized the aforementioned imputation approach, as it achieves the lowest deviation across all three methods.

Table 36 Comparison of imputation strategies across PD and HC cohorts in PPMI dataset. Each value represents the mean absolute distributional shift between the original (non-imputed) and imputed feature distributions, computed for the mean, standard deviation, and average z-score distance. Lower values indicate smaller distortion of the underlying data statistics.

abs. dist. Shift	PD cohort			HC cohort		
	PDualNet	kNN	MICE	PDualNet	kNN	MICE
Mean	0.011	0.013	0.025	0.012	0.018	0.026
std	0.013	0.023	0.016	0.032	0.040	0.041
Z-score	0.010	0.014	0.024	0.022	0.039	0.052

Clustering

The clustering procedure is performed on the PPMI cohort and the trained model (i.e., LSTM Autoencoder), as well as the determined cluster centroids are used to extract the labels for the PDBP cohort (external validation set).

The LSTM Autoencoder, consisting of a single Layer in both the encoder and decoder part, with a hidden dimension (i.e., the embedding dimension) of 32, is trained for (N= 70) epochs, using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-3} .

Upon completion of the training, K-Means clustering is performed for extracting the progression subtypes. For determining the number of clusters k , we examined the alternatives $k=2$ and $k=3$, as they represent the common practice in the latest literature (Su et al. 2024, Hähnel et al. 2024). We assessed their respective clustering performance using the silhouette score, the Davies-Bouldin index, and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), as summarized in **Table 37**. Since $k=3$ produced the best results in two of the three cases and is also the most prevalent choice in related studies, we adopted $k=3$ for subsequent analysis.

Table 37 Comparison of AIC, Silhouette score and Davies-Bouldin index for the two dominant choices ($k = 2$ and $k = 3$) for the number of progression subtypes.

N clusters	AIC (↓)	Silhouette (↑)	Davies-Bouldin index (↓)
$k = 2$	-111698.99	0.294	1.43
$k = 3$	-115456.17	0.288	1.36

Specifically, for the PPMI cohort, the clustering unveiled (N= 145) rapid, (N= 152) moderate and (N=94) slow progression patients. The clustering result can be found in **Figure 41** illustrating the 3 clusters (plus the HC participants). For visualization purposes, the projected

2D longitudinal embedding space is derived using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Karl Pearson, 1901) on the latent representations of the participants.

With respect to the PDBP cohort, using the trained LSTM encoder to derive the latent representation embeddings, followed by the prediction of the cluster labels, based on the determined centroids, we detected (N= 112) rapid, (N= 128) moderate and (N = 40) slow PD patients. We additionally provide the mean distribution of certain feature categories, including the MDS-UPDRS I-III scores along with the Schwab and England ADL scores, which are of particular importance for our analysis, in **Figure 42**. Although the two cohorts exhibit differences - as expected, due to the heterogeneity of the disease and patients in each group - the progression subtypes appear to be consistent across the two.

Figure 41 2D embedding space visualization of PPMI

Figure 42 Progression plots for both cohorts for the feature categories: MDS-UPDRS I-III & Schwab and England ADL. Continuous lines correspond to the PPMI cohort, while dashed lines represent the PDBP cohort. The shaded areas represent the std. deviation from the mean value of each subtype.

6.5.2 Second stage: PDualNet Training and Evaluation

For the training of PDualNet we split the cohort into training and test set, containing 75% and 25% of the participants respectively, stratified with respect to the progression subtypes (109/36 for rapid, 114/38 for moderate, 70/24 for slow and 141/47 for HC). Additionally, we further split the training set into 5 stratified subsets, to perform a 5-fold cross validation. To generate the input sequences, we use a sliding window for each participant, with sizes $W = \{2,3,4,5\}$, and for training we set the maximum number of future MDS-UPDRS scores to predict to 5.

For performance comparison, we use the same data split to train and test three baseline models. The first is a Temporal Convolutional Neural Network (TCN) (Lea et al., 2016) -based model, consisting of a TCN encoder followed by two Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) decoders - one for classification and one for regression. Our second baseline shares the same encoder-decoder architecture, but with the encoder replaced by a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

module. Both aforementioned models were trained following a two-phase procedure analogous to that of our proposed model, ensuring clarity and fair comparison. Specifically, in the first phase, the models were trained on the classification task alone, with the regression decoders' parameters kept frozen; in the second phase, both tasks were jointly optimized using the dual-task objective. The third baseline comprises two separate Random Forest (RF) models, each dedicated to classification and regression, respectively. However, since these baseline models do not support multi-length input/output sequences, we train different models for each sliding window size W and set the number of future MDS-UPDRS scores to one, to ensure a fair comparison. Testing of all models (including PDualNet) is similarly conducted separately for each W , predicting a single future MDS-UPDRS I-III score.

6.5.3 Testing on PPMI cohort

For the held-out test set, we present the mean and standard deviation results for varying numbers of input visits (ranging from 2 to 5), across several evaluation metrics, which are summarized in **Table 38a**. More specifically, considering the subtype classification task, PDualNet surpasses both baseline models, achieving the highest overall accuracy (82.87 ± 1.06), precision (83.48 ± 1.18), recall (81.68 ± 1.16) and F1 score (82.37 ± 1.16), retaining at the same time minimal standard deviation, indicating a stable and consistent performance. Another point worth mentioning is that PDualNet is the only model that achieves perfect accuracy for the HC participants, while it performs reliably across all PD subtypes. Lastly, since the task must meet rigorous performance standards, we underline the model's ability to retain high precision, adding to model's safety, reliability and effectiveness.

When it comes to the regression learning objective (**Table 38b**), our model demonstrates the lowest MSE (19.62 ± 0.19), RMSE (4.11 ± 0.01) and highest R^2 (0.81 ± 0.01) for the MDS-UPDRS I-III scores. Seemingly, neither of the LSTM and RF_{reg} models can reliably predict all three sub-scores, while all baselines are constrained to a single-step prediction horizon, further highlighting the advantage of PDualNet's more comprehensive and robust modeling capability.

When it comes to the model's autoregressive capabilities, we evaluate the model's performance on several future prediction horizons. The results, reported in **Table 38c**, indicate stable prediction performance, with controlled and gradual error increase for longer prediction horizons. Specifically, the mean RMSE rises from 4.72 (p.h. = 2) to 5.15 (p.h. = 4), indicating moderate degradation in multi-step forecasting accuracy. The RMSE values by prediction horizon exhibit similar trends, confirming that the PDualNet maintains consistent predictive behavior rather than experiencing abrupt degradation at any specific horizon.

To assess the statistical significance of the discussed performance differences between PDualNet and the baselines, we conducted paired Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, applied separately for both regression and classification metrics. For classification, we computed the error as $(1-p)$, where p denotes the probability assigned by the model to the true class c . The results, present in **Table 38d**, indicate statistically significant improvements with all p -values below 0.05 in all comparisons.

Table 38 Performance comparison of models across all input sequence lengths (mean \pm standard deviation) - PPMI

(a) Subtype Prediction Performance

Model	Rapid	Moderate	Slow	HC	Overall	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)			

PDualNet	78.87 ±2.26	76.42 ± 1.57	71.43 ± 1.08	100.00 ± 0.00	82.87 ± 1.06	83.48 ± 1.18	81.68 ± 1.16	82.37 ± 1.16
TCN	80.50 ± 1.7	71.54 ± 5.12	73.77 ± 1.3	97.89 ± 0.61	81.72 ± 0.89	82.01 ± 1.20	80.92 ± 0.80	81.31 ± 1.00
LSTM	74.97 ± 5.27	73.09 ± 3.30	69.16 ± 8.94	97.99 ± 2.05	79.93 ± 1.56	79.98 ± 1.68	78.80 ± 1.73	79.14 ± 1.62
RF _{class}	80.15 ± 1.80	70.5 ± 4.58	60.32 ± 4.42	98.68 ± 0.42	79.21 ± 2.20	78.65 ± 2.22	77.41 ± 2.72	77.82 ± 2.40

(b) MDS-UPDRS I-III Score Prediction Performance

Model	MDS-UPDRS I MSE	MDS-UPDRS II MSE	MDS-UPDRS III MSE	Overall MSE	Overall RMSE	Overall R ²
PDualNet	9.15 ± 0.18	8.30±0.10	41.39±0.74	19.62 ±0.19	4.11 ±0.01	0.81 ±0.01
TCN	9.29 ±0.57	10.32 ±1.01	41.32±1.22	20.31 ±0.51	4.23 ±0.07	0.80 ±0.01
LSTM	16.41±4.61	16.99 ±3.31	45.31±1.42	26.24 ±2.68	4.95 ±0.31	0.69 ±0.05
RF _{reg}	16.01±0.90	14.89 ±0.64	50.02±1.45	26.97 ±0.64	4.98 ±0.07	0.70 ±0.00

(c) Autoregressive MDS-UPDRS I-III Score Prediction Performance. Mean RMSE values summarize the mean prediction errors up to each prediction horizon (p.h.), while RMSE by p.h. represents the prediction error specifically at each horizon.

p.h.	Mean RSME				RMSE by Prediction Horizon			
	MDS-UPDRS I	MDS-UPDRS II	MDS-UPDRS III	Overall	MDS-UPDRS I	MDS-UPDRS II	MDS-UPDRS III	Overall
1	3.20	3.11	6.85	4.72	3.35	3.34	7.16	4.96
2	3.35	3.32	7.14	4.94	3.66	3.74	7.69	5.37
3	3.54	3.56	7.37	5.15	4.03	4.27	8.14	5.79

(d) Wilcoxon signed-rank test for statistical comparison of PDualNet against baselines for regression and classification tasks. Extremely small p-values are reported as $p < 10^{-15}$.

Comparison	Task	Statistic	p-value
PDualNet vs. LSTM	Regression	1.937.608,50	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. LSTM	Classification	1.641.988,00	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. RF _{reg}	Regression	1.852.861,50	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. RF _{class}	Classification	2.002.570,50	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. TCN	Regression	18.983.508,50	6.27×10^{-12}
PDualNet vs. TCN	Classification	1.349.853.0	$p < 10^{-15}$

6.5.4 External Validation on PDBP

To put into the test the generalization capabilities of PDualNet, we evaluate its performance on the PDBP cohort. No further fine-tuning is applied to any of the models. The cluster labels derived in the earlier clustering step are used as ground truth, and the results are summarized in **Table 39**.

PDualNet maintains strong performance across both objectives, achieving an overall accuracy of 82.13 ± 0.80 , precision of 78.70 ± 1.38 , recall of 79.22 ± 1.17 and F1 score of 78.89 ± 1.31 for the subtype prediction task. Looking into the model's regression performance, it achieves an overall MSE of 20.44 ± 0.96 , RMSE of 4.28 ± 0.11 and R^2 of 0.78 ± 0.00 for the MDS-UPDRS I-III scores. On the other hand, its autoregressive behaviour further indicates that the model effectively captures longitudinal progression patterns while preserving reasonable accuracy for short- to mid-term forecasts. The aforementioned results closely align with those achieved in the internal test set of the PPMI cohort, showcasing PDualNet's robustness and generalization capabilities across different datasets and varied input sequence lengths. Another observation is that the baseline models present biases towards certain subtypes. For instance, the RF_{class} demonstrates a clear preference for the moderate subtypes, even in the PPMI test set, while producing erratic predictions for the remaining subtypes. When it comes to the LSTM model, it achieves significantly higher accuracy for the slow subtype, while the other two subtypes are predicted less reliably - a pattern not observed when tested on the PPMI data, suggesting the model's difficulty to generalize across cohorts. Similar observations can be made for the TCN model as well, as a bias is observed toward predicting the rapid progression subtypes, with great variance in the model's performance metrics for the moderate and slow subtype, compared to the PPMI case. In contrast, PDualNet shows no such biases, and exhibits stable cross-cohort performance, further demonstrating its robustness.

Table 39 Performance comparison of models across all input sequence lengths (mean \pm standard deviation) - PDBP.

(a) Subtype Prediction Performance

Model	Rapid	Moderate	Slow	HC	Overall	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)	Acc (%)			
PDualNet	77.70 \pm 2.87	75.21 \pm 0.55	68.13 \pm 1.50	95.86 \pm 0.82	82.13 \pm 0.80	78.70 \pm 1.38	79.22 \pm 1.17	78.89 \pm 1.31
TCN	78.27 \pm 2.01	69.40 \pm 4.05	67.26 \pm 13.58	91.44 \pm 1.17	78.99 \pm 1.51	75.57 \pm 1.70	76.59 \pm 3.63	75.63 \pm 2.16
LSTM	70.07 \pm 3.79	64.39 \pm 3.58	79.27 \pm 12.70	90.07 \pm 1.93	75.69 \pm 2.50	72.11 \pm 2.86	75.95 \pm 3.98	72.68 \pm 3.02
RF_{class}	70.06 \pm 2.58	78.76 \pm 2.51	62.01 \pm 4.81	96.30 \pm 1.39	80.66 \pm 0.77	77.53 \pm 1.48	76.78 \pm 1.76	76.86 \pm 1.70

(b) MDS-UPDRS I-III Score Prediction Performance

Model	MDS-UPDRS I MSE	MDS-UPDRS II MSE	MDS-UPDRS III MSE	Overall MSE	Overall RMSE	Overall R^2
PDualNet	11.19 \pm 0.50	9.96 \pm 0.85	40.17 \pm 1.60	20.44 \pm 0.96	4.28 \pm 0.11	0.78 \pm 0.00

TCN	11.17 ± 0.51	11.61 ± 1.05	38.77 ± 1.01	20.51 ± 0.57	4.42 ± 0.08	0.77 ± 0.01
LSTM	16.98 ± 4.44	19.13 ± 4.26	44.86 ± 3.60	26.99 ± 3.95	5.04 ± 0.40	0.67 ± 0.05
RF _{reg}	15.60 ± 0.94	17.89 ± 1.56	49.62 ± 0.71	27.70 ± 0.96	5.07 ± 0.11	0.68 ± 0.01

(c) Autoregressive MDS-UPDRS I–III Score Prediction Performance. Mean RMSE values summarize the mean prediction errors up to each prediction horizon (p.h.), while RMSE by p.h. represents the prediction error specifically at each horizon.

p.h.	Mean RSME				RMSE by Prediction Horizon			
	MDS-UPDRS I	MDS-UPDRS II	MDS-UPDRS III	Overall	MDS-UPDRS I	MDS-UPDRS II	MDS-UPDRS III	Overall
1	3.44	3.34	6.68	4.75	3.55	3.55	6.97	4.96
2	3.56	3.57	6.96	4.96	3.80	4.02	7.47	5.37
3	3.70	3.78	7.21	5.16	4.10	4.42	7.96	5.77

(d) Wilcoxon signed-rank test for statistical comparison of PDualNet against baselines for regression and classification tasks. Extremely small p-values are reported as $p < 10^{-15}$.

Comparison	Task	Statistic	p-value
PDualNet vs. LSTM	Regression	70,466,069.0	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. LSTM	Classification	7,932,208.0	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. RF _{reg}	Regression	68,899,606.5	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. RF _{class}	Classification	6,814,771.5	$p < 10^{-15}$
PDualNet vs. TCN	Regression	78,284,353.0	$p = 0.0023$
PDualNet vs. TCN	Classification	7,044,716.5	$p < 10^{-15}$

Similarly to the PPMI case, we also provide the paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test results. The test statistics are consistently large in magnitude, and all corresponding p-values fall well below conventional significance thresholds ($p < 0.005$), indicating that the observed performance gains are statistically significant. Even in the least significant comparison (regression PDualNet vs. TCN, where $p = 0.0023 < 0.005$), PDualNet still shows a statistically robust improvement.

Model Interpretability

In order to provide a deeper understanding and transparency regarding the model's decision-making process, we provide the SHAP values of the 20 most significant features for each subtype. The results are illustrated in the form of a violin plot in **Figure 43**, where positive (or negative) SHAP values indicate that features push the prediction closer to (further from) the final output. The subplots reveal a clear, clinically interpretable structure in the model's decision space: high-magnitude motor features, i.e., MDS-UPDRS-III items are the dominant drivers that push predictions toward pathological subtypes, whereas preserved global function and cognition (e.g., higher ADL/Modified Schwab & England, higher MoCA score) tend to push predictions away from rapid decline and toward slower courses or HC. Non-motor features (daytime sleepiness, EPWORTH score items, constipation, mood) contribute more subtly but consistently, enhancing the separation of moderate and slow subtypes from each other and from HC. Moreover, the participant's age is considered in all subtypes, suggesting that younger patients experience slower disease progression, and vice versa. The colour gradients

in the summary plots show that higher values of motor-severity features produce positive SHAP contributions for identifying fast progressors, whereas higher cognitive/ADL scores produce negative contributions for those labels, while the exact opposite pattern is observed for the slow subtype. Overall, the SHAP-driven explainability is both informative and clinically meaningful, as it maps the model's decisions onto familiar, domain-relevant measurements. It should be noted, though, that SHAP describes the model's associations, not causation, and further analysis should be made before clinical deployment.

Figure 43 Violin plots for SHAP values corresponding to (a) rapid, (b) moderate, (c) slow and (d) Healthy Control subtypes

Fairness assessment

To gain greater insight into the model's generalization capabilities, we perform a stratified analysis across different demographic subgroups of the PDBP cohort. Specifically, we assessed PDualNet's performance separately for male and female participants, as well as for

younger (<60 years) and older (≥ 60 years) individuals, in both the classification and regression tasks. As illustrated in **Figure 44**, across all subgroups, classification accuracy ranged from 0.805 to 0.834 and F1-score from 0.703 to 0.801, indicating consistent model performance, and suggesting fairness and external generalization. Minor reductions, within accepted ranges, are observed in recall and MSE in older and male participants, which may reflect sample distribution or clinical heterogeneity rather than algorithmic bias.

Figure 44 Stratified analysis of PDualNet performance over different Demographic groups, including female, male, participants under 60 years (< 60) and those over 60 years (> 60). Similar performance is observed over all subgroups, indicating no significant algorithmic bias.

6.6 Discussion

6.6.1 Interpretation

We developed and evaluated a progression-prediction framework combining (i) supervised prediction of predefined clinical outcomes (a1–a3, E2-1, E2-2,) and (ii) supervised prediction of data-driven subtypes derived from two unsupervised strategies (multi-view consensus and a longitudinal, time-weighted clustering). Wearable digital biomarkers (Verily Study Watch) were added at the supervised stage to augment clinical predictors without influencing subtype discovery. This two-pronged design targets clinically agreed endpoints while also exploiting latent structure in the data to surface stable phenotypes of progression.

Across predefined clinically defined outcomes, discrimination was moderate overall, with variability by endpoint (primary a1-a3 generally stronger than secondary outcomes), reflecting the heterogeneity of PD trajectories and the challenge of forecasting relatively small 12-month changes. By contrast, models predicting cluster membership for the data-driven subtypes achieved high internal performance, suggesting that the learned subtypes capture coherent, reproducible patterns that are easier to identify from baseline plus wearable signals than narrowly defined single-scale changes. Notably, the inclusion of wearable-derived features consistently improved performance across all outcomes, confirming their complementary value for capturing subtle aspects of motor and behavioral change that are often missed by clinical scales alone.

Based on clinical expert feedback, the three clusters exhibit distinct and clinically interpretable patterns. Cluster 0 groups individuals with the highest baseline motor and non-motor burden and the most pronounced worsening over 12 months. Cluster 1 includes patients with moderate baseline severity and relatively stable clinical profiles, with minimal change across

assessments. Cluster 2 contains individuals with the lowest overall burden at baseline and mild, selective progression. These patterns suggest meaningful heterogeneity in how patients evolve over time.

Furthermore, an end-to-end deep learning framework, namely PDualNet, was proposed to address the dual-problem of PD progression subtype classification and future MDS-UPDRS score prediction. The model exploits the longitudinal nature of the data on two levels: first, by encoding the single visit information into a latent representation (SiVE), and second, by identifying the hidden temporal patterns across all provided visits, through a Transformer-based architecture. This structure, combined with the three-phase training procedure, allows the model to learn a shared representation (DiSE), that essentially encodes the disease state in terms of progression, and thus being able to address both tasks simultaneously.

In addition, the model is trained on a large, broadly representative cohort, namely PPMI, and evaluated on a) a held-out test set and b) an external validation set, derived from the PDBP study. Additionally, to that, to benchmark performance, we compared PDualNet with two baseline models that are often used in the field to address the same tasks. The results demonstrated the model's superior performance on both cohorts, highlighting its robustness and generalization capabilities. It is also worth mentioning that, compared to the baselines, PDualNet was able to achieve the highest accuracy, F1 score, and lowest MSE for the regression task, all within a single-unified framework. This is a significant advantage over the baseline models, which are constrained to single-step predictions, and specific input sequence lengths.

6.6.2 Beyond SoA

This section outlines how the PD progression modelling advances beyond the current state of the art across methodological, analytical, multimodal, and validation components. We evaluated our approach and its novelty through direct comparison to the landscape of progression modelling techniques reviewed in D2.4 and in recent literature. We highlight advancements in progression outcome definition, longitudinal subtyping, and multimodal feature integration. Collectively, these contributions demonstrate that the PD progression model goes beyond traditional approaches in several clinically meaningful domains.

Expanded and clinically aligned progression outcomes. Existing PD progression models typically predict a single endpoint, most commonly the change in MDS-UPDRS III. In contrast, our framework operationalizes a broader and clinically richer set of outcomes, including motor worsening, treatment escalation, emergence of motor complications, and key non-motor deterioration. These multidimensional targets better reflect real clinical decision-making and overcome the narrow single-metric focus of traditional approaches.

Time-aware data-driven subtyping beyond static baselines. Most published studies define PD subtypes using baseline-only information or long-term trajectories not applicable to short-term clinical settings. Here, we introduce two novel short-term longitudinal subtyping approaches that jointly model baseline status and 12-month change profiles. These strategies enable the identification of early progression phenotypes, improving the clinical utility of subtype discovery compared with static clustering approaches.

Comprehensive multimodal feature integration. Prior work in PD progression modelling relies largely on clinical rating scales or coarse clinical descriptors. Our approach integrates rich multimodal features, combining

- demographics, treatment exposure, cognitive and non-motor scales,
- composite motor domain scores (PIGD, Tremor, Bradykinesia, Rigidity),
- genetic susceptibility (PRS), and

- digital biomarkers from the Verily Study Watch, including gait, activity regularity, slowness, and sleep behaviour extracted using tsfresh.

This multimodal feature set significantly enhances data richness and improves predictive discrimination across most outcomes.

Improved discriminatory performance across multiple clinically relevant endpoints.

Unlike previous state-of-the-art models limited to single-target prediction, we systematically assessed performance across several clinically defined outcomes as well as data-driven subtypes. Results demonstrated consistent gains across heterogeneous targets, highlighting the added prognostic value of real-world digital biomarkers and the advantages of multimodal fusion.

Holistic dual-task deep learning architecture. Previous deep learning approaches in PD progression modelling typically predict continuous scores or classify progression groups in isolation. We developed PDualNet, a multi-task Transformer architecture that jointly learns progression subtype and future MDS-UPDRS I–III scores. This dual-task model provides a unified embedding of disease progression that is more expressive and more clinically informative than traditional, single-task deep learning approaches.

Comprehensive bias and fairness assessment. Few PD progression models evaluate fairness. We conducted a complete bias assessment across sex, race, education, and age at diagnosis using balanced accuracy, demographic parity, and equalized odds. For most outcomes, performance remained consistent across major subgroups, though small minority groups exhibited variability due to limited sample size. This structured fairness evaluation ensures that the developed models adhere to Trustworthy AI guidelines and exceeds the typical fairness reporting in current literature.

6.6.3 Limitations

For the yearly progression prediction, the models have not yet been validated on an independent external dataset. As such, external validation within the AI-PMP cohort remains essential to confirm generalizability and to ensure that performance estimates obtained on PPMI translate to the intended population.

The supervised subset with complete clinical and wearable data was relatively small, and several outcomes exhibited class imbalance. Although we applied SMOTE oversampling during training to mitigate this issue, synthetic balancing cannot fully substitute for larger, well-represented datasets.

Also, one limitation of the current analysis is that advanced therapeutic interventions, such as deep brain stimulation (DBS), were not explicitly studied in the progression outcomes. Future work will explicitly investigate the role of such advanced treatments, as potential modifiers of progression patterns across both clinically defined and data-driven outcomes.

As for the fairness analysis power, even when balanced accuracy was high across major groups, several subgroups (e.g., minority races) had very small *n*, producing unstable estimates and extreme fairness ratios/differences. These should not be over-interpreted;

Regarding computational efficiency, while PDualNet contains more parameters than its counterparts, it is important to highlight that baseline models were separately trained for each of the four input sequence lengths, resulting in comparable or even higher overall complexity and training effort when considering the total number of the required trained models.

Another limitation is that, although two large datasets were used, the study may not fully capture the diversity encountered in real-world clinical practice. The inevitable data

heterogeneity (different quality or lack of data across different institutions) and/or possible inherent biases in training data may cause errors in predictions for underrepresented groups. Therefore, deeper analysis, including a wide spectrum of individual cases, is warranted before clinical deployment can be considered. Additionally, the use of latent representations of data leads inevitably to limited interpretability. External validation and targeted causal and bias assessments are required in applications where interpretability is key.

6.6.4 Next steps and future directions

For the yearly progression prediction approach, several steps can further refine and extend the methodology. As an immediate next step, we plan to apply the same clustering algorithms to the PDBP dataset to investigate whether comparable progression subtypes emerge in an independent cohort. This will also enable external validation of the clinical-only supervised models and provide insight into the reproducibility and robustness of the identified subtypes. In parallel, the wearable-data pipeline can be strengthened by incorporating domain-specific digital mobility biomarkers (such as tremor and dyskinesia). These more progression-relevant dBM features may increase model sensitivity and enhance the detection of meaningful yearly changes.

For long-term progression modelling using deep learning, it would be interesting to integrate additional data sources, and modalities, such as wearable sensor data (e.g., accelerometer), imaging data (e.g. MRI, DaTscan) or genetic information, to further enhance the model's generalization capabilities and deepen its disease encoding abilities. Multimodal fusion could help the model capture complementary information and disease signals that could lead to improved performance in downstream tasks.

Exploring modality-specific encoders or cross-modal attention mechanisms that would enable the transformer to learn richer, clinically meaningful representations of PD heterogeneity. This could also strengthen the model's explainability. For instance, the integration of molecular biomarker or neuroimaging data (e.g., DAT-SPECT or MRI-derived features), could unveil stronger subtype-biomarker correlations, enhancing the clinical interpretability and diagnostic relevance of PDualNet.

Another promising direction is to explore stacking-based ensemble learning models for combining results from different architectures. As recent studies (Yanar et al, 2025a, Yanar et al, 2025b) have shown, such ensemble frameworks can enhance diagnostic accuracy and generalization. Similar models could be employed to fuse the predictions of PDualNet with complementary information from additional modality-specific modules (e.g., imaging, genetic, or sensor data), thereby leveraging their joint strengths to achieve more robust and clinically meaningful decision support. In the context of our work, similar models can be applied to fuse PDualNet results with data from modules processing additional modalities to combine their complementary strengths towards improved clinical decision support.

Furthermore, extensions of PDualNet can be proposed by employing multi-modal federated learning for training models without direct access to the raw data held by different clients, thus facilitating clinical deployment and addressing important data privacy and security concerns. Another observation arising from the model's modular structure is that the encoder component or the learned *DiSE* embeddings alone, can be employed independently in downstream tasks related to the disease (e.g. for predicting longitudinal trajectories of additional clinical scales such as MoCA, ESS, Schwab and England ADL score, etc.).

7 Development and evaluation of a model to predict side effects related to PD medication

7.1 Background and objectives

As already mentioned in the introductory sections, PD is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that primarily affects movement, caused by the gradual loss of dopamine-producing neurons in the brain. While there is no cure, medications such as levodopa and dopamine agonists are commonly used to manage the symptoms. However, these medications can lead to various side effects, including dyskinesia (i.e., involuntary movements), hallucinations, mood changes, and motor fluctuations. Over time, the severity of the PD symptoms increases, requiring higher dosages and increasing the risk of these side effects occurring. In fact, managing the occurrence of these side effects while maintaining sufficient dopaminergic treatment is one of the major challenges in advanced PD.

The goal of this research pillar of the AI-PROGNOSIS is to investigate how ML techniques can provide support for individualized medication prescription strategies. Central to this is the usage of predictive modelling to assess the risk of a specific individual experiencing multiple side effects given the patient's characteristics and planned medication dosages. Specifically, we trained random forest (RF) models to predict, given a current visit of a patient in which the side effect of interest has not yet occurred, whether it will occur by the next visit. In this way, the clinician can perform a more data-driven, informed trade-off between providing sufficient dosage for the primary treatment, while limiting the risk of adverse effects as much as possible.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Dataset description

All data used in this study (both for the development and the evaluation) were obtained from the CPP Integrated Parkinson's Database as described in Section 3.2. We focused on the three biggest datasets from this integrated database: (PPMI, NCT01141023), Parkinson's Repository of Biomarkers and Networked Datasets (PRoBaND, not registered with an NCT number) (Malek et al., 2015) and NINDS Exploratory Trials in PD Long-Term Study 1 (NET-PD LS-1, NCT00449865) (Kieburtz et al., 2015).

These studies were selected based on the availability of the outcomes we aimed to investigate and the large number of patients involved in those studies. The PPMI is a longitudinal, observational, international, multicentre study launched in 2010 to identify biomarkers of PD progression, from prodromal to moderate stages, through clinical, imaging, biological, genetic, and digital assessments, encompassing about 2600 participants at the time of downloading these data. Similarly, PRoBaND is a longitudinal, multicentre study based in the UK, which enrolled about 2000 participants recruited between 2012 and 2017 that have been diagnosed either at most 3.5 years before the study start or at an age younger than 50 years. Finally, NET-PD LS-1 is a multicentre, double-blind, phase-III randomized controlled trial launched in 2007 to assess the impact of creatine on progression in patients with early, treated Parkinson's disease. It contains 1741 patients diagnosed at most five years before the start of the study and on dopaminergic therapy for 3–24 months, randomly assigned to the creatine or placebo groups.

In collaboration with the clinical partners, three outcomes for the predictive models were defined, i.e.: *dyskinesias*, *hallucinations* and *excessive daytime sleepiness*. All three of these can significantly reduce the quality of life in PD patients. They are also typically associated

with prolonged dopaminergic therapy and/or more advanced PD and managing them becomes a major challenge in advanced PD stages. We extracted these outcomes for each visit of every subject in the datasets from the unified Parkinson's disease rating scale (UPDRS) as follows: dyskinesias are defined as having a score of 1 or more on UPDRS item 4.2 (functional impact of dyskinesias), hallucinations as a score of 1 or more on item 1.2 and excessive daytime sleepiness as a score of 2 or more on item 1.8. These specific UPDRS items and scores were chosen as they reflect the earliest point at which these outcomes notably affect the patient. However, while both PPMI and PProBaND datasets reported MDS UPDRS, NET-PD-LS1 exclusively reported UPDRS scores. Thus, for this specific dataset, we followed the guidelines of Goetz et al. to extract UPDRS items as close as possible to the MDS UPDRS items for all outcomes (Goetz et al., 2008). Dyskinesias were defined as UPDRS item 33 being 1 or higher, hallucinations as item 2 being 2 or higher and daytime sleepiness as item 41 being 1. It is important to note that these conversions are not exact and, especially in the case of daytime sleepiness, might lead to some level of dissimilarity in the definitions of the outcomes between datasets.

We then proceeded to create a dataset for the outcomes dyskinesia, hallucinations and sleepiness for the PPMI, PProBaND and NET-PD LS-1, resulting in 9 different datasets in total. First, a number of visits were excluded from each dataset: (1) visits in which the outcome of interest could not be predicted because its value was missing, (2) visits of subjects with less than two recorded visits, (3) visits of subjects already experiencing the outcome at baseline, (4) visits of subjects belonging to the healthy or prodromal groups of PPMI and (5) visits of subjects undergoing deep brain stimulation.

As previously mentioned, the task of the model will be to predict from a current, side effect-free visit, whether the side effect will occur by the next visit. As such, we also proceeded to exclude any visits after the side effect first occurred for each subject from that side effect's specific dataset. This is an important step given the fact that the outcomes are not independent between visits: when a certain side effect is either present or absent in a certain visit, the most likely scenario is that the same will hold true in the next visit. To prevent a model from achieving overoptimistic scores by learning such trivial rules and instead focus on discerning visits where the side effect is not about to occur from those where it is based on the features, this exclusion of visits after the first incidence of the side effect was a necessary step. We will call this prediction framework "first incidence prediction" in the remainder of this text and show it schematically in **Figure 45**. A full breakdown of the details of each of the resulting datasets and some descriptive statistics can be found in **Table 40**.

Table 40 Dataset descriptive statistics after preprocessing for first incidence prediction. This involves the exclusion of healthy controls in PPMI, patients with less than 2 visits, patients already experiencing the outcome at baseline and patients undergoing deep brain stimulation. The earlier or later occurrence of a specific side effect also results in a different number of visits remaining in each setting.

All	PPMI	PProBaND	NET-PD LS-1
Age [years]	62.7±9.4	66.6±8.6	61.8±9.5
PD duration [years]	3.7±2.1	4.6±3.4	1.67±1.1
Sex (M/F)	61.8%/38.2%	65.5%/34.5%	64.2%/35.7%
LEDD [mg]	573±385	544±307	725±569
Dyskinesia			
Number of visits	4551	4,016	8,154

Number of subjects	672	1640	1701
Number of subjects with dyskinesia	228	303	199
Hallucinations			
Number of visits	6,605	3,923	7,846
Number of subjects	912	1,563	1,669
Number of subjects with hallucinations	259	427	266
Daytime sleepiness			
Number of visits	3,558	1,651	3,666
Number of subjects	746	819	1,084
Number of subjects with daytime sleepiness	398	483	647

Figure 45 First incidence framework. Red and green visits indicate visits where the outcome, for instance, dyskinesia, is respectively present and absent. Only visits until the first incidence of the outcome are employed for prediction. If someone never encounters the outcome during the study, all their visits are included.

7.2.2 Data pre-processing

First, the quality of the data was checked by visually inspecting the distributions occurring for the features that were planned to be incorporated into the model. Extreme, unrealistic values (for instance, age being over 200 years) were removed and treated as non-numbers, the same as with any missing data. As an extra step of outlier detection, any values distanced 4 standard deviations away from their respective feature means were removed. Fuzzy string-matching methods were employed to correct for different misspelled entries and match them to a single value.

The random forest models we have been using are naturally able to handle NaN values and thus require no imputation of any kind. Since there is typically a class imbalance between people who experience medication side effects and those who do not, we employed a class-weighted loss every time we train our model. In addition, an array of classification and calibration metrics, such as accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, AUROC and expected calibration error (ECE) are evaluated for each model to ensure they are not overly sensitive to only one of the classes.

7.2.3 Prediction models

Feature inclusion was based on 3 distinct sources: a) an extensive state of the art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable D2.4 “Updated report on domain review and datasets”), b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (QMUL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) to ensure

that the model is clinically informed by expert opinions and c) data availability in the CPP dataset. These features are summarized in **Table 41**. In addition, for each of the outcomes, an initial set of the most relevant risk factors was composed. From the AI-Prognosis consortium, a number of clinical experts were recruited from a variety of different sites. Each of these experts provided a list of candidate risk factors, which were then compiled, checked for evidence in existing literature and availability and completeness in the three investigated datasets. Following this, an online discussion was held and the final risk set for each outcome was decided by consensus.

Table 41 Summary of features included in the prediction models and their ranges. Following the recommendation of the clinical partners, these are assigned to be part of the a priori risk set for dyskinesia's, hallucinations and daytime sleepiness. '/' indicates features used in the model, but not included in any predefined risk set.

Feature	Value	Included as risk factor for
Days until predicted visit	Days	All
Sex	Male/Female	Dyskinesia
Age	Years	/
Body Mass Index (BMI)	kg/cm ²	Dyskinesia
Age at PD diagnosis	Years	Dyskinesia
Hoehn and Yahr stage	0-5	/
Time since PD diagnosis	Years	All
UPDRS I	0-52	/
UPDRS II	0-52	/
UPDRS III	0-132	/
MoCA score	0-30	Hallucinations
Hallucinations (UPDRS 1.2)	0-4	Sleepiness
Insomnia (UPDRS 1.7)	0-4	Sleepiness
Freezing of gait (UPDRS 2.13)	0-4	Hallucinations
Daytime sleepiness (UPDRS 1.8)	0-4	Hallucinations, Sleepiness
LEDD years	years*mg	/
Total LEDD	mg	All
Dopamine agonists	Yes/no	Hallucinations, Sleepiness
MAO-B inhibitors	Yes/no	/
COMT inhibitors	Yes/no	/
Amantadine	Yes/no	/

While most of the features could be directly extracted from the dataset, the following features required additional processing:

- **Medication classes:** Medication taken by the subjects were categorized as belonging to one of 5 different medication classes, in agreement with 5 neurologists: Levodopa, dopamine agonists (e.g. apomorphine, ropinirole, pramipexole), MAO-B inhibitors (selegiline, rasagiline, safinamide), COMT inhibitors (entacapone, tolcapone, opicapone) and amantadine. Thus, each feature vector includes 5 binary variables indicating whether any of these medication classes were being taken at that time.

- **Levodopa equivalent daily dosage (LEDD):** In addition to the binary medication classes the total levodopa equivalent daily dosage (LEDD) of every visit was computed using the guidelines described in Jost et al., 2023.
- **LEDD years:** To summarize the total amount of levodopa taken by a subject so far, we computed LEDD years as a composite feature. It is computed by multiplying the total LEDD taken with the amount of years this has been done, integrated over the entire time since the start of treatment. For example, taking a 100mg of LEDD for a year, followed by 300 mg for half a year would result in a current LEDDyears value of $100*1+300*0.5=250$ mg*years

The listed features are extracted for each visit and then used to perform the binary prediction of whether dyskinesias, hallucinations or daytime sleepiness is present in the next visit. The output of this model is a probability score, which is evaluated with classification and calibration metrics. For the classification metrics, the output probability is converted to a binary decision through thresholding, with the threshold being optimized on a validation set to balance sensitivity and specificity. In addition, ECE is used to assess whether the probabilities align with the empirical risk observed in the data.

7.2.4 Analytical methods

The models used for prediction are random forests (RF) due to (1) their straightforward handling of missing data, (2) the ease of extracting feature importances from them, and (3) their strong generalization properties. Training and hyperparameter optimization occurs through stratified, nested 10-fold cross-validation, with the folds-consisting of the data of disjoint sets of subjects, preventing overfitting and ensuring generalizability to new subjects. For each train/test fold pair, 10-fold cross-validation is performed on this training set to perform hyperparameter optimization, calibration and selecting the threshold. Calibration is performed by fitting a meta-estimator transforming the output of the random forest to calibrated probabilities through Beta calibration. The continuous features of the training set are standardised as to have zero mean and unit standard deviation, while the discrete features are left unstandardised. At test time, the learned standardisation of the training set is then applied to the test set. The considered hyperparameters consist of several standard settings for RF (depth of the decision trees, number of estimators, number of features used per decision tree). The hyperparameter setting that leads to the highest 10-fold cross-validation performance, as measured by average AUROC across the folds, is then selected. Finally, the model is re-trained on the full training dataset using the selected hyperparameters and then evaluated on the test fold.

In addition, we also perform cross-dataset and joint dataset experiments to (1) investigate how well models trained on one dataset generalize to a different dataset and (2) whether pooling data from multiple datasets can improve predictive performance. In the cross-dataset setting, the inner cross-validation loop is performed in the same way as described above, but with the test set consisting of another dataset instead of a different fold. In the joint-dataset setting. The training, validation and test folds of the different datasets are pooled. All three of the settings are illustrated in **Figure 46**.

Figure 46 Cross-validation framework for the three training settings. (a) Within-dataset training trains and evaluates on the folds of a single dataset. (b) Cross-dataset training trains on the folds of one dataset and evaluates on a different dataset. (c) Joint dataset training pools the training folds of all datasets and evaluates on all of the test folds. Performance metrics are reported through the 10-fold outer cross-validation loop. Within every one of these settings, an internal cross-validation loop is performed on the training set to perform hyperparameter optimization and calibration.

Evaluation of the models happens through the previously described cross validation procedure. The cross-dataset evaluation gives some indication on how well models trained on these datasets adapt to feature shifts in different, external validation sets

7.2.5 Training versus evaluation

Differences between training and evaluation data depends on the specific training framework. For within-dataset training and joint dataset training, evaluated through 10-fold cross validation, the training and test distributions are not significantly different. Cross-dataset training however gives a picture of the performance losses that can be incurred when there is a distributional shift between training and testing. Especially in the case of PPMI/PProBaND versus NET-PD LS-1, a significant difference can be observed, with NET-PD LS-1 on average having a lot more early-stage PD visits, which is also reflected in the lower prevalence rate for the side effects.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Participants

The number of patients, the amounts of visits retained in the dataset for first incidence prediction and the amount of them experiencing each side effect are summarized in **Table 40**. This shows a large class imbalance in the prediction of all side effects, especially for dyskinesia and hallucinations. The models are faced with the major challenge of balancing a good sensitivity to find the few positive ‘tipping point visits’, where a side effect is about to occur for the first time, with limiting the false alarm rates in the multiple earlier visits where no side effects will occur.

7.3.2 Model development

The outcome in each prediction task is the prediction of either dyskinesia, hallucinations or daytime sleepiness occurring in the next visit, based on the features of the current visit. As mentioned earlier, we also specifically perform this task in the framework of first incidence prediction, where visits beyond the first occurrence of the side effect in question are excluded to ensure the classification metrics accurately represent how good the model is in detecting the transition from absent to present side effects.

7.3.3 Model specification

The prediction models used are Random Forests. Development took place in Python 3.9, using the *scikit-learn* library for the model, *pandas* for the pre-processing of the data, *matplotlib*

for data visualization, *shap* for explainability and *betacal* to perform Beta calibration. At the end of the analysis, the developed source code will be made publicly available. The full pipeline in Python proceeds as follows. Data is extracted from the dataset, with some composite features being calculated. For instance, total UPDRS_III scores per visit are computed by summing all the relevant entries per visit, or BMI is calculated by dividing the weight in kilograms by the length in centimetres squared. Then a 10-fold outer cross-validation loop is constructed by splitting the subjects of the dataset in 10 disjoint sets. Within each of these 10 train-test splits, inner 10-fold cross-validation is performed in the same way, by creating disjoint sets of subjects. Then, scikit-learn's StandardScaler is fitted on the training data and applied to the training and validation data. Hyperparameter optimization and model fitting happen through feeding a RandomForestClassifier (with the class weight parameter set to 'balanced') to the GridSearchCV, which selects the best model based on 10-fold cross-validation and AUROC as a metric, selecting from the hyperparameters of **Table 42**.

In addition, the validation set is used to perform Beta calibration, by fitting a meta-estimator to transform the output probabilities of the random forest into calibrated probabilities. After hyperparameter selection, the model is then re-fitted to the training data with these settings, a scaler is fitted for normalization and Beta calibration once again being performed on a randomly selected part of this training set. Prediction is then performed on the held-out test fold, with this whole process being repeated 10 times in the outer crossvalidation loop. Classification metrics are reported as averages and standard deviations across these 10 test folds. Calibration metrics such as ECE are unreliable to compute on the individual folds though: since they are based on binning to estimate empirical risks, they need a sufficient number of positive samples in each individual fold, but those are rather rare in this setting. Instead, we aggregate all the out-of-fold test predictions and compute the calibration curve on all this data combined through quantile binning. 95% confidence intervals are then computed by performing bootstrapping with 1000 resamples with replacement.

Table 42 Hyperparameter search space for the predictive models

Parameter	Value
Maximum depth	[5,10,20,30,40]
Relative amount of features per tree	[0.25,0.50,0.75,1]
Minimum samples per leaf	[1,3,5,8,15]
Number of trees	[100,200,400,600]

7.3.4 Model performance

The performance metrics of the within-dataset trained models for dyskinesia, hallucination and daytime sleepiness prediction with the PPMI, PRoBaND and NET-PD LS-1 datasets are shown in **Table 43**. Here, we also report the performance gains of the models employing the full feature set compared to using only the outcome-specific, predefined feature set specified by the clinical partners and only using total LEDD. In addition, we illustrate calibration curves and the feature contributions as explained by SHAP values for the models trained on the PPMI dataset in **Figure 47** and **Figure 48**. Finally, **Table 44** compares the within-dataset, the cross-dataset and the joint dataset performance for the models using all feature sets.

Table 43 Model performance on PPMI, ProBaND and NET-PD LS-1 for predicting dyskinesias, hallucinations and daytime sleepiness. Bal.Acc.: balanced accuracy, Spec.: specificity, Sens.: sensitivity, Prec.: precision, AUROC: area-under-ROC curve, ECE: expected calibration error. The classification metrics are reported as means +/- standard deviations across the 10 test folds. ECE on the other hand, could not reliably be computed on a single fold due to the low sample size. Instead, we report a 95% confidence interval computed by performing bootstrapping (1000 resamples) on the

aggregated out-of-fold predictions. The calibration curve ECE is based on is computed through quantile binning with 10 bins.

Dyskinesia							
Dataset	Feature set	Bal. Acc. [%]	Spec. [%]	Sens. [%]	Prec. [%]	AUROC [%]	ECE [%]
PPMI	All	70.4 ± 3.7	70.7 ± 4.1	70.1 ± 7.7	11.3 ± 2.3	76.7 ± 3.6	0.7, [0.6, 1.5]
	Risk set	66.0 ± 4.5	66.8 ± 4.4	65.1 ± 11.1	9.4 ± 2.1	72.7 ± 5.5	0.4, [0.5, 1.4]
	LEDD	63.0 ± 4.1	59.2 ± 6.9	66.7 ± 11.3	7.9 ± 1.3	66.3 ± 4.6	0.8, [0.7, 1.6]
PRoBaND	All	67.2 ± 3.7	67.9 ± 2.9	66.5 ± 9.4	14.4 ± 2.6	75.0 ± 4.2	0.6, [0.7, 1.7]
	Risk set	68.5 ± 2.5	67.4 ± 3.7	69.6 ± 6.8	15.0 ± 3.4	74.1 ± 3.6	0.8, [0.7, 1.9]
	LEDD	61.6 ± 4.8	56.6 ± 4.4	66.5 ± 10.2	11.1 ± 1.9	64.9 ± 5.1	1.5, [1.3, 2.6]
NET-PD LS-1	All	67.9 ± 3.9	66.3 ± 2.5	69.4 ± 8.1	4.9 ± 1.1	75.5 ± 2.8	0.4, [0.3, 0.8]
	Risk set	65.0 ± 4.3	66.6 ± 3.4	63.4 ± 9.8	4.5 ± 0.7	72.7 ± 2.9	0.4, [0.3, 0.8]
	LEDD	56.9 ± 4.5	66.2 ± 4.0	47.7 ± 8.3	3.4 ± 0.8	61.4 ± 4.0	0.6, [0.4, 1.0]
Hallucinations							
Dataset	Feature set	Bal. Acc.	Spec.	Sens.	Prec.	AUROC	ECE
PPMI	All	59.9 ± 5.5	60.6 ± 5.0	59.1 ± 11.3	6.5 ± 1.8	65.1 ± 4.9	0.4, [0.5, 1.2]
	Risk set	56.4 ± 3.6	55.9 ± 4.9	56.8 ± 9.2	5.6 ± 1.2	59.4 ± 4.7	0.6, [0.6, 1.4]
	LEDD	51.5 ± 4.6	83.9 ± 13.6	19.1 ± 18.6	7.4 ± 8.4	51.1 ± 7.9	1.1, [0.8, 1.7]
PRoBaND	All	63.3 ± 3.2	61.2 ± 4.3	65.4 ± 7.2	17.1 ± 2.5	67.6 ± 3.7	1.5, [1.2, 2.7]
	Risk set	60.4 ± 3.4	57.8 ± 4.5	63.0 ± 8.6	15.5 ± 2.0	62.9 ± 3.2	1.0, [1.0, 2.4]
	LEDD	53.4 ± 3.0	47.4 ± 11.1	59.4 ± 14.6	12.1 ± 1.7	55.2 ± 3.8	1.5, [1.1, 2.7]
NET-PD LS-1	All	62.4 ± 4.5	61.5 ± 3.1	63.4 ± 9.3	5.5 ± 1.3	67.0 ± 4.8	0.4, [0.3, 0.9]
	Risk set	52.1 ± 4.8	62.4 ± 6.1	41.8 ± 9.4	3.9 ± 1.5	55.9 ± 5.6	0.6, [0.5, 1.1]
	LEDD	52.1 ± 2.2	87.5 ± 5.3	16.7 ± 6.1	4.7 ± 1.5	50.6 ± 3.1	0.6, [0.5, 1.1]
Daytime sleepiness							
Dataset	Feature set	Bal. Acc.	Spec.	Sens.	Prec.	AUROC	ECE
PPMI	All	64.1 ± 3.1	63.2 ± 6.5	65.1 ± 7.7	18.4 ± 1.7	68.2 ± 4.2	1.1, [0.9, 2.4]
	Risk set	63.1 ± 4.7	62.0 ± 5.0	64.3 ± 9.9	18.0 ± 3.8	65.9 ± 4.8	1.8, [1.3, 3.0]
	LEDD	59.3 ± 6.7	61.6 ± 3.2	56.9 ± 13.2	16.4 ± 5.9	60.9 ± 7.4	1.8, [1.6, 3.1]
PRoBaND	All	60.4 ± 2.5	59.1 ± 5.3	61.6 ± 6.5	38.7 ± 5.4	65.7 ± 2.9	2.8, [2.5, 5.6]
	Risk set	60.8 ± 3.8	60.8 ± 2.6	60.8 ± 8.4	39.1 ± 5.0	65.2 ± 4.0	1.4, [1.9, 4.8]

	LEDD	52.3 ± 3.0	53.0 ± 7.2	51.5 ± 6.4	31.6 ± 4.6	55.5 ± 3.6	3.3, [3.1, 6.6]
NET-PD LS-1	All	51.8 ± 3.9	53.5 ± 8.3	50.0 ± 10.2	18.8 ± 3.2	53.3 ± 4.5	1.0, [1.1, 2.7]
	Risk set	52.0 ± 3.3	50.2 ± 9.0	53.9 ± 7.8	19.0 ± 2.2	54.0 ± 4.7	1.2, [1.1, 3.0]
	LEDD	50.8 ± 3.0	49.4 ± 12.9	52.3 ± 11.7	18.3 ± 2.7	50.0 ± 3.1	1.8, [1.5, 3.5]

Table 44 Cross-dataset and joint dataset model performance on PPMI, ProBaND and NET-PD LS-1 for predicting dyskinesias, hallucinations and daytime sleepiness. Bal.Acc.: balanced accuracy, Spec.: specificity, Sens.: sensitivity, Prec.: precision, AUROC: area-under-ROC curve, ECE: expected calibration error. Training a prediction model on one dataset and applying it to another leads to minor performance losses, indicating strong generalization properties of cross-dataset models. Training on all datasets jointly does not lead to significant increases on the individual datasets.

Dyskinesia							
Evaluation set	Training set	Bal. Acc. [%]	Spec. [%]	Sens. [%]	Prec. [%]	AUROC [%]	ECE [%]
PPMI	PPMI	70.4 ± 3.7	70.7 ± 4.1	70.1 ± 7.7	11.3 ± 2.3	76.7 ± 3.6	0.7, [0.6, 1.5]
	PRoBaND	66.8 ± 0.2	57.5 ± 0.4	76.1 ± 0.6	8.6 ± 0.0	72.5 ± 0.1	3.6, [3.3, 3.8]
	NET-PD LS-1	63.9 ± 0.6	43.6 ± 1.2	84.2 ± 0.6	7.3 ± 0.1	70.6 ± 0.2	2.0, [1.8, 2.2]
	All	69.3 ± 5.3	58.7 ± 3.8	79.8 ± 9.5	9.3 ± 2.2	77.0 ± 4.0	0.5, [0.5, 1.4]
PRoBaND	PRoBaND	67.2 ± 3.7	67.8 ± 2.9	66.5 ± 9.4	14.4 ± 2.6	75.0 ± 4.2	0.6, [0.7, 1.7]
	PPMI	67.0 ± 0.3	70.0 ± 3.2	64.1 ± 3.5	14.9 ± 0.7	72.4 ± 0.1	2.4, [2.1, 2.6]
	NET-PD LS-1	65.3 ± 0.2	55.2 ± 1.7	75.3 ± 1.5	12.1 ± 0.2	71.8 ± 0.2	4.7, [4.4, 4.9]
	All	67.8 ± 4.4	52.8 ± 3.9	82.8 ± 8.5	12.4 ± 2.8	75.6 ± 4.2	1.3, [1.0, 2.3]
NET-PD LS-1	NET-PD LS-1	67.9 ± 3.9	66.3 ± 2.5	69.4 ± 8.1	4.9 ± 1.1	75.5 ± 2.8	0.4, [0.3, 0.8]
	PPMI	63.1 ± 1.2	85.3 ± 2.2	40.8 ± 4.4	6.6 ± 0.3	75.7 ± 0.2	0.8, [0.7, 0.9]
	ProBaND	64.9 ± 0.4	72.8 ± 1.3	57.0 ± 1.4	5.0 ± 0.2	73.0 ± 0.4	4.0, [3.9, 4.1]
	All	64.6 ± 4.5	79.7 ± 11.6	49.4 ± 17.5	7.2 ± 2.1	76.5 ± 2.7	0.3, [0.3, 0.8]
Hallucinations							
Evaluation set	Training set	Bal. Acc. [%]	Spec. [%]	Sens. [%]	Prec. [%]	AUROC [%]	ECE [%]
PPMI	PPMI	59.9 ± 5.5	60.6 ± 5.0	59.1 ± 11.3	6.5 ± 1.8	65.1 ± 4.9	0.4, [0.5, 1.2]

	PRoBaND	57.7 ± 0.8	78.6 ± 2.3	36.9 ± 3.9	7.3 ± 0.1	64.8 ± 0.3	4.2, [4.1, 4.4]
	NET-PD LS-1	57.4 ± 0.5	46.2 ± 1.6	68.6 ± 2.0	5.5 ± 0.1	59.8 ± 0.4	0.7, [0.6, 0.9]
	All	62.6 ± 4.7	66.5 ± 3.2	58.8 ± 11.8	7.4 ± 1.4	67.1 ± 3.4	0.5, [0.5, 1.2]
PRoBaND	PRoBaND	63.3 ± 3.2	61.2 ± 4.3	65.4 ± 7.2	17.1 ± 2.5	67.6 ± 3.7	1.5, [1.2, 2.7]
	PPMI	58.2 ± 0.2	23.8 ± 0.9	92.7 ± 0.8	12.9 ± 0.1	63.0 ± 0.3	4.4, [4.1, 4.7]
	NET-PD LS-1	54.3 ± 0.4	13.9 ± 2.0	94.6 ± 1.5	11.8 ± 0.1	61.9 ± 0.4	5.3, [5.0, 5.6]
	All	58.4 ± 2.7	25.6 ± 12.3	91.2 ± 8.4	12.2 ± 1.9	67.5 ± 3.4	1.7, [1.3, 3.0]
NET-PD LS-1	NET-PD LS-1	62.4 ± 4.5	61.5 ± 3.1	63.4 ± 9.3	5.5 ± 1.3	67.0 ± 4.8	0.4, [0.3, 0.9]
	PPMI	59.8 ± 0.5	78.1 ± 1.5	41.6 ± 0.8	6.2 ± 0.3	64.4 ± 0.3	0.8, [0.7, 0.9]
	ProBaND	51.6 ± 0.6	98.8 ± 0.5	4.3 ± 1.8	11.4 ± 1.2	64.3 ± 0.2	2.8, [2.7, 3.0]
	All	60.4 ± 5.4	74.0 ± 16.5	46.9 ± 17.2	7.4 ± 2.6	67.3 ± 4.7	0.3, [0.3, 0.9]
Daytime sleepiness							
Evaluation set	Training set	Bal. Acc. [%]	Spec. [%]	Sens. [%]	Prec. [%]	AUROC [%]	ECE [%]
PPMI	PPMI	64.1 ± 3.1	63.2 ± 6.5	65.1 ± 7.7	18.4 ± 1.7	68.2 ± 4.2	1.1, [0.9, 2.4]
	PRoBaND	60.2 ± 0.7	81.5 ± 1.0	38.9 ± 2.3	20.9 ± 0.3	68.3 ± 0.1	11.3, [11.0, 11.6]
	NET-PD LS-1	58.4 ± 0.3	53.8 ± 0.9	63.1 ± 0.9	14.8 ± 0.7	62.8 ± 0.3	7.0, [6.7, 7.3]
	All	59.0 ± 3.5	84.3 ± 3.3	33.7 ± 6.2	21.9 ± 5.1	68.9 ± 4.5	2.9, [2.5, 4.1]
PRoBaND	PRoBaND	60.4 ± 2.5	59.1 ± 5.3	61.6 ± 6.5	38.7 ± 5.4	65.7 ± 2.9	2.8, [2.5, 5.6]
	PPMI	59.5 ± 0.2	37.2 ± 0.8	81.8 ± 0.6	35.0 ± 0.2	65.6 ± 0.1	13.9, [13.2, 14.6]
	NET-PD LS-1	53.1 ± 1.3	12.0 ± 5.5	94.1 ± 3.0	30.7 ± 0.7	62.4 ± 0.3	9.8, [9.1, 10.5]
	All	59.9 ± 3.1	39.4 ± 14.1	80.3 ± 14.5	33.5 ± 7.1	66.8 ± 2.5	4.8, [3.3, 7.0]
NET-PD LS-1	NET-PD LS-1	51.8 ± 3.9	53.5 ± 8.3	50.0 ± 10.2	18.8 ± 3.2	53.3 ± 4.5	1.0, [1.1, 2.7]
	PPMI	51.7 ± 0.2	90.1 ± 0.4	13.4 ± 0.6	22.5 ± 0.4	54.1 ± 0.1	10.3, [9.9, 10.7]
	ProBaND	53.1 ± 1.3	12.0 ± 5.5	94.1 ± 3.0	30.7 ± 0.7	62.4 ± 0.3	9.8, [9.1, 10.5]

	All	53.7 ± 5.4	45.3 ± 13.4	62.0 ± 15.5	20.2 ± 6.4	57.0 ± 7.2	3.2, [2.4, 4.6]
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Figure 47 Calibration curves for dyskinesia, hallucination and sleepiness prediction in the PPMI dataset obtained through 10-fold cross-validation. 95% confidence intervals are computed through bootstrapping (1000 resamples). Due to the relative rarity of visits with dyskinesia's and hallucinations, the vast majority of the models' predictions result in an output risk of less than 20%.

Finally, we performed a bias and fairness assessment by evaluating how the model's performance varied across different subgroups. Based on availability in the datasets and socio-economic and sociodemographic relevance, we performed this analysis on the protected variables sex, race, age and education level by looking at how the balanced accuracy of the model differs in different groups. **Table 45** summarizes this information for the dyskinesia prediction model on the PPMI, PRoBaND and NET-PD LS-1 datasets. While for some subgroups a drop in performance can be observed, the number of samples in those groups is generally too small to draw reliable performance conclusions in the first place. The most important observation from this assessment is rather that there is still a limitation in the model concerning the representation of different races and ethnicities.

Figure 48 Feature importances for dyskinesia, hallucination and sleepiness prediction in the PPMI dataset as computed by SHAP values. The most relevant features for all outcomes generally align with clinical expectations

Table 45 Analysis per protected variable

Sex	No. of samples	Percentage	Balanced accuracy
F	4961	35	0.68
M	9213	65	0.69
Age group			
40-	257	1.54	0.65
40-50	1406	8.41	0.69
50-60	4327	25.88	0.70
60-70	6989	41.8	0.68
70-80	3442	20.58	0.65
80+	300	1.79	0.39
Race			
American Indian or Alaska native	24	0.17	0.58
Asian	235	1.66	0.72
Asian or Asian British	21	0.15	0.64
Black or African American	192	1.35	0.79
Black or black British	7	0.05	0.86
Mixed	9	0.06	0.25
Multiple	139	0.98	0.80
Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	5	0.04	0.20

Other	18	0.13	0.83
Unk	43	0.3	0.83
Unknown	123	0.87	0.73
Unknown or not reporter	4	0.03	0.75
White	13354	94.21	0.68
Education years (PPMI)			
0-12	688	18.12	0.75
12-16	1598	42.09	0.67
16-20	1365	35.95	0.69
20+	146	3.85	0.60
Education level (NET-PD LS-1)			
9 th to 12 th grade, no diploma	156	2.31	0.82
<9 th grade	144	2.13	0.46
Associate degree	543	8.02	0.73
Bachelor's degree	1857	27.44	0.77
Graduate or professional degree	2173	32.11	0.68
High school graduate	807	11.93	0.62
Some college, not degree	1087	16.06	0.66

7.4 Discussion

7.4.1 Interpretation

When training and evaluation is limited to a single dataset, reasonable performances in sensitivity, specificity, AUROC and ECE are obtained for the three outcomes on the three datasets. In addition, a clear trend can be observed where the model employing the full feature set outperforms the predefined risk set. The only problematic case is the combination of daytime sleepiness and NET-PD LS-1. This can be explained due to the fact that daytime sleepiness in this context is defined as the score of a specific MDS-UPDRS item being 2 or higher, with no exact equivalent existing in the original UPDRS score used in NET-PD LS-1. This means that there is no way to guarantee the severity of the positive sleepiness cases in this dataset is of the same level as in the other datasets.

Important to note is the low precision score obtained by almost all models, especially when it comes to dyskinesia and hallucinations. A major reason for this is the large class imbalance that can be observed in the dataset. In the dyskinesia PPMI dataset for example, only 228 out of 4551, or about 5% of the visits are 'positives' for the binary classification task. In addition, even when almost all of the risk factors are met, it is still uncertain whether a specific side-effect will occur. For example, the calibration curve of Figure 8.3 shows that the model will only very rarely t a risk of more than 20%. Thus, it is simply a very challenging task to prevent false positives in earlier visits, while precisely pinning down the exact visit in which the side effect will occur for the first time. Nevertheless, though these low precision values show the difficulty for the models to perform discrimination, the calibration curves show rather well calibrated models that output good estimates of the empirical risk.

The feature contributions of Figure 8.4 align well with expectations of the clinical partners. For instance, for dyskinesia, total LEDD, the accumulated LEDD years, time since the PD

diagnosis, younger age of diagnosis and the presence of COMT inhibitors are retrieved as the major risk factors. The clinical interpretation of the contribution of the accumulated LEDD years is still up for discussion. Since it is not trivial to exactly separate the influence of accumulated LEDD years from both the disease duration and the current LEDD dosage, we will further statistically investigate the exact relation between accumulated LEDD and dyskinesias. Hallucinations are mostly related to the current UPDRS II and I state, and the presence of amantadine or dopamine agonist medication. Finally, excessive daytime sleepiness is correlated with current mild sleepiness, older age, older age at diagnosis, the current UPDRS I scores and the presence of dopamine agonists.

Next, we analyse the cross-dataset performances and within-dataset performances of Table 8.5. While we typically observe a certain performance decrease when training on a different dataset than the one we evaluate on, we can observe that the performance decrease in AUROC is rather small. This implies that models trained on one dataset do not overfit too much on this specific dataset and generalize rather well. We also observe that in the cross-dataset training, it becomes harder to balance sensitivity and specificity, meaning that a decision threshold trained to work at a certain operating point on one dataset, might not make the same trade-off in a different dataset. One cause of this is the difference in prevalence between the datasets. For instance, in NET-PD LS-1, about 2.5% of visits contain dyskinesia's, while this is 5% in PPMI. Thus, a decision threshold learned for NET-PD LS-1, will be relatively low when applied to PPMI, resulting in sensitivity rising at the cost of specificity, as also observed in these results. A similar shift can be observed in the expected calibration error, demonstrating the difficulty of transferring models trained on one dataset to an external one, without a small calibration set to update the model.

Finally, the joint dataset performances show only marginal increases in performance compared to the within dataset performances, in spite of our original hypothesis that increased heterogeneity in data could improve predictive performance. However, it is still likely that such a pooled model will generalize better to new, external datasets due to the increased variety in patient profiles it has learned from.

Due to the usage of Random Forests, the models naturally lend themselves well towards missing data. Nevertheless, a thorough analysis on how robust the model is in recovering performance in the absence of certain features can still be performed.

The goal is to implement the model trained on the pooled data in an intuitive interface (AIMED module of the mAI-Insights platform for HCPs) where the user can input medications, which class they belong to and the envisioned dosage, allowing a report to then be generated on the risk of the side effects along with an explanation based on the SHAP values. The major envisioned user of this application are the healthcare professionals responsible for determining the medication, although no particular expertise should be required to operate the application by itself. The next major steps will be comprehensive evaluation of the pooled dataset model on an external dataset to get a full picture on its generalisability.

7.4.2 Beyond SoA

The presented medication response model advances the currently existing state of the art as follows:

- **Extensive generalization analysis:** Existing literature aiming to predict outcomes such as dyskinesia are typically limited to training and evaluation within a single dataset. This work has extensively analysed how performance varies within-dataset, cross-dataset and whether performance increases can be obtained by pooling different datasets.

- **Extensive and accurate evaluation of all relevant metrics:** Typically, evaluation in existing work is based solely on AUROC, which is insufficient to evaluate the applicability of a model in clinical context. In contrast, we have evaluated balanced accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity and AUROC. In addition, we have performed calibration analysis, reporting both calibration curves and expected calibration error (ECE). Finally, enormous care was taken to avoid mistakes in literature that could lead to overoptimistic performance metrics, such as the inclusion of healthy controls.
- **Bias and fairness assessment:** We conducted a thorough bias assessment for the sensitive variables age, sex, education level and race. In general, signs of bias were only observed in subgroups with an extremely limited sample size, where any bias assessment is unreliable in the first place.

7.4.3 Limitations

Several limitations have already been described in the previous section, primarily due to the general difficulty of directly generalizing from one dataset to another and the challenging nature of the first incidence prediction task, as well as its large class imbalance. Currently, the main limitations are the lack of a validation of the pooled model on external datasets to quantify if and how much this model generalizes better than datasets trained on single models.

8 Open science

8.1 Data sharing

All datasets used to develop and evaluate the predictive models outlined in this report were obtained after formal data access applications. Please refer to Section 3 for more information on the datasets. The dBM-DEV Study Dataset used to evaluate the SAM-PD score for the estimation of PD risk, was collected under the AI-PROGNOSIS project and will be openly available after the end of the project.

8.2 Code sharing

All codes supporting the findings of this study will be made openly available after publishing the results of the current deliverable in peer reviewed journals.

9 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Compliance

For the purpose of development and evaluation of the PD predictive models, the AI-PROGNOSIS team utilised research datasets, consisting exclusively of anonymised records derived from longitudinal clinical studies. Prior to our access, all direct and indirect identifiers were removed by the data providers, ensuring that no data subject could be identified by our team through any reasonably likely means. Nevertheless, our consortium chose to implement the already adopted, GDPR aligned, measures and procedures, as part of our ethically and legally compliant data management framework (see D1.4 'Ethics and data protection impact assessment report (midterm)'). By adhering to these standards, the AI-PROGNOSIS project ensures that, even when processing anonymised data, the use of information remains aligned with the GDPR provisions and broader ethical considerations governing health-related research data.

All data processing activities were conducted in accordance with the GDPR's fundamental principles of purpose limitation and data minimisation. The datasets were used exclusively for the development, evaluation, and validation of the predictive models and no action was undertaken that could lead to the re-identification of individuals, in line with our contractual and ethical obligations to the data providers. Access to the data was strictly limited to authorised project partners and all processing operations were confined to data categories demonstrably necessary for the predefined purpose. Prior to processing, a rigorous assessment was carried out to determine the relevance and necessity of each data element, ensuring full compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements.

10 Conclusions

The key takeaways of the current report are:

- The objective of this multi-study report was to integrate genetic, clinical, and digital biomarker data across different datasets to develop predictive models for PD risk estimation, progression prediction, and medication response evaluation.
- These three types of models were successfully developed and internally validated addressing PD risk estimation, progression prediction and medication response, demonstrating the feasibility of AI-driven approaches to support early diagnosis and personalized disease monitoring and management.
- Fastpop analysis showed that the AMP-PD cohort is predominantly of European ancestry, providing a consistent genetic background for analysis. PD risk PRSs replicated expected patterns, with the latest 2025 SNP set offering slightly stronger case–control discrimination than earlier models. In contrast, none of the PRSs examined showed meaningful associations with PD progression, underscoring the current limitations of genetic predictors for disease evolution.
- The SAM-PD risk model combined wearable-derived sleep and activity related features with clinicodemographic data to achieve strong discrimination between PwPD and HC with excellent test-retest reliability. The model's potential to be utilised as an early, unobtrusive biomarker was evidenced by the significant correlation with DaTscan SBR and SAA positivity in people at risk to develop PD. The SAM-PD score improved the performance of the MDS-PD risk score.
- The yearly progression model combined clinical assessments with wearable digital biomarkers to predict predefined clinical progression outcomes as well as to predict membership in data-driven progression subtypes derived from clinical data alone. The results demonstrate that wearable-derived features provide complementary value beyond clinical measures, improving predictive performance for both clinically defined outcomes and data-driven progression subtypes.
- A novel deep learning framework, namely PDualNet, was proposed to simultaneously predict PD progression subtypes and future clinical severity scores using longitudinal patient data. The model was trained and validated using data from PPMI dataset, while additional validation was performed on PDBP dataset, demonstrating strong performance and generalizability across both tasks.
- The medication response model, trained on three CPP datasets to predict adverse outcomes such as dyskinesia, showed robust predictive accuracy across datasets with the key features leveraged for its prediction being aligned with clinical expectations, demonstrating its potential to guide personalised medication regimes.

- AI model explainability was achieved using SHAP, Gini index and LIME. These approaches provided clinically interpretable insights into specific feature contributions.
- Further development is needed to ensure fairness in the model performances to ensure robust and unbiased predictions across different demographic subgroups.
- Together, the results of this report highlight the prognostic value of the AI-PROGNOSIS models. AI-based models can provide complementary tools to support disease management and the robust evaluation of treatment efficacy.

Future efforts will focus on the validation of the models within the AI-PROGNOSIS AI-PRA and AI-PMP clinical studies. Future developments will be reported in deliverable D5.8 'AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem: proof-of-concept and beyond'.

References

- Berg, D., Postuma, R. B., Adler, C. H., Bloem, B. R., Chan, P., Dubois, B., Gasser, T., Goetz, C. G., Halliday, G., Joseph, L., Lang, A. E., Liepelt-Scarfone, I., Litvan, I., Marek, K., Obeso, J., Oertel, W., Olanow, C. W., Poewe, W., Stern, M., & Deuschl, G. (2015). MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*, *30*(12), 1600–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.26431>
- Chairta, P. P., Hadjisavvas, A., Georgiou, A. N., Loizidou, M. A., Yiangou, K., Demetriou, C. A., Christou, Y. P., Pantziaris, M., Michailidou, K., & Zamba-Papanicolaou, E. (2021). Prediction of Parkinson's disease risk based on genetic profile and established risk factors. *Genes*, *12*(8), 1278. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12081278>
- Davergne, T., Kedra, J., & Gossec, L. (2021). Wearable activity trackers and artificial intelligence in the management of rheumatic diseases. *Zeitschrift für Rheumatologie*, *80*(10), 928–935.
- Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2018). BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. *Proceedings of NAACL-HLT 2019*, 4171–4186.
- Doty, R. L., Frye, R. E., & Agrawal, U. (1989). Internal consistency reliability of the fractionated and whole University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *45*, 381–384. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03210709>
- Fang, X., Han, D., Cheng, Q., Zhang, P., Zhao, C., Min, J., & Wang, F. (2018). Association of levels of physical activity with risk of Parkinson disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Network Open*, *1*(5), e182421. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2018.2421>
- Fitzgerald, J. J., Lu, Z., Jareonsettasin, P., & Antoniadou, C. A. (2018). Quantifying motor impairment in movement disorders. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *12*, 202. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2018.00202>
- Freeman, R., Wieling, W., Axelrod, F. B., Benditt, D. G., Calderon, E., Chelimsky, G., Christopher, M. S., Coleman, G. C., El Sayed, H., Figueroa, J. J., Hainsworth, R., Isaacson, S. H., Kaufmann, H., Kelley, J. M., Macefield, V. G., Mayer, S. A., Oppenheimer, S. M., Palma, J. A., Raj, S. R., ... Wenning, G. K. (2011). Consensus statement on the definition of orthostatic hypotension, neurally mediated syncope and the postural tachycardia syndrome. *Clinical Autonomic Research*, *21*(2), 69–72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10286-011-0119-5>
- Goetz, C. G., Tilley, B. C., Shaftman, S. R., Stebbins, G. T., Fahn, S., Martinez-Martin, P., Poewe, W., Sampaio, C., Stern, M. B., Dodel, R., Dubois, B., Holloway, R., Jankovic, J., Kulisevsky, J., Lang, A. E., Lees, A., Leurgans, S., LeWitt, P. A., Nyenhuis, D., ... LaPelle, N. (2008). Movement Disorder Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS): Scale presentation and clinimetric testing results. *Movement Disorders*, *23*(15), 2129–2170. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.22340>
- Gossec, L., Guyard, F., Leroy, D., Lafargue, T., Seiler, M., Jacquemin, C., ... & Servy, H. (2019). Detection of flares by decrease in physical activity, collected using wearable activity trackers in rheumatoid arthritis or axial spondyloarthritis: An application of machine learning analyses in rheumatology. *Arthritis Care & Research*, *71*(10), 1336–1343.
- Hähnel, T., et al. (2024). Progression subtypes in Parkinson's disease identified by a data-driven multi-cohort analysis. *NPJ Parkinson's Disease*, *10*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-024-00712-3>

- Heinzel S, Berg D, Gasser T, Chen H, Yao C, Postuma RB; MDS Task Force on the Definition of Parkinson's Disease. Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*. 2019 Oct;34(10):1464-1470. doi: 10.1002/mds.27802.
- Iakovakis, D., Hadjidimitriou, S., Charisis, V., Bostantzopoulou, S., Katsarou, Z., & Hadjileontiadis, L. J. (2018). Touchscreen typing-pattern analysis for detecting fine motor skills decline in early-stage Parkinson's disease. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 7663. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25999-0>
- Johns, M. W. (1991). A new method for measuring daytime sleepiness: The Epworth Sleepiness Scale. *Sleep*, 14(6), 540–545. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/14.6.540>
- Jost, S. T., Kaldenbach, M. A., Antonini, A., Martinez-Martin, P., Timmermann, L., Odin, P., ... & International Parkinson and Movement Disorders Society Non-Motor Parkinson Disease Study Group. (2023). Levodopa dose equivalency in Parkinson's disease: Updated systematic review and proposals. *Movement Disorders*, 38(7), 1236–1252.
- Kaye, A. D., Perkinson, K. A., Spillers, N. J., Vega, A. J., Roberts, C. J., Downs, E. M., Sheth, M. M., McGregor, D. W., Jr., Ahmadzadeh, S., Mathew, J., & Shekoochi, S. (2024). Parkinson's Disease: A Narrative of the Evolving Understanding of the Role of α -Synuclein in Screening. *Current Issues in Molecular Biology*, 46(11), 12746-12755. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb46110757>
- Kiebertz, K., et al. (2015). Effect of creatine monohydrate on clinical progression in patients with Parkinson disease: A randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*, 313(6), 584–593.
- Kim, J. J., Vitale, D., Otani, D. V., Lian, M. M., Heilbron, K., 23andMe Research Team, Iwaki, H., Lake, J., Solsberg, C. W., Leonard, H., Makarios, M. B., Tan, E. K., Singleton, A. B., Bandres-Ciga, S., Noyce, A. J., Global Parkinson's Genetics Program (GP2), Blauwendraat, C., Nalls, M. A., Foo, J. N., & Mata, I. (2024). Multi-ancestry genome-wide association meta-analysis of Parkinson's disease. *Nature Genetics*, 56(1), 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01584-8>
- Kline, E. M., Houser, M. C., Herrick, M. K., Seibler, P., Klein, C., West, A., & Tansey, M. G. (2021). Genetic and environmental factors in Parkinson's disease converge on immune function and inflammation. *Movement Disorders*, 36(1), 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.28411>
- Lea, C., Flynn, M. D., Vidal, R., Reiter, A., & Hager, G. D. (2016). Temporal convolutional networks for action segmentation and detection. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 1003–1012. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2017.113>
- Leonard, H. L., & Global Parkinson's Genetics Program (GP2). (2025). Novel Parkinson's disease genetic risk factors within and across European populations. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.14.24319455>
- Malek, N., Swallow, D. M., Grosset, K. A., Lawton, M. A., Marrinan, S. L., Lehn, A. C., ... & PRoBaND Clinical Consortium. (2015). Tracking Parkinson's: Study design and baseline patient data. *Journal of Parkinson's Disease*, 5(4), 947–959.
- Marek, K., et al. (2018). The Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) – establishing a PD biomarker cohort. *Annals of Clinical and Translational Neurology*, 5(12), 1460. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.644>
- Marees, A. T., de Kluiver, H., Stringer, S., Vorspan, F., Curis, E., Marie-Claire, C., & Derks, E. M. (2018). A tutorial on conducting genome-wide association studies: Quality control and statistical analysis. *International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research*, 27(2), e1608. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpr.1608>

- Mavaddat, N., Michailidou, K., Dennis, J., Lush, M., Fachal, L., Lee, A., Tyrer, J. P., Chen, T. H., Wang, Q., Bolla, M. K., Yang, X., Adank, M. A., Ahearn, T., Aittomaki, K., Allen, J., Andrulis, I. L., Anton-Culver, H., Antonenkova, N. N., Arndt, V., ... Easton, D. F. (2019). Polygenic risk scores for prediction of breast cancer and breast cancer subtypes. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 104(1), 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajhg.2018.11.002>
- Menza, M., Dobkin, R. D., Marin, H., & Bienfait, K. (2010). Sleep disturbances in Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*, 25(S1), S117–S122. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.22788>
- Nalls, M. A., Blauwendraat, C., Vallerga, C. L., Heilbron, K., Bandres-Ciga, S., Chang, D., Tan, M., Kia, D. A., Noyce, A. J., Xue, A., Bras, J., Young, E., von Coelln, R., Simón-Sánchez, J., Schulte, C., Sharma, M., Krohn, L., Pihlstrøm, L., Siitonen, A., Iwaki, H., ... International Parkinson's Disease Genomics Consortium. (2019). Identification of novel risk loci, causal insights, and heritable risk for Parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies. *The Lancet Neurology*, 18(12), 1091–1102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(19\)30320-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(19)30320-5)
- Nasreddine, Z. S., et al. (2005). The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA): A brief screening tool for mild cognitive impairment. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 53, 695–699. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-5415.2005.53221.x>
- Ofori, E., Du, G., Babcock, D., Huang, X., & Vaillancourt, D. E. (2015). Parkinson's Disease Biomarkers Program brain imaging repository. *NeuroImage*, 124, 1120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.05.005>
- Paul, K. C., Schulz, J., Bronstein, J. M., Lill, C. M., & Ritz, B. R. (2018). Association of polygenic risk score with cognitive decline and motor progression in Parkinson disease. *JAMA Neurology*, 75(3), 360–366. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2017.4206>
- Pereira, G. M., Teixeira-dos-Santos, D., Soares, N. M., et al. (2024). A systematic review and meta-analysis of the prevalence of Parkinson's disease in lower to upper-middle-income countries. *NPJ Parkinson's Disease*, 10, 181. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-024-00779-y>
- Rizou, V., Grammalidis, N., Daras, P. et al. PDualNet: a deep learning framework for joint prediction of Parkinson's disease progression subtype and MDS-UPDRS scores. *Sci Rep* 15, 41931 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-25812-9>
- Schalkamp, A. K., Peall, K. J., Harrison, N. A., & Sandor, C. (2023). Wearable movement-tracking data identify Parkinson's disease years before clinical diagnosis. *Nature Medicine*, 29(8), 2048–2056. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-023-02440-2>
- Schalkamp, A. K., Peall, K. J., Harrison, N. A., Escott-Price, V., Barnaghi, P., & Sandor, C. (2025). Wearables-derived risk score for unintrusive detection of α -synuclein aggregation or dopaminergic deficit. *EBioMedicine*, 117, 105782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2025.105782>
- Severson, K. A., Chahine, L. M., Smolensky, L. A., Dhuliawala, M., Frasier, M., Ng, K., Ghosh, S., & Hu, J. (2021). Discovery of Parkinson's disease states and disease progression modelling: A longitudinal data study using machine learning. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 3(9), e555–e564. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(21\)00101-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(21)00101-1)
- Sia, M. W., Foo, J. N., Saffari, S. E., Wong, A. S., Khor, C. C., Yuan, J. M., Tan, E. K., Koh, W. P., & Tan, L. C. (2021). Polygenic risk scores in a prospective Parkinson's disease cohort. *Movement Disorders*, 36(12), 2936–2940. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.28761>

- Siderowf, A. (2010). Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living Scale. In *Encyclopedia of Movement Disorders* (Vol. 3, pp. 99–100). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-374105-9.00070-8>
- Sotirakis, C., Su, Z., Brzezicki, M. A., Conway, N., Tarassenko, L., FitzGerald, J. J., & Antoniadou, C. A. (2023). Identification of motor progression in Parkinson's disease using wearable sensors and machine learning. *NPJ Parkinson's Disease*, 9(1), 142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-023-00581-2>
- Stebbins, G. T., Goetz, C. G., Burn, D. J., Jankovic, J., Khoo, T. K., & Tilley, B. C. (2013). How to identify tremor dominant and postural instability/gait difficulty groups with the Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale: Comparison with the Old Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale. *Movement Disorders*, 28(5), 661–666. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.25383>
- Su, C., et al. (2024). Identification of Parkinson's disease pace subtypes and repurposing treatments through integrative analyses of multimodal data. *NPJ Digital Medicine*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01175-9>
- Tinaz, S., Chow, C., Kuo, P. H., Krupinski, E. A., Blumenfeld, H., Louis, E. D., & Zubal, G. (2018). Semiquantitative analysis of dopamine transporter scans in patients with Parkinson disease. *Clinical Nuclear Medicine*, 43(1), e1–e7. <https://doi.org/10.1097/RLU.0000000000001885>
- Troyanskaya, O., et al. (2001). Missing value estimation methods for DNA microarrays. *Bioinformatics*, 17(6), 520–525. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/17.6.520>
- van Buuren, S., & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, K. (2011). MICE: Multivariate imputation by chained equations in R. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 45(3), 1–67. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v045.i03>
- Vaswani, A., et al. (2017). Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 5998–6008.
- Yanar, E., Hardalaç, F., & Ayturan, K. (2025). CELM: An ensemble deep learning model for early cardiomegaly diagnosis in chest radiography. *Diagnostics*, 15, 1602.
- Yanar, E., Hardalaç, F., & Ayturan, K. (2025). PELM: A deep learning model for early detection of pneumonia in chest radiography. *Applied Sciences*, 15, 6487.
- Yao, Y., Yu, B., Gong, C., & Liu, T. (2023). Understanding how pretraining regularizes deep learning algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 34, 5828–5840. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2021.3131377>
- Zanardi, A. P. J., da Silva, E. S., Costa, R. R., Passos-Monteiro, E., Dos Santos, I. O., Kruegel, L. F. M., & Peyre-Tartaruga, L. A. (2021). Gait parameters of Parkinson's disease compared with healthy controls: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 752. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-80768-2>